

Capstone Project

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Master of Business Administration (90 ECTS)

**Raising Women's Participation in Cash for Work Programmes in Jordan:
Gender-Responsive Feasibility-Based Recommendations and a Pipeline-Stage Monitoring
Framework**

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Dedication

To Ahmad, my husband, my best friend, and the love of my life. You inspired me to take the first step, provided the comfort to commit, and have been my proudest supporter every step of the way since. Since we met, we have shared our passions, successes, and most importantly, our support for each other, no matter what. It is a grace to have you in my life.

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Abstract

Women's participation in Cash-for-Work (CfW) programmes in Jordan has persistently fallen short of targets despite repeated identification of the same barriers. What the evidence base has lacked is not more barrier documentation, but a practitioner-level mapping of which design features are feasible under current constraints, and whether monitoring data is actually reaching the people who make design decisions.

This exploratory study addresses both gaps, using a cross-sectional quantitative survey of 23 CfW implementers across two structurally distinct regulatory environments: the Incentive-Based Volunteering (IBV) framework governing refugee camp settings and the work-permit framework governing host-community delivery.

The findings reveal a consistent pattern of infrastructure without follow-through. Transport support, rated highly feasible and associated with the strongest completion signals when implemented, remained absent from 61% of programmes. All camp programmes used digital payment systems, yet only 56% of payments were made directly into women's own accounts. 27% of programme managers could not report their own programme's women's participation target or achieved rate, a pattern consistent with a breakdown in the feedback mechanism connecting monitoring evidence to design decisions.

The study derived a minimum viable package of six programme-operable design measures and a 16-indicator pipeline-stage monitoring framework. Within the reviewed CfW literature on Jordan, no prior evaluation identifies this monitoring-to-decision feedback gap as a distinct obstacle to gender-responsive implementation.

Keywords: Cash-for-Work, women's economic participation, programme design, Jordan, refugee livelihoods, gender-responsive monitoring, gender-responsive design

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full term
BNLWG	Basic Needs and Livelihoods Working Group
CfW	Cash-for-Work
DEval	German Institute for Development Evaluation
FCFS	First-come, first-served
GBV	Gender-Based Violence
GIZ	Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit GmbH
IBV	Incentive-based volunteering
ILO	International Labour Organization
LFP	Labour Force Participation
MEAL	Monitoring, Evaluation, Accountability and Learning
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
PPE	Personal Protective Equipment
RAIS	Refugee Assistance Information System
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
UN	United Nations
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees

1. Introduction

1.1 Context

Globally, Cash-for-Work (CfW) and labour-intensive public works (LIPW) programmes are implemented across displacement, post-conflict, and climate-shock contexts in sub-Saharan Africa, the Middle East, South and Southeast Asia, and the Horn of Africa. Key implementing agencies include the ILO, WFP, UNHCR, GIZ, and implementing NGOs, with bilateral donors including Germany, the Netherlands, and Norway serving as principal funders (Loewe et al., 2020, pp. 55–58). IOM additionally implements cash-based interventions across displacement contexts globally (IOM, 2023). Jordan can be considered as one of the most institutionally structured CfW delivery systems in the MENA region, combining mandatory Standard Operating Procedure (SOP)-governed camp delivery with a multi-actor host communities' framework, a duality that makes it a particularly informative case for examining the relationship between design features, regulatory constraints, and women's participation (see Sections 2.8 and 3.2).

Jordan's displacement context is both large-scale and institutionally organised. Jordan hosts one of the largest Syrian refugee populations in the world. At the time of the CfW programming examined in this study, over 650,000 Syrian refugees were registered with UNHCR (UNHCR, 2025a). As of April 2026, following large-scale returns to Syria, this figure had declined to 396,640 (UNHCR, 2026), a shift whose implications for CfW programme design fall outside the scope of this study but are noted in Section 6.5. UNHCR coordinates a range of response functions, including protection, legal assistance, cash support, access to health and education, community outreach, livelihoods, and camp management in Za'atari and Azraq refugee camps. Within this framework, partner organisations implement CfW activities that link vulnerable refugees and members of host communities to time-bound employment (UNHCR, 2025a). In practice, CfW programmes engage workers for a fixed period of at least 40 days, at a standardised daily wage set in accordance with inter-agency standard operating procedures. Workers are registered for social security, assigned to mixed nationality teams to promote social cohesion between refugee and host communities participants, and deployed on activities such as road maintenance, solid waste management, greening and tree planting, and the rehabilitation of public facilities (Basic Needs and Livelihoods Working Group [BNLWG], 2020, Section 2.1; ILO, 2021, p. 15). Key implementing organisations include the ILO, GIZ, WFP, UN Women, and national and international non-governmental organisations (NGOs), which operate in coordination with UNHCR, relevant ministries, and municipal authorities (Loewe et al., 2020, pp. 48–55).

CfW and LIPW programmes have gained prominence in development and humanitarian policy for their ability to combine short-term employment with the delivery of public goods and infrastructure. LIPW is the broad category; within this, the ILO's Employment-Intensive Infrastructure Programmes (EIIPs) are a specific programmatic model that links infrastructure development with employment creation through local resource-based technologies (ILO, 2021, pp. 15, 28). CfW is the most widely used operational term in Jordan's humanitarian context, covering EIIP-funded activities alongside

other donor-funded short-term work programmes implemented through UN agencies, GIZ, and NGOs. Because this study examines design features across all implementing organisations, the term CfW is used throughout.

Since 2016, donors have supported several CfW initiatives targeting Syrian refugees and vulnerable Jordanians, implemented through ministries, municipalities, and refugee camp settings (Loewe et al., 2020, p. 48). CfW has increased local economic activity and supported women's participation in paid work (Loewe et al., 2020, pp. 107, 121). In Jordan's displacement context, the dual logic of income support combined with community infrastructure has made CfW particularly attractive to donors seeking to address both livelihood stress and the economic and social tensions in refugee-host communities simultaneously (Loewe et al., 2020, p. 55). However, access remains limited for women due to prevailing social norms, particularly when work occurs in public spaces or involves construction, and design measures are needed to enable women's participation and completion (Loewe et al., 2020, pp. 104–105).

The broader labour market context underscores the structural barriers women face and the urgency of deliberate design responses. In quarter 3, 2025, the total unemployment rate for all residents was 16.2%. Among Jordanians, unemployment was 21.4% (18.0% for men; 33.9% for women), while for those aged 24 and above, it was 17.2% (13.5% for men; 30.1% for women). In contrast, among non-Jordanians, unemployment was lower at 9.2% (8.1% for men; 14.7% for women), with rates for non-Jordanians aged 24 and above at 6.4% for men and 11.5% for women (Department of Statistics Jordan, 2025).

Women constitute 56.8% of informal workers in Jordan, predominantly in sectors with limited protection (EuroMed Feminist Initiative, 2023, pp. 8–9), which underscores why the design quality of short-term work programmes matters: CfW may represent one of the few accessible, regulated income opportunities available to women who would otherwise be absorbed into the informal economy on worse terms.

1.2 Problem

Despite a decade of CfW investment in Jordan, with a total programme budget reaching EUR 300 million between 2016 and 2019, women's participation has remained persistently below targets (Zintl & Loewe, 2022, pp. 1292, 1298). The most recent ILO programme (Phase VI) data illustrate the scale of the shortfall: in Jordan, only 1,079 jobs were created against a target of 2,500, a target that itself specified 30% women's participation, and the evaluation notes that gender composition targets have proven difficult to achieve consistently across programme sites (ILO, 2024, pp. 49–50). Women's participation is not an automatic consequence of programme existence; it is an implementation outcome shaped by programme architecture (ILO, 2021, p. 32). Participation is not a single event but a sequence of stages, from hearing about an opportunity, through application, eligibility, selection, starting work, and sustained attendance to completion, each of which can fail independently.

This study refers to that sequence as the participation pipeline and distinguishes two broad stages: entry, covering everything before work begins, and completion, covering everything after it starts. CfW programmes include a third pipeline stage, post-programme labour market transition, which assesses whether women move into sustained employment, self-employment, or further training after the work cycle ends. This stage falls outside the scope of this study, which focuses exclusively on the design features that enable women to enter and complete a CfW cycle. Post-programme transition is identified as a priority for future research in Section 6.5.

The problem is not a lack of awareness that gender barriers exist. Evaluations repeatedly identify the same constraints, household consent, documentation requirements, transport gaps, work-type acceptability, and inadequate worksite conditions (ILO, 2021, p. 32; ILO, 2024, pp. 37, 49–50; Loewe et al., 2020, pp. 104–105), yet implementation data implied that these constraints remain largely unaddressed (ILO, 2024, pp. 47-50; German Institute for Development Evaluation [DEval], 2021, p. 9). The knowledge that better design is needed has not translated into consistent practice. What is missing is not more evaluation of whether gender barriers exist, but an implementer-level, practice-oriented mapping of which specific design features are associated with higher women's uptake and completion, how feasible they are under Jordan's specific regulatory constraints, namely the camp-based incentive-based volunteering (IBV) framework governing Za'atari and Azraq, and the work-permit requirements applying to Syrian refugees in host communities, and what minimum standards practitioners can actually operationalise within a single programme cycle. These two delivery settings operate under fundamentally different regulatory architectures. In camp settings, CfW delivery is governed by mandatory Standard Operating Procedures administered under UNHCR's coordination authority (BNLWG, 2020; BNLWG, 2022). In host communities, a CfW Working Group co-chaired by ILO and GIZ coordinates implementing agencies voluntarily (ILO, 2024, p. 17), and design measures that are achievable in one setting may not be transferable to the other (BNLWG, 2020; ILO, 2021, p. 32). Existing evaluations identify barriers and recommend measures, but do not systematically assess feasibility from the perspective of CfW implementers working under current conditions: monitoring and evaluation have focused on counting jobs, headcounts and percentage of women share, rather than on understanding where and why the participation pipeline fails (ILO, 2021, pp. 35-36; ILO, 2024, pp. 47–50; DEval, 2021, p. 9). This study addresses that gap.

The consequences of persistently low uptake and non-completion extend beyond individual households: at the programme level, they represent a failure to achieve the 'double dividend' of wage employment and infrastructure creation that donor-funded CfW is designed to deliver. Independent evaluations continue to find that "scope remains to better realise the programme objectives" precisely because women's participation remains structurally constrained (ILO, 2024, p. 45). At the policy level, they perpetuate the exclusion of refugee women from what is, in many parts of Jordan, the only realistic point of entry into the labour market available to them (Loewe et al., 2020, p. 107-108), deepening protection and self-reliance gaps that successive programming cycles have yet to close.

1.3 Research Question

Which Cash-for-Work (CfW) design features are associated with higher women's uptake and completion in Jordan, and how can these be implemented feasibly within current regulatory and delivery constraints?

1.4 Objectives

This study aimed to develop evidence-informed design recommendations based on practitioners' reported practices and perceptions in CfW programmes in Jordan. The study has five objectives: (1) to identify constraints limiting women's uptake and completion at each stage of the participation pipeline, based on practitioner-reported practices and perceptions; (2) to map which design features practitioners associate most strongly with women's uptake and completion at each pipeline stage, and to assess their perceived feasibility across delivery settings and respondent roles; (3) to benchmark current CfW design and monitoring practices across the two delivery settings against existing evaluation frameworks and implementing organisation standards for gender-inclusive programme design; (4) to develop recommendations distinguishing measures that can be implemented within a single programme cycle through existing procurement, staffing, and operational authority (programme-operable) from measures that depend on policy reform, infrastructure investment, or inter-institutional coordination beyond the individual programme's scope (policy-dependent); and (5) to propose a pipeline-stage monitoring framework and a compact set of indicators that implementers can use to track women's uptake, completion, and enabling conditions within routine programme reporting.

1.5 Methodological Overview

The study used a cross-sectional design with descriptive and comparative subgroup analyses. The analytical framework draws on secondary sources, evaluations, SOPs, practitioner guides, labour market data, and national policy frameworks. In practice, the range of available CfW-specific sources on Jordan was narrower than expected, which is itself a finding: the evidence base this study had to work with reflects the same gaps in systematic documentation that the study identifies as a problem. The study takes a practitioner perspective, treating implementers as the primary informants, because the research question concerns operational design decisions made by programme staff rather than participants. Primary data are then collected through a closed-ended questionnaire administered via the Qualtrics online survey platform (Qualtrics International Inc., n.d.) from CfW programme managers, field officers, Monitoring, Evaluation, Accountability, and Learning (MEAL) staff, and safeguarding professionals working in Jordan. The analysis is descriptive and comparative, examining patterns across delivery settings and respondent roles without inferential statistical testing. Full methodological details are presented in Chapter 3.

1.6 Structure of the Thesis

This study is organised into six chapters. Chapter 1 introduces the study context, problem, research question, objectives, and methodological overview. Chapter 2 reviews implementation-oriented literature across six design domains, organised around the two-stage participation pipeline, and derives the analytical framework. Chapter 3 details the quantitative cross-sectional survey design, sampling strategy, questionnaire instrument, data management procedures, and ethical considerations. Chapter 4 presents descriptive results and setting-based comparisons across all six design domains. Chapter 5 discusses findings in relation to the literature, synthesises feasibility evidence, and sets out 36 operational recommendations. Chapter 6 answers the research question, states the study's contributions, revisits the objectives, identifies limitations, and proposes directions for future research.

2. Literature Review

The literature search prioritises sources published between 2021 and 2025. Four older sources are kept where no more recent equivalent exists. Penchansky and Thomas (1981) provide the theoretical foundation for the access framework used in Section 2.1. Loewe et al. (2020) remains the most rigorous empirical study of CfW effects in Jordan, with no comparable successor covering gender, task acceptability, work permit data, and programme design. Oxfam (2018) is cited for specific findings on women's CfW participation in Za'atari camp, for which no more recent participant-level study exists. BNLWG (2020) remains the only governance document for the Azraq IBV framework, and no revised version has been issued since 2020.

The literature reviewed in this chapter was produced in a higher-caseload context; most sources predate the large-scale returns to Syria that reduced Jordan's registered Syrian refugee population from over 650,000 to 396,640 by April 2026 (UNHCR, 2025a; UNHCR, 2026). The structural barriers to women's participation documented across these sources reflect the conditions under which the programmes examined in this study were designed and delivered; their relevance to programme design is not negated by the caseload shift, but readers should note that scale-dependent assumptions, such as programme demand, resource allocation, and demographic pressure, may not hold in the current environment.

2.1 Theoretical Framing: Access Theory and the Participation Pipeline

Why access theory? This study uses access theory, developed by Penchansky and Thomas (1981, pp. 127–128), to understand why women do or do not participate in CfW programmes. The theory identifies five conditions that must be met for someone to participate in a service. The service must be physically reachable (accessibility). It must be affordable (affordability). It must be socially acceptable (acceptability). Its schedule and operations must fit the participant's daily life (accommodation). And it must have enough places to meet demand (availability). Each condition must be met separately. Removing one barrier does not remove the others. A programme that reaches

women through effective outreach does not automatically resolve the barriers that stop them from attending consistently.

A Theory of Change (ToC) was considered as an alternative framework, because it is widely used in development programme evaluation. A ToC requires that the link between a specific design feature and a participation outcome can be clearly defined and tested in advance. That requirement cannot be met here. The study uses a descriptive survey design, and the existing literature does not yet support causal claims at the feature level about CfW participation. Access theory does not require causal claims. It provides a structured way to identify where the fit between a programme and its intended participants breaks down, which maps directly onto the question this study asks: which specific design features are associated with participation failures, and which can be addressed within a single delivery cycle?

Entry and completion are two separate stages. In CfW, access theory means that design solutions must be targeted at two distinct stages: getting women in (entry) and keeping them in (completion). Evaluations show that a programme can succeed at one stage while failing at the other (ILO, 2021, p. 10; ILO, 2024, pp. 49–50). The 2024 ILO cluster evaluation shows how combining these two stages into a single participation rate hides important differences. In the Jordan Phase VI programme, 1,079 jobs were created against a target of 2,500 (which set a 30% women's participation target). Worker-days reached 94,837 against a target of 220,000 (ILO, 2024, pp. 49–50). These two figures tell different stories. A woman who worked 30 days and then dropped out contributes to worker-days but not to the job headcount, which only counts participants who reached 40 days. Treating entry and completion as separate stages makes this difference visible.

Six design domains. The five access dimensions map onto the six design domains that organise this study. Availability maps onto recruitment, outreach, and selection, whether programme opportunities reach women at all. Acceptability maps onto work design and work type, whether the work itself is socially and culturally appropriate for women. Accommodation maps onto worksite conditions, safety, and protection, whether the daily working environment supports women's sustained attendance. Accessibility maps onto time, transport, and childcare, whether the schedule, location, and care arrangements make attendance practically possible. Affordability maps onto payment modality and financial control, whether the wage reaches the woman directly and remains under her control.

A sixth domain, monitoring, is added beyond the original Penchansky and Thomas framework. The CfW literature identifies monitoring as a distinct operational failure point, where existing indicators track outputs but do not capture where in the participation pipeline women drop out (ILO, 2024, pp. 47–50, 67). These six domains organise the literature review, structure the survey instrument, and frame the analysis and recommendations in Chapters 4 and 5.

How the delivery setting shapes access. The delivery setting, refugee camp or host communities,

determines which barriers are most severe at each stage. In Za'atari camp, as of December 2022, the IBV (the volunteering scheme governing camp CfW delivery) scheme engaged approximately 3,208 people, nearly 10% of the camp population aged 18 or older, of whom approximately 42% were female (BNLWG, 2022, Section 1). This profile reflects the specific rules and the camp's design. The six domains reviewed below are not generic best-practice categories. They are drawn from the specific barriers documented in Jordan's two delivery settings.

2.2 Recruitment, Outreach, and Selection: Participation Begins Before Work Starts

Before work begins, women's entry into CfW is shaped by three things: how opportunities are advertised, who receives the information, and whether the selection process is seen as fair. Each of these is a design choice, and each one directly affects whether women participate.

How outreach works, and where it fails. The 2021 ILO evaluation links stronger women's participation to outreach through community leaders, culturally appropriate recruitment practices, women-only teams where suitable, and contractor training on gender-specific recruitment and retention (ILO, 2021, p. 8). When outreach relies on male-dominated community networks, women in those communities will be systematically under-informed regardless of their formal eligibility. Reaching women and telling them the right information are two separate problems. Fixing one does not fix the other. Sending job notices by SMS can also reproduce information gaps if women have lower phone ownership or less digital access than men.

Selection and perceived fairness. Selection has a second independent effect on entry. In Jordan, demand for CfW jobs regularly exceeds the number of available positions. When this happens, the selection process becomes a source of social tension, and perceived unfairness reduces women's willingness to apply, even when they are not formally excluded (ILO, 2021, p. 27). Wide advertising and open ballots are recommended as ways to reduce the influence of personal connections and strengthen women's confidence in the process (ILO, 2021, p. 27). In both camp and host-community settings, SOPs (the mandatory operating procedures) and donor guidance commonly require a minimum share of female participants or reserve a proportion of places for women. However, existing evaluations provide little evidence on whether quotas are more effective than other measures, such as targeted outreach or addressing household consent, in increasing women's uptake and completion rates (BNLWG, 2020, Section 3.7; BNLWG, 2022, Section 4).

How camp settings govern recruitment. In refugee camps, recruitment is governed by mandatory SOPs. In the Azraq camp, agencies must advertise opportunities publicly with full details on qualifications, duration, location, working hours, and application procedures. In Za'atari camp, job notices must be posted across multiple district locations, including community centres, to reach women beyond male-dominated networks (BNLWG, 2020, Section 2.1; BNLWG, 2022, Section 3). Eligibility must be checked in advance through the Refugee Assistance Information System (RAIS) and verified by UNHCR's Field Unit at least three days before enrolment (BNLWG, 2022, Section 3).

The eligibility system itself can work against women. In Za'atari, IBV eligibility requires active camp registration and confirmation that no other household member is already in an IBV role. In Azraq, the pre-eligibility check screens applicants against several criteria, including camp residency, service break requirements, and the IBV status of other family members (BNLWG, 2020, Section 3.3.1). Women who lack complete or current documentation cannot pass these checks, regardless of how suitable they are for the role. These checks feed into a scoring system that ranks households by need. Existing evaluations often treat this scoring as a neutral administrative tool. However, evidence from Loewe et al. (2020, pp. 146–147) demonstrates that selection mechanisms are frequently distorted by favouritism (*wasta*) and household clustering. While Loewe documents these structural flaws, existing evaluations do not examine how such score designs, documentation gaps, or household dynamics specifically interact with gender, a gap that warrants urgent attention. Documentation requirements are therefore not neutral; they can block women's access before any selection decision is even made.

A smaller but recurring problem concerns when and where applications are collected. When applications are only accepted during limited weekday hours, or at locations that are far from women's homes or associated with men, women who know about the opportunity and meet the eligibility criteria can still be shut out simply because they cannot reach the application point (Oxfam, 2018, pp. 20–21; Loewe et al., 2020, p. 102, 136, 146; ILO, 2022, p. 54).

How host-community settings govern recruitment. In host-community programmes, recruitment relies on municipal networks, NGO field staff, and contractor outreach. Worker selection uses a structured ballot system in which unskilled workers register by nationality, gender, and disability status and must live within a 20-minute commute of the worksite (ILO, 2024, p. 34). These mechanisms are applied less consistently than the camp SOP framework, and independent evaluations have documented gaps in compliance, including the absence of basic worksite provisions, despite the existence of coordination SOPs (ILO, 2024, pp. 39–40).

Household-level barriers exist before formal recruitment begins. In both settings, a set of barriers operates at the household level, before any formal recruitment mechanism comes into play. In camp settings, the rule that limits each household to one IBV participant per rotation pushes families to favour men when only one slot is available. This happens through domestic decision-making, not through any formal exclusion rule (BNLWG, 2020, Section 3.3.1). Oxfam's Za'atari study found that this one-member-per-household rule had a particularly negative effect on women by reducing the number who could formally apply in the first place (Oxfam, 2018, p. 18).

In host communities, the same pattern operates through social norms rather than programme rules. Families typically consider women's paid work outside the home acceptable only during periods of financial difficulty, and husbands often prefer that their wives work from home (Zintl & Loewe, 2022, p. 1298). The decision of whether to apply is effectively made at home before the programme's selection process begins. Quotas and eligibility rules cannot reach this barrier.

Importantly, household consent is not a fixed barrier. It depends on conditions, which means programmes can influence it. World Bank (2024b, p. 33) identifies the specific conditions under which husbands are more likely to approve of their wives working outside the home, including safe transport and worksites without mixed-gender contact. Where a worksite is located, who else is on the team, and whether transport is provided are not minor operational details. They determine whether a woman's household approves before the programme has any opportunity to recruit her. Programmes that get these conditions right expand the pool of women who can participate. Programmes that ignore them lose women before outreach has even started.

2.3 Work Design, Work-type Acceptability, and Team Composition

Once women enter a CfW programme, the type of work, the team they work with, and how visible the work is in public all affect whether they stay. Task acceptability is something programmes can design for; it is not a fixed cultural constraint (Loewe et al., 2020, pp. 104–107).

Work types that are perceived as appropriate for women. Women's participation is consistently linked to whether the work is socially compatible with their roles. Tasks that take place in public spaces and are traditionally associated with men, particularly waste collection and street-based work, are widely perceived as unsuitable for women. The visibility of the work and the social stigma attached to women performing it in public are the main reasons (Loewe et al., 2020, pp. 104–106). Task design is therefore both an operational and a social question. Programmes that overlook this can expect lower participation, even among eligible and informed women.

At the same time, acceptability is not simply about avoiding certain tasks. Loewe et al. (2020, pp. 106–107) show that some tasks become acceptable when they involve women working with other women, for example, door-to-door awareness activities, and that many women found CfW to be a safer and more respectful work environment than other available options. The relationship works in both directions: designing tasks with social norms in mind may be necessary to secure initial participation, but participation itself can gradually shift those norms over time. This shift is neither automatic nor guaranteed; Loewe et al. (2020, p. 109) caution that changed attitudes toward gender roles may not last after the programme ends. The 2024 ILO cluster evaluation confirms that gender-sensitive implementation included work-type adaptation and women-only team arrangements, but found that programme sensitivity to women's needs remained incomplete, particularly in relation to dignified working conditions, women's access to leadership roles, and protection measures (ILO, 2024, p. 37).

Work type differ between settings. The range of work types available to women differs depending on the delivery setting. In refugee camps, work types are defined by camp governance rules and the IBV framework: community services, administrative and data tasks, light maintenance within camp facilities, and care-related work are the main categories (BNLWG, 2020, Section 2.1; BNLWG, 2022, Section 1). In host communities, a wider range is available, including solid waste management,

greening and landscaping, and community infrastructure work. However, the social acceptability of public-space tasks varies by governorate and community and cannot be predicted from the type of programme alone (Loewe et al., 2020, pp. 104–106).

Supervision and team composition. When programmes cannot offer women-only teams or female supervisors due to staffing or budget constraints, designing work types with social norms in mind becomes even more important. But work-type design alone cannot replace gender-balanced supervision (ILO, 2024, p. 37). Having female supervisors and team leads is a separate and independent design decision. The ILO gender-responsive procurement guide recommends including provisions for a certain share of work attributed to women in managerial positions as a bid requirement in procurement contracts, and both the Zaatari and Azraq IBV frameworks classify team leader and site supervisor roles as contractable IBV positions with defined skill levels and pay rates (ILO, 2022, p. 54; BNLWG, 2020, Annex 1). Providing female supervisors is therefore a staffing decision that programmes can make directly; it does not depend on other choices being made first.

Some programmes have also tried a middle option between women-only and mixed-gender teams: mixed teams that are managed in ways designed to keep women safe, for example, through codes of conduct, clear behavioural expectations, and visible supervision. Existing studies mention this approach but do not treat it as a distinct design option. Its specific effects on women's sense of safety and their likelihood of completing the programme have not been studied in depth (Loewe et al., 2020, p. 104; Zintl & Loewe, 2022, p. 1301).

2.4 Time, Transport, and Childcare: From Background Conditions to Core Design Variables

Across almost all sources in this review, time constraints, transport barriers, and the lack of childcare are the most consistently reported reasons why women do not enter or complete CfW programmes. These are not external circumstances that programmes cannot control. They are specific, measurable conditions that programme design can address, and their absence is enough to prevent women's participation even when everything else is in place.

Proximity and scheduling. The 2021 ILO evaluation reports that transport availability and the difficulty of combining paid work with domestic responsibilities were the most consistent concerns raised by women workers, not occasional complaints, but recurring barriers across the programme's female workforce (ILO, 2021, p. 32). Many women in the Loewe et al. study said CfW was attractive precisely because it was safe, predictable, and close to home (Loewe et al., 2020, p. 107-108). Women in Jordan consistently report that working closer to home lowers transport costs, reduces the risk of harassment on the way to work, and makes it easier to combine paid work with caring for children (Loewe et al., 2020, p. 136; ILO, 2021, p. 32). Proximity is therefore not a secondary convenience; it is a condition that affects whether women complete the programme.

In host communities, worksites are typically chosen based on proposals from municipalities. The

main criteria are cost-sharing arrangements, maintenance capacity, and alignment with programme goals, rather than the proximity of the worksite to where women live (ILO, 2024, p. 34). In camp settings, daily working hours are capped at six and must be specified in job advertisements, as required by the Azraq SOP (BNLWG, 2020, Section 2.1). This limit is not just a welfare measure; it makes participation compatible with household responsibilities. No equivalent scheduling standard exists in host-community programmes, leaving the decision to individual programme managers with inconsistent results for women.

Transport barriers in each setting. Transport problems take different forms depending on the setting. In refugee camps, the physical distances within the camp are short, but movement restrictions and limited affordable transport create specific barriers for women. The evidence on the scale of these barriers predates recent SOP revisions and should be read with caution (Oxfam, 2018, pp. 20–21). In host communities, where distances are longer and transport is less regulated, the barriers are more familiar: infrequent services, fares that take up a significant portion of the daily wage, and safety concerns at bus stops or transit points (Alam & Bagnoli, 2023, pp. 55–57).

Data from Amman shows that three in five women who are not working cite the lack of affordable, safe, and reliable transport as the reason they are not seeking work. A 5-percentage-point improvement in transit safety is estimated to raise women's labour force participation (LFP) by 4.7 percentage points (Alam & Bagnoli, 2023, pp. 10, 73). Even where transport is available and affordable, a woman whose household disapproves of her travelling to work faces a barrier that transport improvements alone cannot remove. For CfW programmes, this means that family acceptance of women's mobility should be treated as something programmes can influence, through outreach, proximity of worksites, and scheduling decisions, rather than a fixed constraint.

Childcare. The shortage of childcare in Jordan is one of the most significant structural barriers to women's participation in paid work. Formal childcare covers less than 3% of the 1.48 million children under five in the country. Research cited by the World Bank (2024b, p. 7) found that 56% of mothers surveyed were unable to enter paid employment due to childcare responsibilities, and that expanding access to free childcare could raise women's LFP by up to 7.3 percentage points. Many districts have almost no licensed childcare facilities at all (World Bank, 2024b, pp. 20–21). For CfW, this means childcare is not only a barrier to entering the programme but also a reason women drop out, as caring responsibilities grow heavier as the programme cycle continues. The UN Women Jordan Office evaluation confirms that lack of affordable childcare, combined with unreliable transport, is a shared barrier for Syrian refugee women in both camp and host-community settings (UN Women Jordan Office, 2024, p. 35).

2.5 Worksite Conditions, Safety, and Protection

Once women start a CfW programme, whether they continue attending depends on whether the worksite remains physically adequate, dignified, and safe throughout the cycle.

What the evidence shows about worksite conditions. The 2024 ILO cluster evaluation found that programmes still need to do more to meet women's specific needs at the worksite, including providing proper water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH) facilities for menstruating women (ILO, 2024, p. 37). Programmes with gender targets and female team leaders can still fail to provide the basic physical conditions that enable sustained attendance. In Jordan specifically, independent evaluators documented worksites without drinking water or toilets (ILO, 2024, p. 33), as well as salary deductions and unstable employment conditions (ILO, 2024, pp. 39–40). These are not hypothetical risks; they were observed in the same delivery context examined in this study.

How protection standards differ between settings. The level of protection available to women depends significantly on the delivery setting. In refugee camps, the IBV SOP framework sets enforceable minimum standards. Implementing agencies must operate complaint mechanisms with at least two ways to report a problem, designate a focal point who is not the direct supervisor, tell participants about the mechanism during enrolment, and respond within three weeks (BNLWG, 2020, Section 5.6; BNLWG, 2022, Section 5). When women cannot safely report problems, leaving the programme becomes the rational choice. Both the Za'atari and Azraq SOPs also provide maternity protection, including one paid hour per day for breastfeeding mothers for up to 1 year after childbirth (BNLWG, 2020, Section 5.5; BNLWG, 2022, Section 2).

In host communities, worksite protections are built into contractor agreements, donor procurement requirements, and programme codes of conduct. These instruments can establish equivalent standards, but whether those standards are met depends on contractor compliance, the capacity to monitor, and the availability of dedicated safeguarding staff, standards that the ILO guide specifies should be embedded in procurement contracts and contractor monitoring (ILO, 2022, pp. 40–45). The same protection measure is therefore more reliably delivered in camp settings than in host-community programmes.

2.6 Payment Modality and Women's Financial Control

How wages are paid is both a practical arrangement and a design decision with gender implications. The payment modality, who controls the account, and whether payments arrive on time all affect women's financial independence and, through it, their willingness to participate and their ability to stay.

Payment modality. The 2021 ILO evaluation reports that, from September 2018, all workers were issued ATM cards and notified by SMS when wages were ready for collection. This reduced the administrative burden on contractors and improved the accuracy and timeliness of payments (ILO, 2021, p. 27). The evaluation explicitly links this shift to 'direct payment to women' and to the programme's improved capacity to engage female workers, confirming that payment modality, not only payment level, functions as a trust and continuity mechanism (ILO, 2021, p. 27).

The gender gap and direct payment to women. Among refugees in Jordan, 63% of mobile

payment users are male, and 37% are female (GIZ, 2022, p. 3). 42% of women, compared with 19% of men, reported worrying about making mistakes with mobile technology (GSMA, 2015, as cited in GIZ, 2022, p. 28). While this figure pre-dates the period examined in this study, more recent GIZ data on mobile payment patterns among Jordanian refugees confirm that the gender gap in digital financial access persisted into 2022 (GIZ, 2022, pp. 7, 28). The gap in account ownership grew between 2017 and 2022: women's ownership rose modestly from 27% to 31%, while men's increased from 38% to 53% (GIZ, 2022, pp. 7, 28). Women who are separated from their partners also raised concerns about their former partner's ability to monitor or access their accounts (GIZ, 2022, p. 28). In some situations, receiving cash directly at the worksite, though more administratively demanding, may give a woman more effective control over her wages than a mobile wallet that someone else can monitor. Payment modality, therefore, is a financial control decision, not just a logistical one.

Payment timeliness. The timing of payment is a second dimension that is often overlooked. Studies that highlight the shift to ATM cards and mobile wallets often assume that digital payments automatically guarantee consistent and on-time payments. Women in Jordanian CfW programmes have, however, indicated that delays or unpredictability in wage payments undermine household trust in the programme and reduce the confidence that digital payment systems are meant to guarantee (Loewe et al., 2020, pp. 136, 139; ILO, 2021, p. 27).

Differences between settings. The Za'atari SOP now explicitly encourages agencies with more than 50 IBV participants to use mobile wallets and requires all payments to be recorded in RAIS (BNLWG, 2022, Section 3). In host communities, mobile wallets, iris-enabled ATMs, and prepaid debit cards are the most common payment methods. However, without rules about who owns the account and how payments are made privately, direct payments alone do not guarantee that women control their own wages (GIZ, 2022, pp. 15, 28; ILO, 2021, p. 27).

2.7 Monitoring, Indicators, and What Counts as Success

Monitoring systems in CfW programmes are often weaker than the programmes' stated ambitions, with direct consequences for accountability, learning and improvement.

What the evaluations show. Both ILO evaluations document this problem. The 2021 evaluation identifies unclear measurement methods and missing indicators on retention as fundamental weaknesses. Key Lesson 4 of that evaluation explicitly states that monitoring and evaluation must go beyond counting jobs and build an evidence base to support future planning (ILO, 2021, p. 35-36). The 2024 cluster evaluation takes this further, calling for more specific tracking at each stage of the participation pipeline and stronger monitoring of programme processes (ILO, 2024, pp. 47–50).

Crucially, this gap is not merely about the volume of data but about what the indicators are designed to capture. The 2024 cluster evaluation found that while output indicators permit disaggregation of men's and women's access to jobs, the indicators and baselines do not allow disaggregation of how

well the programme specifically contributed to improving women's livelihoods. It recommended clarifying ambiguous outcome indicators (ILO, 2024, p. 67). The same concern about monitoring appears beyond Jordan: the DEval meta-evaluation of German development cooperation's employment programmes across the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region likewise recommends improving impact monitoring at the participant level, including systematic tracking of participants' subsequent outcomes (DEval, 2021, p. 9). Together, these evaluations establish that the monitoring gap is not limited to individual programmes; it is a sector-wide pattern. Addressing it requires tracking participation at each stage of the pipeline separately, rather than combining entry and completion into a single overall rate.

Differences between settings. Camp settings already have a minimum monitoring standard. Both Azraq and Za'atari SOPs require agencies to submit monthly reporting templates to UNHCR covering the number of IBV participants disaggregated by gender, with all payments and participant records logged individually through the RAIS (the camp registration and eligibility system) IBV module. Complaint tracking and an annual IBV assessment are also required (BNLWG, 2020, Section 4; BNLWG, 2022, Section 6). In host-community programmes, gender disaggregation is applied to two denominators: the number of jobs created and the number of worker-days, both of which are broken down by gender, nationality, and disability status (ILO, 2024, pp. 49–50). Neither setting tracks the number of women who applied, selected, started work, or left before the programme ended. Where monitoring captures a gender share at the end of the pipeline but not the stages that produced it, programmes can report whether a target was met, but cannot explain why it was missed or where women dropped out. This gap is one of the reasons this study treats entry and completion as separate analytical targets rather than combining them into a single participation rate.

2.8 Feasibility Under Regulatory and Delivery Constraints

Not all desirable design measures are equally possible under current conditions in Jordan. This applies across every domain reviewed in the preceding sections. Feasibility depends not only on budget but also on regulatory rules, contractor capacity, inter-agency coordination requirements, and institutional readiness. Any design recommendation must distinguish between measures that a programme can implement within a single delivery cycle and those that require broader policy change.

How camps are regulated. In camp settings, almost every design measure is shaped by the SOP framework. Agencies must use the RAIS pre-eligibility system and follow the Za'atari or Azraq SOP rules on working hours, job advertising, complaint mechanisms, and payment methods (BNLWG, 2020; BNLWG, 2022). This level of regulation limits flexibility, but it also provides a standardised base on which gender-sensitive measures can be required rather than negotiated individually with each contractor.

How host communities are coordinated. In host-community settings, a CfW Working Group co-chaired by the ILO and the GIZ Programme Support Unit coordinates implementing agencies across

the sector. A Programme Support Unit based in the Ministry of Labour helps harmonise approaches, support work permit processes, and provide technical advice (ILO, 2024, p. 17). Unlike the BNLWG camp SOPs, which are mandatory under UNHCR's coordination authority, the working group operates voluntarily. Its standards are not monitored or enforced by a single authority.

For Syrian women in host communities, work permit restrictions limit the types of jobs and the hours they can legally work. Transport and childcare barriers compound these restrictions, making participation especially sensitive to programme failures in addressing them (UN Women Jordan Office, 2024, p. 35). Stave et al. (2021, p. 56) confirm that work permit hurdles and labour market restrictions are persistent barriers to both staying in work and transitioning to other employment, particularly for Syrian refugees.

The eligibility gap between settings. The regulatory difference between the two settings extends to who is eligible to participate. In camp settings, CfW is delivered through the IBV scheme, established in 2014 by an agreement between the Government of Jordan and UNHCR. It is classified as volunteering rather than formal employment, so it does not require a work permit. The Azraq SOP treats holding a work permit as grounds for deprioritising an applicant, not as a requirement (BNLWG, 2020, Sections 1 and 3.3). In host communities, CfW falls under formal employment rules. Syrian refugees must hold a valid work permit in an eligible sector to participate. By mid-2019, women received only approximately 5% of the 156,761 work permits issued to Syrian refugees in Jordan (Loewe et al., 2020, p. 49). By 2025, this share had risen to 15.6% of permits issued (UNHCR, 2025b), reflecting gradual progress following Jordan Compact sector liberalisation. Yet, women remained significantly underrepresented relative to their share of the working-age refugee population, and structural exclusion persists, even if its scale has shifted. The documentation barrier in host communities is therefore not the same as the RAIS eligibility check in camps. It is a higher and earlier threshold that the large majority of Syrian refugee women have not yet cleared.

Practical implementation constraints. The 2021 ILO evaluation documents several implementation constraints: overlapping programme phases, approval bottlenecks in the Jordan Response Information System for the Syria Crisis (JORISS), payment delays, and financial pressure on implementing organisations (ILO, 2021, p. 32). Short programme cycles reduce the time available to invest in gender-sensitive staffing, contractor training, or monitoring systems, because these require upfront resources and negotiations that tight budgets and short timelines do not support. Contractor capacity is a further gap. Delivering gender-sensitive recruitment, gender-based violence (GBV) prevention, grievance mechanisms, and appropriate payment systems requires trained staff and dedicated budget, not just written rules. A conclusion supported by the ILO 2021 evaluation's evidence that deliberate contractor training on gender-specific recruitment was necessary to achieve solid participation rates (ILO, 2021, p. 8; ILO, 2022, pp. 40–45).

Programme-operable versus policy-dependent measures. A useful distinction for structuring feasibility analysis separates measures that programmes can implement directly from those that require

broader system change. The ILO gender-responsive procurement guide argues that equal pay, safe workplaces, grievance mechanisms, and GBV (gender-based violence) prevention should be built into procurement contracts and contractor monitoring, rather than left to voluntary practice (ILO, 2022, pp. 40–45). This defines a category of measures, codes of conduct, personal protective equipment (PPE), complaint systems, and payment procedures that can be required contractually and checked within a single programme cycle. Measures such as affordable childcare or major public transport improvements fall into a different category. They require a national policy change that individual CfW programmes cannot achieve on their own.

This distinction is not permanent. The World Bank Programme for Results (PforR) on Enhancing Women's Economic Opportunities (EWEO) identifies women-friendly workplaces, financial inclusion, safe transport, and childcare as connected policy priorities (World Bank, 2024a, pp. 3–4). These developments show that some currently system-dependent constraints are being actively addressed at the policy level, which means the line between what programmes can do now and what requires policy change will shift over time.

2.9 Framework Derived from Literature

The literature reviewed above supports a dual analytical framework for the empirical chapters that follow. Evidence is organised around a two-stage participation pipeline, entry and completion, and six design domains, which together allow failures at each pipeline stage to be traced to specific combinations of outreach, work-type design, logistical arrangements, worksite conditions, payment design, and monitoring practice. A second, cross-cutting distinction between barriers amenable to programme-level change within a single CfW cycle and those requiring policy-level reform defines the feasibility boundary on which Chapter 5's recommendations are built. The framework does not claim that better design automatically improves women's participation; it provides a structured basis for identifying which specific features are associated with higher uptake and completion under current Jordanian delivery conditions, and where the boundary lies between operational improvement and structural constraint. For the monitoring domain, this study applies a benchmarking approach, comparing current practice against existing evaluation frameworks and implementing organisation standards, and proposing a minimum measurable standard where none currently exists.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Design and Rationale

A quantitative, cross-sectional, deductive survey design was used. The research question asks which programme design features are associated with higher women's uptake and completion, and whether these features are feasible under current regulatory and delivery constraints in Jordan. The design is non-experimental and descriptive-comparative: it compares patterns across pre-defined groups, delivery settings, and respondent roles without manipulating variables or randomly assigning respondents to conditions. Programme design features constitute the independent variables;

women's uptake and completion serve as the outcome variables of interest.

A quantitative approach was appropriate for three reasons: First, the study aimed to measure the prevalence and distribution of specific programme design practices across different implementation contexts. These include recruitment and selection approaches, worksite arrangements, childcare and transport support, and monitoring practices. A structured questionnaire captures these features consistently and comparably across respondents, unlike open-ended methods.

Second, the study required systematic comparison across subgroups expected to shape implementation choices and constraints: respondent role, delivery setting, and target population composition. Quantitative survey data supported the descriptive and comparative analysis, including frequencies, percentages, and cross-tabulations, needed to show whether patterns differed across contexts.

Third, the study included standardised proxy measures reported by implementers, specifically women's participation targets and latest achieved rates, and perceived effectiveness and feasibility ratings for each design measure. This enabled exploratory examination of patterns between reported design features and reported outcomes, without claiming causality.

A qualitative design, specifically semi-structured interviews, was considered and set aside for two reasons. The study required a systematic comparison of the prevalence of design practice across implementation contexts, in which structured comparability across cases takes analytical precedence over the depth of individual experience. The research question also asks what is associated with participation outcomes across programmes, not how any single implementer interprets their practice. That is a distributional question that interviews cannot efficiently address at the intended sample coverage. The design, therefore, prioritised structured comparability across many programmes, making a quantitative survey the more appropriate choice.

3.2 Research Setting and Unit of Analysis

This study is situated in Jordan, which serves as the research location for both data collection and analysis. Jordan was selected because it hosts one of the largest and most institutionally structured CfW delivery systems in the MENA region, and because it presents two structurally distinct regulatory environments within a single national context. The first is the IBV scheme governing CfW in the refugee camps of Za'atari and Azraq, operating under mandatory Standard Operating Procedures developed by the BNLWG. The second is the more fragmented, multi-actor framework governing host-community delivery, in which participation by Syrian refugees requires a valid work permit in an eligible sector. This regulatory duality, documented in detail in Chapter 2, makes Jordan a particularly informative research setting. Design measures that are achievable under the IBV framework may not be transferable to host-community programmes, and vice versa. The research question explicitly asks about feasibility under current delivery constraints, and it can only be meaningfully answered by treating the two settings as analytically distinct rather than as a single operational context.

The unit of analysis is the programme design and delivery configuration relevant to women's

participation outcomes across the programme cycle. In practice, each completed questionnaire was treated as a programme configuration observation, representing a specific CfW project, component, or operational cluster as defined by the respondent.

To support the interpretation and assessment of feasibility under different delivery conditions, the analysis used three contextual classification variables. The first captured whether implementation occurred in host communities, camp settings, or both-settings, meaning programmes operating across both refugee camp and host communities contexts. The second captured whether the targeted participant group was composed primarily of Syrian refugees, Jordanians, or a mixed group. The third captured the respondent's role in relation to programme delivery and oversight, covering programme management and coordination, field supervision, MEAL and data management, safeguarding and protection, and supervision roles with donor, ministry, or municipality counterparts who directly implement. Given the sample size and non-probability sampling approach, these contextual dimensions were used to structure descriptive subgroup comparisons and interpretation, and not to support statistical inference.

3.3 Data Source

The primary data source was a structured questionnaire administered via Qualtrics. The survey captured respondent role and programme context; reported programme design practices across the CfW delivery cycle; perceived effectiveness of selected design measures for women's uptake and completion; feasibility assessments under operational and regulatory constraints; monitoring and reporting practices, including the availability of gender-disaggregated indicators; and the programme's latest reported women's participation target and achieved rate, where known. The questionnaire responses constitute the sole empirical dataset for quantitative analysis in this thesis.

Secondary sources were used to ground the analytical framework in Chapter 2 and to contextualise and interpret the survey findings in the discussion chapter. These include peer-reviewed journal articles, programme evaluations, institutional and donor reports, Standard Operating Procedures, labour market studies, and national policy frameworks. Where secondary sources pre-dating 2021 are cited, this reflects the scarcity of more recent empirical literature on gender-disaggregated CfW outcomes in Jordan. Each such source is identified and justified in the opening of Chapter 2.

3.4 Sampling Strategy and Recruitment

The target population comprised CfW implementers and related professionals with direct implementation responsibilities or oversight roles in CfW programming in Jordan. Eligible respondents included individuals involved in the past 60 months in planning, implementation, supervision, MEAL and data management, safeguarding and protection, or donor, ministry, and municipality oversight. The 60-month eligibility window was chosen to include practitioners with experience across multiple CfW phases and SOP revisions, while ensuring familiarity with current Jordanian delivery conditions. Eligibility was confirmed through survey consent and screening questions that required

demonstrated involvement in CfW programmes in Jordan within the past 60 months. Only responses that passed these screens were routed to the survey and included in the analysis dataset.

Sampling followed a non-probability purposive and snowball approach to reach eligible CfW professionals while maintaining anonymity. No central registry of CfW implementers exists in Jordan, and professional networks are the only viable route to reach the target population. The anonymous Qualtrics link was shared via WhatsApp with the researcher's professional contacts active in relevant sector networks, who could forward it to eligible colleagues and partner organisations. The study aimed to obtain at least 20 complete questionnaires to allow meaningful descriptive cross-tabulations across the main contextual categories.

3.5 Achieved Sample and Participant Profile

The survey was distributed from 27 February to 15 March 2026. Of the 32 responses received, nine were excluded before analysis: one respondent did not provide informed consent, six reported no involvement in a CfW programme in Jordan within the preceding 60 months, and two self-reported insufficient involvement to answer the survey meaningfully. The remaining 23 valid responses constitute the analytical dataset. The exclusion rate of 28% reflects the specificity of the eligibility criteria and confirms that all retained respondents had direct, recent experience with CfW programme implementation in Jordan.

By respondent role, the sample achieved included 11 programme managers and coordinators (48%), 7 field officers (30%), 4 MEAL and data staff (17%), and 1 safeguarding and protection professional (4%). By delivery setting, 9 respondents (39%) reported working in refugee camp settings (Za'atari or Azraq), 11 (48%) in both-settings, and 3 (13%) in host communities' settings only. The both-settings category is the largest single group in the sample and was treated throughout the analysis as a distinct contextual category not collapsed into either the camp or host communities sub-group. By targeted participant group, the sample covered programmes targeting Syrian refugees only, Jordanians only, and mixed groups. Full cross-tabulations of role by setting and of setting by participant group composition are presented in Chapter 4. No personal identifiers were collected at any stage. Results are presented as descriptive patterns and subgroup comparisons within the sample, and all subgroup findings, particularly those based on the host communities sub-group (n=3), were interpreted as indicative rather than definitive.

3.6 Pilot Testing

Before distribution, the questionnaire was piloted with two practitioners working in the same implementing organisation in Jordan. The pilot assessed four dimensions: the time required to complete the survey; the clarity and comprehensibility of question wording, given that English is not the first language of most target respondents; the overall cognitive load and respondent fatigue across the full instrument; and whether any items were ambiguous or missing important response options.

Pilot respondents were selected to reflect the expected language profile of the target population,

whose first languages are predominantly Arabic, German, or English. The two pilot practitioners, one Arabic-speaking and one German-speaking, were chosen to assess comprehension across the two main non-English first-language groups. Both completed the full questionnaire and provided feedback.

Based on pilot feedback indicating a gap in the instrument's coverage of perceived effectiveness, Q20 was designed and added to the survey instrument, and minor wording adjustments were made to improve readability before distribution. The estimated completion time of 8 to 12 minutes was derived from their completion experience. No item ambiguity was identified during piloting. The full survey instrument, including all question wording, response options, and branching logic, is provided in Appendix A.

3.7 Data Collection and Questionnaire Design

The questionnaire was a closed-ended instrument structured into blocks reflecting the CfW programme cycle and the study's analytical framework, covering all six design domains identified in Chapter 2. The instrument also included items on monitoring practices, covering whether key gender-disaggregated pipeline indicators were recorded, and collected respondents' assessments of which measures were most effective for women's completion and overall participation, as well as feasibility ratings under current budgetary, regulatory, and operational constraints. Response formats included single-choice and multiple-select items, Likert scales, and a numeric item measured on a 0 to 100 scale for women's participation target and achieved rate.

Key variables were operationalised to align directly with the research question. Women's uptake was captured through items describing recruitment accessibility and selection mechanisms, alongside respondents' reported experiences and judgements of measures that facilitate women's entry. Women's completion was captured through respondents' prioritisation of measures perceived as most effective for completion, and through items reflecting perceived changes in completion-related outcomes after implementation, for which respondents indicated sufficient knowledge to judge these effects. Women's participation target and achieved level were collected using a numeric item recording the programme target percentage and the latest achieved percentage. When both values were provided, a descriptive target-achievement gap was calculated as the percentage difference between the target and the achieved value. Because no standardised Jordan-wide baseline exists for women's participation in CfW programmes, implementer-reported targets, achieved rates, and perceived post-implementation changes are treated throughout the analysis as indicative associations rather than causal evidence of improvement. Design levers were captured through respondents' selections of implemented and relevant measures, along with ratings of perceived effectiveness and feasibility. Feasibility under constraints was captured using a feasibility matrix applied to respondent-selected measures, alongside a separate item identifying the most salient constraints.

To reduce respondent burden and increase relevance, Qualtrics display branching logic was used

to carry forward only the measures selected in Q16 into the feasibility-rating matrix in Q18, so that respondents rated feasibility only for measures they identified as implemented or applicable. Unselected measures were carried forward into the perceived-effectiveness matrix in Q20, which was administered to measures not selected as the top three measures contributing to higher participation in Q16. This design decision strengthened the analytical validity of the feasibility ratings by grounding them in respondents' own implementation experience rather than hypothetical judgment.

Though it was not detected during pilot testing, an early version of the schedule-pattern item Q7 included an undifferentiated "fixed daily schedule" option alongside a "morning only" option. These were refined mid-data collection following respondent feedback indicating ambiguity between the two categories. The response set was subsequently simplified, and the two legacy responses could not be assumed to refer to the "morning only" option. They were therefore excluded from Q7 analysis, leaving an analytical base of $n=21$. This exclusion does not materially change the overall descriptive interpretation of Q7.

As a data-quality safeguard, all substantive items after the initial screening questions were set to require a "force response" so that eligible respondents could not submit partially completed questionnaires.

The full survey instrument, including all question wording, response options, and branching logic, is provided in Appendix A.

3.8 Data Preparation and Analysis Procedure

Survey responses were exported from Qualtrics in comma-separated values format and stored in a secure, access-restricted location. The dataset was checked for empty responses and potential duplicates using available response identifiers and timestamps. No duplicates were identified, consistent with the duplicate-prevention setting enabled in Qualtrics during data collection.

An analysis-ready dataset was created through systematic coding. Single-choice items were coded as categorical variables using the survey response categories. Multiple-select items were recoded into binary indicator variables, with each response option represented as a separate variable coded 1 if selected and 0 otherwise. Matrix items were coded on ordered numeric scales consistent with the response anchors, enabling descriptive summaries. The numeric target and achieved participation items were stored as continuous variables on a 0-100 scale. When both target and achieved values were available, a target-achievement gap was computed as the difference between achieved and target, expressed as percentage points, and summarised descriptively. When one or both values were unknown, the gap was not computed for that case.

Two data cleaning decisions were applied before analysis. First, one respondent selected "Mixed Jordanians and Syrians" as the target population while simultaneously selecting "Refugee camp" as the delivery setting. Since Jordanian nationals do not reside in Jordan's Syrian refugee camps, this was identified as a data entry error and recoded to "Syrians only." Second, a post-hoc internal

consistency check of Q19 responses identified two cases in which the dropout item was rated in a direction incompatible with the respondent's own uptake and completion ratings. As the dropout item was the only reverse-coded item in Q19, this pattern indicates misinterpretation of the scale direction. Both respondents were excluded from all Q19 analyses rather than selectively retaining specific items, as partial retention would require assumptions about which responses within the same response set were reliable. Q19 analysis was therefore based on n=21. All cleaning decisions are fully documented in Appendix E, Tables 31 and 32.

Analysis proceeded in two stages. First, descriptive statistics were produced for all variables. Categorical variables and binary indicators were summarised using frequencies and percentages. Where applicable, means and standard deviations were reported to reflect the distribution of responses, while Likert scale variables were summarised using distributional descriptions and measures of central tendency appropriate to the data. Second, subgroup comparisons were conducted using the contextual classification variables defined in Section 3.2, covering programme setting, participant group composition, and respondent role. Cross-tabulations and side-by-side descriptive summaries were used to compare patterns across subgroups. Findings were interpreted as indicative patterns rather than inferential estimates, given the sample size and non-probability sampling approach. Descriptive statistics, frequency tables, and cross-tabulations were produced using Microsoft Excel, including pivot tables and charts.

A separate population-based disaggregation was not applied. In this sample, the delivery setting already captures population composition precisely. All nine refugee camp respondents served only Syrian beneficiaries, while all three host communities respondents served mixed Jordanian and Syrian populations. Both-settings programmes followed the same pattern in practice, with 10 of the 11 respondents serving mixed populations and only one reporting Syrian beneficiaries only. A standalone population disaggregation would not add analytical value beyond what the setting variable already reveals and would risk producing redundant subgroup comparisons across near-identical groups.

The questionnaire included "I don't know" as a response option in three analytical contexts: Q14 covering indicator tracking, Q20 covering perceived effectiveness, and Q21 covering participation targets and achieved rates. In each case, it was treated as a meaningful, reportable category rather than missing data. In Q14, it was interpreted as a monitoring visibility or knowledge gap and summarised by item and respondent role. In Q20, it indicated that a measure was not implemented or that the respondent lacked sufficient observational basis to judge its effectiveness, and was reported as an evidence-strength signal by lever and role. In Q21, it captured the lack of access to or recall of programme monitoring figures. Where either the target or achieved value was unknown, the target-achievement gap was not computed for that case. For the monitoring domain specifically, the analysis applies the benchmarking approach defined in Section 2.9, comparing 2026 practitioner-reported practices against existing evaluation frameworks and implementing organisation standards.

3.9 Data Protection and Ethics

The survey begins with an information sheet that explains the study purpose, what participation involves, and how data will be used, followed by an informed consent item and eligibility screening questions. Respondents who did not provide consent were routed to a suspension page. Data processing was carried out on the basis of freely given, informed consent in accordance with Article 6(1)(a) of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Participation was voluntary, and respondents could discontinue at any point by closing the survey without providing a reason or facing any negative consequences.

To protect anonymity and confidentiality, the questionnaire does not request names, phone numbers, email addresses, employer identifiers, or any other direct personal identifiers. Qualtrics settings were configured so that IP addresses are not permanently stored in the exported dataset; however, a duplicate-prevention setting was enabled to detect and block repeated submission attempts from the same device at the time of entry. IP addresses were used only for this real-time duplicate check and were not retained in the data file made available for analysis. Survey data were processed by Qualtrics International Inc., a third-party data processor operating under a Data Processing Agreement in compliance with the GDPR requirements for processor arrangements (Art. 28 GDPR). The dataset will be retained for the duration required for thesis examination and assessment, after which it will be securely deleted.

3.10 Rigour, Validity, and Limitations

Rigour and Validity: The researcher's prior role as a CfW practitioner at GIZ Jordan shaped this study and must be acknowledged. Practitioner experience informed the instrument design and enabled access to a professional network that an external researcher could not have reached within the same timeframe. Although the survey was anonymous, respondents aware of the researcher's affiliation may have answered with greater openness or greater caution than they would for an outsider, particularly on items where non-provision carries professional cost.

Eligibility screening was embedded at the beginning of the questionnaire. Respondents indicating no relevant CfW involvement within the past 60 months, or selecting "Limited involvement / not enough information," were routed to a suspension page to avoid collecting non-eligible responses. The questionnaire's construct validity is supported by grounding all items directly in the six-domain analytical framework from Chapter 2, so that each question maps to a specific participation barrier or design lever. Reliability is supported through a fully standardised, closed-ended instrument administered under identical conditions via Qualtrics. The branching logic, which carried forward only respondents' own selected measures into the feasibility rating matrix, prevented hypothetical bias. All coding decisions, exclusions, and mid-collection revisions are fully documented in Appendix E to allow independent verification.

Limitations: Four limitations apply to this study.

First, no comprehensive sampling frame exists for CfW implementers in Jordan. Practitioners are distributed across UN agencies, NGOs, government bodies, and contractors with no central registry. Purposive and snowball sampling were the only viable approaches, and respondents were drawn from overlapping professional networks that may not represent the full range of implementation experience. The snowball network originating from the researcher's GIZ contacts is likely to over-represent better-resourced, SOP-compliant organisations, while implementing organisations with weaker documentation cultures may be underrepresented. Findings are interpreted as descriptive patterns within the sample. They are not statistically generalisable, though the sample spans all three delivery settings and four professional roles, providing breadth across the CfW implementation landscape in Jordan.

Second, perceived effectiveness and feasibility ratings reflect professional judgement rather than observed programme outcomes, introducing the possibility of recall bias and social desirability effects. This is particularly relevant for items on harassment prevention and grievance mechanisms, where non-provision carries professional cost. This limitation is managed through subgroup comparisons by role and context, which make role-dependent variation visible rather than averaging it away.

Third, monitoring practice knowledge varies by role, reducing the validity of observations. Instead of treating this as missing data, it is retained and reported as "I don't know" in Section 3.8.

Fourth, significance tests were not applied because the non-probability purposive sample does not meet the assumption of random selection required for statistical generalisation. Applying p-values or confidence intervals to a purposive sample of 23 would yield misleading precision estimates. All findings are therefore reported as descriptive patterns and subgroup comparisons within the sample, consistent with the study's exploratory scope.

4. Data analysis

The analytical sample comprised 23 practitioners, selected and screened as described in Chapter 3. Their full characteristics are presented in the Respondent Profile below. Findings are treated as exploratory and descriptive. The analysis identifies patterns and areas of convergence across settings and roles to inform evidence-based recommendations for CfW programme design in Jordan. Findings are disaggregated by delivery setting throughout, with role-based disaggregation applied selectively when respondents' professional function is likely to shape their responses, specifically regarding monitoring practices, programme-level perceptions, and knowledge of participation targets and outcomes.

Unless otherwise stated, all setting-disaggregated tables in this chapter report frequencies and percentages calculated from the n of each delivery setting column: overall (n=23), both-settings (n=11), refugee camp (n=9), and host communities (n=3). Percentages within each column sum to 100% independently of other columns.

4.1 Respondent Profile

The 23 valid respondents represented diverse roles, delivery settings, and programme types. The largest group was programme managers and coordinators (n=11, 48%), followed by field officers and contractor supervisors (n=7, 30%), MEAL and data staff (n=4, 17%), and safeguarding staff (n=1, 4%). Eleven respondents (48%) worked in both refugee camps and host communities, nine (39%) in refugee camps only, and three (13%) in host communities only. Thirteen (57%) served mixed Jordanian and Syrian beneficiaries, while 10 (43%) served only Syrians. Most (78%) worked in organisations that publicly report CfW activities. Full details are in Table 1.

Tab. 1. Sample composition by role, setting, population, and reporting status (n=23).

Variable	Category	n	%
Professional role	Programme manager/coordinator	11	48%
	Field officer/contractor supervisor	7	30%
	MEAL/data staff	4	17%
	Safeguarding/protection staff	1	4%
Delivery setting	Both camp and host communities	11	48%
	Refugee camp only	9	39%
	Host communities only	3	13%
Target population	Mixed Jordanians and Syrians	13	57%
	Syrians only	10	43%
Public reporting	Yes	18	78%
	No	5	22%

Source: Own representation.

The most commonly reported work cycle duration was 41–60 days (n=12, 52%), followed by 60–90 days (n=8, 35%) and cycles exceeding 90 days (n=7, 30%). Shorter cycles of 21–40 days were reported by 4 respondents (17%), and one respondent (4%) reported cycles of ten days or fewer. Respondents could select multiple cycle lengths, so totals exceed 100%; the 60–90-day and exceeding 90-day categories are not mutually exclusive and may reflect the same respondents reporting more than one cycle length across different programme phases. The full overview is illustrated in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Programme work cycle duration by delivery setting (n=23).

Source: Own representation.

4.2 Recruitment Practices and Perceived Barriers

Q1- Perceptions of the Recruitment Process

Respondents rated eight statements on a five-point Likert scale (1=Strongly Disagree, 5=Strongly Agree). Four items assessed positive process qualities; four assessed structural barriers and were *reverse-coded* so that lower mean scores indicate stronger perceived barriers. Results are disaggregated by delivery setting and professional role.

The formal elements of the recruitment process were generally rated positively: Recruitment information was rated most accessible (M=4.48), followed by clarity of selection criteria (M=4.22), effectiveness of outreach in reaching women (M=4.17), and overall fairness and transparency of the process (M=4.04). All four barrier items fell below the neutral midpoint of 3.0. Household consent and gender norms were rated as the strongest barrier (M=2.48), followed by documentation requirements (M=2.70), registration complexity (M=2.83), and application location or timing constraints (M=2.91). The full results are illustrated in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Perceptions of the recruitment process - mean scores (n=23).

Source: Own representation.

Setting-based disaggregation shows that barrier perceptions were high in refugee camp settings, especially for documentation (M=2.11), and highest for household consent (M=1.89), compared to both-settings programmes (M=3.45 and 3.00). Host communities respondents reported the lowest outreach scores (M=3.00) and highest application accessibility barriers (M=2.00) and highest documentation barrier (M=1.67). MEAL staff saw documentation as less of a barrier (M=4.00) than programme managers (M=2.64) and field officers (M=2.29). Full results are in Appendix B, Table 12.

Q2 - Active Inclusion Measures Used in Recruitment

Respondents selected which active inclusion measures were applied to support women's access during recruitment. Multiple selections were permitted. Women's quotas were the most widely reported measure (n=17, 74%), followed by targeted outreach to women (n=15, 65%). Exclusion risk screening was less commonly applied (n=9, 39%). Setting-based disaggregation and full results are presented in Table 2.

Tab. 2. Active inclusion measures applied, by delivery setting (n=23)

Measure	Overall n (%)	Both n (%)	Camp n (%)	Host Comm. n (%)
Women's quotas	17 (74%)	9 (82%)	6 (67%)	2 (67%)
Targeted outreach to women	15 (65%)	8 (73%)	6 (67%)	1 (33%)
Exclusion risk screening	9 (39%)	4 (36%)	4 (44%)	1 (33%)

Source: Own representation.

Q3 - Participant Selection Mechanisms

Respondents listed mechanisms for selecting participants, with vulnerability scoring most common (70%, n=16), followed by women's quotas as a selection mechanism (48%, n=11), distinct from their use as a recruitment inclusion measure in Q2, committee decisions (30%, n=7), first-come-first-served (26%, n=6), and lottery (13%, n=3). Full results are in Table 3.

Tab. 3. Participant selection mechanisms, by delivery setting (n=23).

Mechanism	Overall n (%)	Both n (%)	Camp n (%)	Host Comm. n (%)
Vulnerability scoring	16 (70%)	9 (82%)	5 (56%)	2 (67%)
Women's quotas	11 (48%)	4 (36%)	5 (56%)	2 (67%)
Committee decision	7 (30%)	2 (18%)	5 (56%)	0 (0%)
First-come, first-served	6 (26%)	1 (9%)	4 (44%)	1 (33%)
Lottery	3 (13%)	1 (9%)	1 (11%)	1 (33%)

Source: Own representation.

4.3 Work Design Features

Q4 - Types of Work Offered to Women

Respondents selected types of work that were included in their CfW programmes (up to 3 selections). Cleaning was the most commonly reported type (n=15, 65%), followed by solid waste and recycling (n=12, 52%), administrative and data tasks (n=9, 39%), greening and agriculture (n=8, 35%), and community services (n=6, 26%). Home-based and semi-skilled work was reported by 3 respondents (13%), care work by 2 (9%), and light maintenance by 1 (4%). Construction and heavy work were not reported by any respondent as one of the three main work types. Setting-based disaggregation is illustrated in Figure 3. Full results by delivery setting are presented in Appendix B, Table 13.

Fig. 3. Work types offered to women in CfW programmes (n=23)

Source: Own representation.

Q5 - Worksite Exposure Type

Respondents selected the primary worksite environment (single-select). The majority of programmes took place in mostly public or open spaces (n=13, 57%), followed by mostly semi-private settings (n=8, 35%). Only two programmes (9%) were conducted mostly indoors, both in refugee camp settings. Full results by delivery setting are presented in Table 4.

Tab. 4. Primary worksite exposure type, by delivery setting (n=23)

Exposure Type	Overall n (%)	Both n (%)	Camp n (%)	Host Comm. n (%)
Mostly public/open spaces	13 (57%)	6 (55%)	6 (67%)	1 (33%)
Mostly semi-private	8 (35%)	5 (45%)	1 (11%)	2 (67%)
Mostly indoor	2 (9%)	0 (0%)	2 (22%)	0 (0%)

Source: Own representation.

Q6 - Team Composition and Gender Safety Arrangements

Respondents selected which team composition and gender safety arrangements were in place (multiple selections permitted). Culturally acceptable work or worksite arrangements were the most widely reported (n=15, 65%), followed by mixed-gender teams managed in a way considered safe and acceptable by women (n=14, 61%), female supervisor or team lead availability (n=13, 57%), and women-only teams (n=12, 52%). Full results by delivery setting are presented in Table 5.

Tab. 5. Team composition, gender safety, by delivery setting (n=23), multiple responses permitted.

Arrangement	Overall n (%)	Both n (%)	Camp n (%)	Host Comm. n (%)
Culturally acceptable work/worksite	15 (65%)	8 (73%)	6 (67%)	1 (33%)
Mixed-gender teams managed safely	14 (61%)	6 (55%)	7 (78%)	1 (33%)
Female supervisors/team leads availa-	13 (57%)	9 (82%)	2 (22%)	2 (67%)
Women-only teams	12 (52%)	6 (55%)	4 (44%)	2 (67%)

Source: Own representation.

4.4 Time, Transport, and Childcare Constraints

Q7 - Daily Schedule Structure

Respondents selected the daily schedule structure applied in their programmes (single-select). As noted in Chapter 3, two legacy responses were excluded, leaving an analytical base of n=21. The majority reported a fixed morning-only schedule (n=17, 81%); 19% reported flexible shifts (n=4). No respondent reported an evening-only fixed schedule. Flexible shifts were reported exclusively in refugee camp settings. Full results are presented in Table 6.

Tab. 6. Daily schedule structure, by delivery setting (n=21)

Schedule	Overall n (%)	Both n (%)	Camp n (%)	Host Comm. n (%)
Morning only - Fixed	17 (81%)	9 (100%)	5 (56%)	3 (100%)
Flexible shifts	4 (19%)	0 (0%)	4 (44%)	0 (0%)
Evening only - Fixed	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)

Source: Own representation.

Q8 - Worksite Location Proximity

Respondents selected worksite proximity to participants' residences (single-select). Responses were almost evenly split between worksites within the same neighbourhood (n=12, 52%) and worksites within the same city (n=11, 48%). No respondent reported worksites located outside the city. No strong pattern in setting was observed across delivery contexts. Full results are presented in Table 7.

Tab. 7. Worksite location proximity, by delivery setting (n=23)

Location	Overall n (%)	Both n (%)	Camp n (%)	Host Comm. n (%)
Within the same neighbourhood	12 (52%)	6 (55%)	5 (56%)	1 (33%)
Same city	11 (48%)	5 (45%)	4 (44%)	2 (67%)

Source: Own representation.

Q9 - Transport Support

Respondents selected items to indicate whether transport support was provided and, if so, in what form (single-select). The majority did not provide any transport support (n=14, 61%). Among the nine that did (39%), organised transport was most common (n=6, 26% of total), while cash transport allowances were provided in three cases (13%). Full results by delivery setting are presented in Table 8.

Tab. 8. Transport support provided, by delivery setting (n=23)

Transport support	Overall n (%)	Both n (%)	Camp n (%)	Host Comm. n (%)
No Transport support	14 (61%)	6 (55%)	7 (78%)	1 (33%)
Organised transport	6 (26%)	3 (27%)	2 (22%)	1 (33%)
Cash transport allowance	3 (13%)	2 (18%)	0 (0%)	1 (33%)

Source: Own representation.

Q10 - Childcare Support

Respondents indicated whether childcare support was provided and, if so, what form it took (single-select). Childcare support was largely absent across programmes; only 4 of 23 (17%) programmes provided any. Among those that did, onsite childcare was the most common form (n=2), followed by a childcare allowance (n=1) and referral to a partner organisation (n=1). All four programmes that provided childcare support were in refugee camp settings. Full results are presented in Table 9.

Tab. 9. Childcare support provided, by delivery setting (n=23)

Childcare support	Overall n (%)	Both n (%)	Camp n (%)	Host Comm. n (%)
No Childcare support	19 (83%)	11 (100%)	5 (56%)	3 (100%)
Onsite childcare	2 (9%)	0 (0%)	2 (22%)	0 (0%)
Childcare allowance	1 (4%)	0 (0%)	1 (11%)	0 (0%)
Referral/partner childcare	1 (4%)	0 (0%)	1 (11%)	0 (0%)

Source: Own representation.

4.5 Worksite Conditions, Safety, and Protection

Q11 - Worksite Conditions

Respondents selected all worksite conditions that applied to their programme from a list of ten features (multi-select). PPE provision was the most widely reported feature (n=20, 87%), followed by onboarding and safety briefings, confidential reporting channels, and timely complaints handling (all n=18, 78%). Separate toilets, supportive supervision, a code of conduct, and harassment prevention measures were each reported by 74% of programmes (n=17). Access to drinking water was reported by 70% (n=16). The least-reported feature was a private rest and prayer space (n=12, 52%). Setting-based disaggregation is illustrated in Figure 4. Full results by delivery setting are presented in Appendix B, Table 14.

Fig. 4. Worksite conditions by delivery setting (n=23)

Source: Own representation.

4.6 Payment Modality and Financial Control

Q12 - Payment Methods Used

Respondents selected all payment methods used in their programme (multi-select). Mobile wallets were the most widely used method (n=17, 74%), followed by cash payments (n=8, 35%), bank transfers (n=5, 22%), prepaid debit cards (n=4, 17%), and EyePay (n=1, 4%). Mobile wallets were the dominant method across all settings and were reported by all refugee camp programmes (n=9, 100%). Full results by delivery setting are presented in Table 10.

Tab. 10. Payment methods used, by delivery setting (n=23)

Payment Method	Overall n (%)	Both n (%)	Camp n (%)	Host Comm. n (%)
Mobile wallet	17 (74%)	7 (64%)	9 (100%)	1 (33%)

Payment Method	Overall n (%)	Both n (%)	Camp n (%)	Host Comm. n (%)
Cash	8 (35%)	3 (27%)	5 (56%)	0 (0%)
Bank transfer	5 (22%)	3 (27%)	0 (0%)	2 (67%)
Prepaid debit card	4 (17%)	3 (27%)	0 (0%)	1 (33%)
EyePay	1 (4%)	1 (9%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)

Source: Own representation.

Q13 - Payment Conditions

Respondents selected which payment conditions applied to their programme (multi-select). Equal pay was nearly universal (n=22, 96%). Direct payment to women and timely payment were each reported by 78% of programmes (n=18). Setting-based disaggregation reveals a gap: only 56% of refugee camp programmes reported direct payment to women and timely payment, compared to 91% in both-settings programmes and 100% in host-community programmes. Full results are presented in Table 11.

Tab. 11. Payment conditions reported, by delivery setting (n=23)

Payment Condition	Overall n	Both n	Camp n	Host Comm. n
Equal pay	22 (96%)	10 (91%)	9 (100%)	3 (100%)
direct payment to women	18 (78%)	10 (91%)	5 (56%)	3 (100%)
Paid on time	18 (78%)	10 (91%)	5 (56%)	3 (100%)

Source: Own representation.

4.7 Monitoring Practices

Q14 - Indicators Monitored

Respondents selected all items their programme tracked from a list of ten monitoring indicators (multi-select). For Q14, the role was treated as a primary analytical variable alongside the setting, because knowledge of monitoring practices is structurally dependent on professional function. The percentage of women selected was the most widely tracked indicator (n=19, 83%), followed by the percentage of women completers (n=17, 74%) and the percentage of women who dropped out (n=16, 70%). Dropout reasons were tracked by 61% of programmes (n=14). By contrast, monitoring of women applicants (n=10, 43%) and women starters (n=9, 39%) was considerably less common. Payment timeliness was monitored by 43% of programmes (n=10). Gender-sensitive worksite checklists and grievances by type were each tracked by only 26% of programmes (n=6). Two respondents (9%) selected "I don't know". Setting-based and role-based disaggregation are illustrated in Figure 5. Full results by delivery setting and respondent role are presented in Appendix B, Table 15.

Fig. 5. Tracked monitoring indicators by delivery setting and respondent role. (n=23)

Source: Own representation.

4.8 Perceived Effectiveness, Implementation, and Feasibility of Gender-Sensitive Design Measures

This section presents findings from five related questions. Q15 identifies which measures respondents considered most effective for women's completion. Q16 identifies measures respondents reported as having contributed to higher women's participation in their own programmes. Q18 captures respondents' ratings of the implemented measures' feasibility. Q19 presents reported changes in participation outcomes following implementation. Q20 captures respondents' perceived effectiveness of measures they had not selected in Q16, based on professional judgement. Q17 on feasibility constraints will be presented separately in Section 4.9.

Q15 - Perceived Most Effective Measures for Completion

Respondents selected up to three measures considered most effective for sustaining women's completion throughout the work cycle. All percentages refer to the share of the full sample (n=23). Worksite proximity was the most frequently selected measure (n=16, 70%), followed by work type (n=12, 52%). A second tier comprised women-only teams (n=8, 35%) and transport support (n=7, 30%). Direct payment to women was selected by 22% (n=5) and a flexible schedule by 17% (n=4). Female supervisor or team lead and gender-sensitive facilities were each selected by 13% (n=3). Childcare support, code of conduct, and induction were each selected by 9% (n=2), and gender guidance and training by 1 respondent (4%). None of the confidential grievance channel, payment timeliness, or emergency attendance rules was selected as a top-three completion measure by any respondent. Full results by delivery setting and respondent role are presented in Appendix B, Table 16.

Q16 - Measures Associated with Higher Women's Participation

Respondents selected up to three measures that contributed to higher women's participation (uptake and completion combined) in their specific programme. All percentages refer to the share of the full sample (n=23). Women's quotas and work type were the most frequently selected measures (48% each, n=11), followed by targeted outreach to women (43%, n=10) and worksite proximity (39%, n=9). Transport support was selected by 22% (n=5). Selection and registration adjustments, flexible schedule, women-only teams, and direct payment to women were each selected by 13% (n=3). Female supervisor or team lead, code of conduct, and induction were each selected by 2 respondents (9%), and gender-sensitive facilities by 1 respondent (4%). Childcare support, a confidential grievance channel, payment timeliness, gender guidance and training, and emergency attendance rules were not selected by any respondent as the top three participation measures. Q15 vs Q16 are illustrated in Figure 6. Full results by delivery setting are presented in Appendix B, Table 17.

Fig. 6. Perceived most effective measures for completion (Q15) vs measures reported as contributing to higher participation (Q16) (n=23, up to 3 selections each).

Source: Own representation.

Q18 - Feasibility Ratings of Implemented Measures

Q18 asked respondents to rate the feasibility of the measures they selected in Q16 (up to 3) using a five-point Likert scale (1=Very difficult; 5=Very feasible). Each respondent rated only the measures they had implemented themselves. When ranked by mean feasibility score, women-only teams received the highest rating (M=4.33, n=3), followed by transport support (M=4.20, n=5), women's quotas (M=3.91, n=11), and targeted outreach to women (M=3.70, n=10). Direct payment to women (M=3.67, n=3) and selection and registration adjustments (M=3.33, n=3) also fell within the feasible range. Female supervisor or team lead (M=3.00, n=2) and flexible schedule (M=2.67, n=3) approximated the scale midpoint. Work type (M=2.55, n=11) and worksite proximity (M=2.44, n=9) were the

two measures with the largest valid n in the difficult half of the scale; work-type responses were strongly dispersed across the full range (SD=1.57). Code of conduct and induction (M=1.00, n=2) was rated very difficult by both respondents who implemented it. Childcare support received no Q18 ratings. The feasibility rating of implemented measures is illustrated in Figure 7. Full results by delivery setting are presented in Appendix B, Table 19.

Fig. 7. Feasibility ratings of implemented measures. (n=23)

Source: Own representation

Q19 - Reported Changes in Participation Rates

Q19 asked respondents to rate how four participation outcomes changed after implementing their chosen Q16 measures: women's uptake, completion, dropout, and overall participation rates (1 = Much lower; 5 = Much higher). The dropout item was reverse-coded, so higher scores indicate better outcomes. For the dropout item, "rated 4+" therefore refers to responses indicating that dropout decreased (the "much lower" and "slightly lower" raw categories), which score highest after reversal. After an internal consistency check, two respondents were excluded; all findings are based on n=21. All four indicators had mean scores above the scale midpoint. Dropout reduction had the highest mean (M=3.52; 52% rated 4+), followed by completion (M=3.48; 57%), uptake (M=3.33; 57%), and overall participation (M=3.29; 57%).

Because Q19 asked respondents to rate outcomes following implementation of all their selected Q16 measures combined, the following per-measure groupings reflect the responses of respondents who included each measure in their package, not the isolated effect of any single measure. Among measures implemented by at least four respondents, respondents who included transport support in their Q16 package (n=4) reported the strongest combined-outcome signals for completion and dropout reduction (both M=4.25). Targeted outreach to women (n=10) and women's quotas (n=10)

indicated consistent improvement across all four indicators. Worksite proximity (n=8) indicated a distinct pattern: dropout reduction was the highest of all 4 items (M=4.00; 63% rated 4 or higher), while uptake and overall participation were closer to the midpoint. Work type (n=10) produced the most subdued uptake and overall participation scores, with dropout reduction the only indicator clearly above the midpoint (M=3.5). Full results by delivery setting and respondent role are presented in Appendix B, Tables 20, 21, 22, 23 and 24.

Q20 - Perceived Effectiveness of Non-Selected Measures

Q20 asked respondents to rate how strongly they agreed that each listed measure would increase women's participation (1=Strongly disagree; 5=Strongly agree). Through branching logic, respondents rated only measures they did not select in Q16. Since Q16 was capped at 3 selections, non-selected measures could mean either not implemented or implemented but not among the top three in Q16. Participants who did not implement these measures were asked to rate them based on their judgment, observations, and interactions with women workers, with an "I don't know" option for those unfamiliar or unsure of their effectiveness. Because Q20 pools vary by measure, widely implemented measures attracted fewer ratings, rarely selected measures more; results include the valid n for each item.

When ranked by mean agreement score, gender-sensitive facilities received the highest rating (M=4.41, n=22), followed by worksite proximity (M=4.36, n=14) and targeted outreach to women (M=4.17, n=12). Emergency attendance rules and selection and registration adjustments shared the next position (M=4.10 each, n=20), followed by work type (M=4.08, n=12). Transport support, child-care support, code of conduct and induction, and direct payment to women each had a mean of 4.00 (n=17, 22, 21, and 19, respectively). A second cluster included confidential grievance channel (M=3.90, n=21), gender guidance and training (M=3.87, n=23), women-only teams (M=3.85, n=20), payment timeliness (M=3.83, n=23), and women's quotas (M=3.83, n=12). Female supervisor or team lead (M=3.70, n=20) and flexible schedule (M=3.65, n=20) had the lowest means. "I don't know" responses were most frequent for emergency attendance rules (n=3) and confidential grievance channel (n=2). Full results by delivery setting are presented in Appendix B, Table 25.

4.9 Feasibility Constraints

Q17 - Constraints Limiting the Implementation of Gender-Sensitive Design

Respondents selected up to three constraints that most limited the feasibility of the measures identified in Q16 (n=23). Budget limits were by far the most frequently cited constraint (n=14, 61%), followed by community norms and acceptance (n=9, 39%) and donor reporting requirements (n=7, 30%). Limited staffing and time, and limited local childcare options were each cited by 26% (n=6). Setting-based disaggregation indicated that limited staffing and time was cited by 45.5% of both-settings respondents, compared to 11.1% in camp programmes and 0% in host-community programmes. Government approvals and regulatory constraints, and worksite location constraints were

selected by 17% (n=4 each). Data privacy restrictions were cited by 13% (n=3), and transport cost and safety constraints by 9% (n=2). Contractor capacity and behaviour was not selected by any respondent. Setting-based and role-based disaggregation are illustrated in Figure 8. Full results by delivery setting and respondent role are presented in Appendix B, Table 18.

Fig. 8. Feasibility constraints limiting implementation of gender-sensitive design (n=23)

Source: Own representation.

4.10 Target and Actual Women's Participation Rates

Q21 - Target vs Actual Women's Participation Rates

Respondents reported their programme's latest target and actual women's participation rates as percentages. Four respondents selected "I don't know" for the target rate and five for the actual rate. All statistics are based on the 18 paired responses that provided both values. The gap was calculated as the difference between actual and target; positive values indicate the programme exceeded its target.

Across the 18 paired responses, the mean target rate was 49.7% (median 49%, range 19–100%) and the mean actual rate was 45.5% (median 50%, range 16–99%), resulting in a mean gap of -4.2 percentage points (median -0.5). Nine programmes met or exceeded their targets by a mean of 5.4 percentage points, and nine fell short by a mean of 13.9 percentage points.

Refugee camp programmes indicated the strongest alignment with the target. All nine camp respondents provided paired data: the mean target rate was 54.2% (median 55%, range 40–68%) and the mean actual rate was 57.8% (median 59%, range 49–65%), resulting in a mean gap of +3.6 percentage points. Both-settings programmes indicated a markedly different pattern: of the 11

respondents, 7 provided paired data. The mean target was 51.9%, and the mean actual rate was 36.9%, resulting in a mean gap of -15.0 percentage points; this figure is heavily influenced by two outlier cases with targets of 90% and 100%. Six of the seven both-settings programmes fell short of their targets. Host-community programmes provided only two paired responses (mean target: 22.0%; mean actual: 20.5%; mean gap: -1.5 percentage points); these figures are illustrative only.

"I don't know" responses to Q21 were also examined by respondent role. Among programme managers (n=11), three (27%) selected "I don't know" for both the target and actual rates. MEAL (monitoring, evaluation, accountability and learning staff) and data staff (n=4) indicated a similar pattern, with one "I don't know" response each for target and actual (25% in both cases). Field officers (n=7) reported the lowest uncertainty: none selected "I don't know" for the target rate, and only one (14%) did so for the actual rate. Both-settings programmes indicated the highest rate of unknown participation figures: four of eleven respondents (36%) selected 'I don't know' for both target and actual rate, compared to none in refugee camp programmes and one of three in host-community programmes. Full results by delivery setting and respondent role are presented in Appendix B, Table 26.

Fig. 9. Target vs actual women's participation rates by delivery setting (n=18).

Source: Own representation

4.11 Chapter Summary

This chapter presented survey findings from 23 CfW practitioners across six design domains. Household consent (M=1.89) and documentation requirements (M=2.11) were the most acute recruitment barriers in camp settings, while host communities respondents reported the most severe application accessibility barrier (M=2.00). Worksite proximity and work type were the most frequently cited completion levers, but both were rated as difficult to implement. Transport and childcare support were less widely provided. Budget limits were the dominant feasibility constraint across all settings, while community norms defined the constraint profile in host-community programmes. These findings form

the empirical basis for the discussion and recommendations in Chapter 5.

5. Discussion and Recommendations

This chapter reads the findings of Chapter 4 against the theoretical and empirical framework established in Chapter 2. The goal is not to restate what the data showed, but to assess what those findings mean in relation to existing knowledge: where they are consistent with, extend, qualify, or contradict what the literature predicted, and what each relationship implies for CfW programme design in Jordan. Findings are read against the two-stage pipeline and feasibility framework established in Chapter 2.

The chapter proceeds in two parts. Section 5.1 conducts a domain-by-domain discussion, followed by a cross-cutting feasibility synthesis identifying the minimum viable package of six programme-operable design measures derived from the study. Section 5.2 derives concrete, evidence-grounded recommendations from that analysis, each specified by design action, delivery setting, and feasibility classification.

5.1 Discussion

All subgroup comparisons are descriptive and exploratory. Percentages and means characterise observed patterns and should not be seen as population estimates. Three subgroups need caution: the host-community delivery setting (n=3), and the MEAL staff role (n=4). Each observation in these groups is 33% and 25%, so a single response change shifts the reported percentage by that margin. Several Q18 feasibility cells have fewer than 4 respondents; their means (with n) should be treated as individual signals rather than subgroup estimates. Loewe et al. (2020) is cited extensively throughout this discussion because it remains the only empirical study of CfW effects in Jordan that covers gender, task acceptability, work permit data, and programme design in an integrated way; no comparable successor study has been published (see Section 2 for the literature search rationale).

5.1.1 Domain 1: Recruitment, Outreach, and Selection

The recruitment domain produced a complex pattern, combining strong alignment with known barriers and new findings that the literature did not predict. Four of the eight Q1 Likert items fell below the neutral midpoint of 3.0, confirming that structural barriers to women's entry were present across the sample and not limited to specific subgroups. The hierarchy of those barriers, however, does not follow what the literature would predict.

Household consent and the camp-specific severity

Household consent and gender norms were rated the most severe barrier overall (M=2.48, Q1), consistent with Oxfam (2018, p. 19), Zintl and Loewe (2022, p. 1298), and World Bank (2024b, p. 33). The survey adds a setting-level breakdown. Camp programmes reported the most acute household consent barrier (M=1.89), more severe than both-settings programmes (M=3.00) or host-

community programmes (M=2.33). Chapter 2 described community-norm pressure as stronger in host communities, where SOP governance does not regulate operations and women's visible public-space labour is directly judged by neighbours. The camp-specific severity observed in Q1 is better explained by high social density and visibility within camps, as documented by Oxfam (2018, p. 19) for Za'atari.

Chapter 2 also establishes that household approval is not a static constraint but a condition-dependent one. It is shaped by transport safety, worksite exposure to male strangers, and whether financial hardship is considered sufficient justification for women to work. Programmes that address these conditions before recruitment begins expand the pool of eligible women. Programmes that ignore them lose women before outreach has started.

Documentation: two distinct barriers across settings

Documentation requirements were the second-strongest barrier overall (M=2.70). The BNLWG (2020, Section 3.3.1) and Oxfam (2018, p. 18) show that the RAIS eligibility stack interacts with displacement-related documentation gaps in a way that can exclude women before any selection decision is made (GIZ, 2022, pp. 9-10). The barrier was most severe in host communities (M=1.67) and camps (M=2.11), and least severe in both-settings programmes (M=3.45). The camp severity is consistent with the mandatory RAIS pre-eligibility checks in Azraq and Za'atari, while the host-community severity reflects a different mechanism examined below. The small host-community subgroup (n=3) means its mean should be read as indicative.

In host communities, the barrier is different and more demanding. Unlike camp-based IBV, which does not require a work permit (BNLWG, 2022, Section 3; BNLWG, 2020, Section 3.3), host communities CfW falls under formal employment rules requiring Syrian refugees to hold a valid work permit in an eligible sector. As noted in section 2.8, by mid-2019, women received only approximately 5% of the 156,761 work permits issued to Syrian refugees in Jordan (Loewe et al., 2020, p. 49). By 2025, this share had risen to 15.6% of permits issued (UNHCR, 2025b), reflecting gradual progress following Jordan Compact sector liberalisation, yet women remained significantly underrepresented relative to their share of the working-age refugee population, and structural exclusion persists at a different magnitude. The Q1 documentation barrier, therefore, captures two distinct constraints: in camps, the RAIS eligibility stack; in host communities, a formal labour-market threshold that most Syrian refugee women have not yet cleared. The low permit rate does not necessarily reflect only documentation barriers; community norms and other constraints may also prevent women from applying in the first place.

Manageable barriers: registration complexity and application logistics

Registration complexity (M=2.83 overall) and application timing and location (M=2.91) tell a different story. Unlike household consent or documentation requirements, these are programme design choices that can be changed within a single delivery cycle without SOP revisions or donor

negotiation. The setting breakdown sharpens this: registration complexity was most acute in camps, while application timing and location were most severe in host communities (M=2.00), where no procedural standard governs how or where applications are collected. MEAL staff rated documentation as substantially less of a barrier (M=4.00) than programme managers (M=2.64) or field officers (M=2.29), suggesting those closest to the eligibility process experience it as a heavier burden than those who design or monitor it from a distance.

Fairness and transparency

Recruitment information was rated the most accessible item of all (M=4.48), and overall process fairness was rated positively (M=4.04). The camp fairness score (M=4.11) is worth noting. Chapter 2 reported Oxfam's (2018, pp. 18-19) finding that favouritism and informal connections were common in Za'atari, even under SOP governance. The higher score may suggest SOP governance has improved perceived transparency since 2018. The lowest score was in host-community programmes (M=3.67), where the ILO/GIZ co-chaired framework provides guidance but carries no mandatory force. Both scores reflect practitioner perception. A process can appear fair to those running it while still excluding the most constrained applicants through mechanisms embedded in its design.

Inclusion measures

Women's quotas were the most widely reported active inclusion measure (74%), with similar usage across settings (67-82%, Q2). Both findings align with the quota encouragement in BNLWG (2020, Section 3.7) and BNLWG (2022, Section 4), and extend it by showing that quotas are now a widely adopted tool rather than a camp-specific feature. Targeted outreach, by contrast, shows the sharpest setting gap of any inclusion measure: reported by 65% of programmes overall but by only 33% of host-community programmes (Q2). Chapter 2 predicted that host-community programmes, lacking shared outreach standards, would be particularly vulnerable to network-based information gaps (ILO, 2021, pp. 8, 32). The 33% figure quantifies that gap and gives it a measurable value.

Exclusion risk screening

Only 39% of programmes used exclusion risk screening (Q2), and the rate was consistently low across all settings. Chapter 2 discussed vulnerability scoring, quotas, and targeted outreach, but did not identify proactive exclusion risk screening as a distinct mechanism. The low adoption rate indicates that most programmes focus on inclusion measures while leaving upstream exclusion prevention largely unaddressed. For women facing the strongest consent and documentation barriers, that is where the design gap is most consequential.

Selection mechanisms and the structural double-bind in camps

Vulnerability scoring accounted for 70% of selection mechanisms overall (Q3). In camps, its relative prevalence was lower (56%) because committee-based decisions were reported by 56% of camp programmes, compared with 18% in both-settings and 0% in host communities. Chapter 2 noted

that vulnerability scoring is often treated as administratively neutral (BNLWG, 2020, Section 3.3.1; Loewe et al., 2020, pp. 146-147), yet available studies rarely examine how score construction interacts with gender. The concentration of committee decisions in camps reinforces it: the mechanism most associated with informal social networks appears most often precisely where structural barriers for women are highest.

FCFS was reported by 44% of camp programmes but only 9% of both-settings programmes (Q3). FCFS and committee decisions differ in form but produce similar effects: FCFS advantages those who can reach the application point quickly and face fewer documentation hurdles; committee decisions favour those with stronger social ties. Committee decisions were concentrated in camps (56%) and absent from host communities (0%), while FCFS appeared primarily in camps (44%) and one host-community programme (33%). Together, their co-occurrence is most pronounced in camp settings, where they create a selection environment that systematically disadvantages the most constrained applicants.

Neither mechanism is unusual in isolation; both have been reported elsewhere in CfW literature. The issue is that they co-exist in camps that also report the highest documentation burden ($M=2.11$) and the most acute household consent barrier ($M=1.89$). The result is a structural double-bind: women who face the greatest difficulty obtaining permission to apply and gathering the required documents are also the ones most likely to lose out in selection processes that reward speed and social connections. No single design change resolves this. It requires simultaneous adjustment at both the barrier and the selection stages.

5.1.2 Domain 2: Work Design and Work-type Acceptability

The work design domain largely aligns with the expectations outlined in Chapter 2. It is also where the gap between perceived effectiveness and perceived feasibility is most evident.

Work-type distribution

Cleaning was the dominant work type (65% overall), most concentrated in camps (78%), consistent with the IBV definitions of semi-skilled work (BNLWG, 2020, Section 2.1). Greening and agriculture appeared in 55% of both-settings and 67% of host-community programmes, but not in camps, reflecting their exclusion from IBV categories (Q4). Care work appeared exclusively in camp settings (22%), again consistent with IBV provisions.

Worksite exposure

A majority of programmes operated in public or open spaces (57%), with the highest proportion in camps (67%, Q5). Chapter 2 documents that highly visible public-space tasks are often seen as socially unsuitable for women and associated with stigma (Loewe et al., 2020, pp. 104–106). The setting with the strongest household consent barriers, therefore, also has the highest concentration of public worksites. IBV work-type categories explain why this pattern exists, but the pattern still

matters for women's participation decisions.

The female supervisor gap

Team composition and supervision deepen this concern. Female supervisors or team leads were reported in only 22% of camp programmes, compared with 67% in host communities and 82% in both-settings programmes (Q6). Chapter 2 established that female supervisors are an explicit, contractable design option and that gender-balanced supervision cannot be replaced simply by adjusting work type (ILO, 2022, p. 54; ILO, 2024, p. 37). The 22% figure means most camp programmes are running public or mixed-gender worksites under male-dominated supervision, despite evidence that women's sense of safety is shaped by who supervises them (ILO, 2024, p. 37).

"Mixed-gender teams managed safely" was reported by 78% of camp programmes, more than any other setting (Q6). Chapter 2 observed that managed mixed-gender teams appear in some studies but are rarely analysed as a distinct design choice. In practice, the survey indicates they have become the primary arrangement in camps, used as a practical alternative when female supervisors are unavailable. This is an adaptation that deserves monitoring, not endorsement. Practitioner-side assessments of safe management are not equivalent to women's lived experience of supervision quality, and the survey cannot establish that one substitutes for the other.

A compounding situation in camps

Considered together, the three findings describe a compounding situation rather than three separate gaps. Camps report the highest public worksite exposure (67%, Q5), the lowest female supervisor availability (22%, Q6), and the highest reliance on mixed-gender teams managed safely (78%, Q6). All three coincide in the setting reporting the strongest household consent barriers (M=1.89, Q1).

Outreach and quota measures bring women into programmes partly by signalling safe and appropriate conditions. If the actual worksite profile does not reflect those conditions, mostly public spaces, mostly male supervisors, mostly mixed-gender teams, women who joined under one set of expectations are working under another. That gap between what entry measures imply and what completion conditions deliver is where uptake and completion conflict in this setting.

Work-type adaptation: valued but hard to implement

Work-type was selected as a top-three completion lever by 52% of respondents (Q15) and as a top-three participation measure by 48% of respondents (Q16), which strongly aligns with the literature's position that work-type acceptability is a core condition for both entry and attendance. The implementation difficulty is real. Among all measures rated in Q18 by at least ten respondents, work-type adaptation had the lowest feasibility mean (M=2.55, n=11) and the highest dispersion (SD=1.57), indicating sharp practitioner disagreement about achievability.

The division reflects setting differences. In camp settings, IBV-defined work-types, covering community services, administrative tasks, light maintenance, and care work (BNLWG, 2020, Section 2.1;

BNLWG, 2022, Section 1), are already among the more socially acceptable options for women because they avoid the public visibility that Loewe et al. (2020, pp. 104-106) identify as the primary source of stigma. The feasibility challenge mainly affects host communities and both-settings programmes, where tasks include waste collection and other visible activities. The dispersion in Q18 indicates varied and socially contested task portfolios rather than a uniform constraint.

5.1.3 Domain 3: Time, Transport, and Childcare

This domain is where the survey most closely aligns with the literature and, at the same time, reveals the clearest gaps between what is recognised as important and what is delivered.

Scheduling

Flexible shifts were reported only in camp programmes (44% of camp respondents; 0% elsewhere, Q7), consistent with the Azraq SOP requirement to cap daily working hours at six and to specify hours in job advertisements (BNLWG, 2020, Section 2.1). Both-settings and host-community programmes reported only fixed morning-only schedules. The finding aligns directly with Chapter 2's observation that time-design standards are codified in camps but not in host-community programmes.

The Q7 finding means more than a compliance observation. Flexible shifts appear exclusively in camps, but at 44% of camp programmes, they represent a deliberate operational choice by practitioners working with the most constrained women in the sample. Their absence elsewhere reflects the absence of a standard that would permit them, not evidence that morning-only schedules serve women better.

The broader dataset qualifies any case for extending flexible shifts. They ranked sixth in Q15 (17%) and joint sixth in Q16 (13%). Practitioners who implemented them rated feasibility below the midpoint ($M=2.67$, Q18). In Q20, flexible scheduling received the lowest perceived effectiveness score of any measure in the sample ($M=3.65$). Practitioners who had not implemented flexible shifts did not expect them to make a material difference. The data do not support the view that flexible scheduling is an underused lever. What they do suggest is that the morning-only pattern has never been formally evaluated against flexible alternatives. It is the default, not a tested design choice.

The proximity paradox

Worksite proximity was selected by 70% of respondents as one of the top three levers for sustaining women's attendance (Q15), making it the most frequently chosen completion measure in the sample. Chapter 2 treated proximity as a background preference (Loewe et al., 2020, p. 136, 161; ILO, 2021, p. 32). The Q15 result goes further: the frequency with which practitioners ranked it above transport, work-type adaptation, and scheduling suggests they treat proximity as a distinct and consequential design variable, not a secondary convenience.

Yet the actual proximity distribution was nearly even: 52% of programmes located worksites in the

same neighbourhood, 48% in the same city (Q8), with no strong setting pattern. This suggests proximity varies with site availability and programme geography rather than explicit design decisions. It is the measure practitioners most value for completion, but its distribution appears to be determined by chance rather than intent.

If proximity were deliberately used as a design lever, a setting-differentiated pattern would be expected in Q8, with camp programmes making specific site-selection decisions to minimise distance, or host-community programmes negotiating worksite locations with municipalities. No such pattern emerges. Chapter 2 identified the structural reason: in host-community programmes, worksite selection is driven by municipal proposals evaluated on cost-sharing and maintenance criteria, not on proximity to women participants (ILO, 2024, p. 34). The Q8 distribution is the predictable result of a site-selection process that lacks a gender-proximity criterion. The gap between valuing this lever and actively managing it is one of the more important accountability findings in the dataset.

Transport support: absent, feasible, and highly effective

Transport support was absent from 61% of programmes. Camp programmes had the lowest provision rate, with 78% reporting no support at all (Q9). Chapter 2 documents transport problems as a major structural barrier to women's labour force participation (Alam & Bagnoli, 2023, p. 10). Camp programmes might therefore be expected to prioritise transport. The survey indicates they do not.

One possible explanation is that geographic containment within camps compensates for transport gaps. If worksites are naturally close to women's homes, the need for organised transport diminishes. The Q8 data do not support this. The proximity distribution in camps, 56% same-neighbourhood and 44% same-city, is almost identical to the overall sample split of 52% and 48%. If proximity were genuinely substituting for transport, a much higher same-neighbourhood rate would be expected in camps. That difference does not appear.

The Q19 data offer a further check: respondents who implemented transport support reported the strongest combined completion and dropout-reduction signals of any subgroup (both $M=4.25$). If proximity were covering the gap, transport would not produce signals of that strength when provided. Transport is simply not funded in camps. The absence is real rather than offset by something else.

The combination raises a specific accountability question. Where transport had been implemented, it was not perceived as difficult: it received the highest feasibility rating of any logistical measure among those who had implemented it ($M=4.20$, Q18). MEAL staff, whose function places them closest to attendance patterns, selected transport support as a top-three completion lever 75% of the time, compared to only 9% of programme managers. The measure that those tracking dropouts consider most critical is the one that budget controllers most consistently decline to fund. High effect and high feasibility when implemented, yet absent from most programmes, make continued non-provision an accountability question, not a structural constraint.

Childcare support: recognised as essential, almost entirely absent

Only four of 23 programmes provided any form of childcare support (17%), and all four were camp programmes (44% of camp respondents; 0% in both-settings and host communities, Q10). Chapter 2 documented that formal childcare reaches less than 3% of children under five in Jordan and that care obligations push women out of paid work (World Bank, 2024b, p. 7). UN Women's evaluation in Jordan identified childcare as a shared barrier across both settings (UN Women Jordan Office, 2024, p. 35). Only camp programmes in this sample attempted to respond at scale.

The Q20 data adds an important dimension. Among respondents who had not selected childcare, the measure received a mean perceived effectiveness score of 4.00 (n=22, one "I don't know" excluded), indicating broad recognition of its value despite low provision. Q17 identifies the main constraints: budget limits (61%) and limited local childcare options (26%). These are largely policy-dependent or system-dependent conditions. For host-community programmes in particular, the absence of childcare provision in this sample must be understood against this wider structural context.

5.1.4 Domain 4: Worksite Conditions, Safety, and Protection

The worksite-conditions domain is mostly consistent with the literature, but also presents one of the clearest challenges to Chapter 2's expectations regarding the regulatory asymmetry between camps and host communities.

Self-reported provision rates

Several core conditions were widely reported. PPE provision was reported by 87% of programmes (Q11). Confidential reporting channels and timely complaint handling were each present in 78% of programmes. Separate toilets, supportive supervision, codes of conduct, and harassment-prevention measures were reported by 75% of respondents. These patterns align with Chapter 2's view that safety and protection measures can be mandated through SOPs and procurement requirements (BNLWG, 2020, Section 5; BNLWG, 2022, Section 5; ILO, 2022, pp. 40-45).

Why high provision rates may not tell the full story.

These rates deserve scrutiny. When respondents who report near-universal PPE provision (87%) and widespread grievance channels (78%) are working within programmes that persistently fall short of women's participation targets, a mean achievement deficit of 15 percentage points in both-settings programmes makes two competing interpretations plausible.

The first is that actual compliance is somewhat lower than self-reported. Respondents characterised their own programmes, and social-desirability bias is a structural risk in self-assessment instruments, particularly for items such as harassment prevention and grievance mechanisms, where reporting non-provision carries professional and reputational costs.

The second is more consequential for programme design: even where physical provisions are in place, they may be insufficient if the behavioural and social dimensions of safety remain

unaddressed. A toilet on site does not constitute a safe worksite if harassment goes unrecorded. A complaints box does not constitute a functioning grievance mechanism if women fear identification. The 2024 ILO cluster evaluation is explicit on this point, finding that sensitivity to women's needs remained incomplete, including dignified working conditions, access to leadership roles, and safeguards (ILO, 2024, p. 37). The same evaluation documented specific violations in Jordan, including the absence of drinking water and toilets at worksites, salary deductions, and precarious employment conditions (ILO, 2024, pp. 39-40), confirming that compliance gaps are observed by independent evaluators in the same delivery context examined in this study. Both interpretations converge on the same implication: high self-reported provision rates are not a reliable proxy for the quality or lived effectiveness of worksite protection.

An unexpected pattern: onboarding briefings lower in camps

All host-community programmes reported onboarding briefings (100%), as did 91% of both-settings programmes, but only 56% of camp programmes (Q11). Chapter 2 treated the camp SOP framework as a stronger regulatory environment that should ensure better implementation of such standards. Onboarding briefings are explicitly required in camp SOPs, which state that volunteers must be informed about complaint mechanisms and rights during enrolment (BNLWG, 2020, Section 5.6; BNLWG, 2022, Section 5). The lower reported rate in camps therefore contradicts what the existence of the SOPs would predict.

Two explanations are possible. Onboarding may be delivered routinely in camp programmes but not recognised by respondents as a distinct measure. Alternatively, the requirement may not be fully implemented in practice. In either case, the finding has monitoring and accountability implications: if a mandatory activity is not tracked or is perceived as a background routine rather than an explicit action, implementation gaps cannot be systematically identified.

Private rest and prayer space: the weakest provision

Private rest and prayer space was the least consistently provided worksite feature, reported by only 52% of programmes overall and by the lowest percentage in both-settings programmes (36%, Q11). Chapter 2 highlighted WASH provision and the need for dignified conditions for menstruating women (ILO, 2024, p. 37) but did not identify private rest and prayer space as a separate indicator. The survey makes clear that it is one of the least consistently delivered elements of gender-sensitive worksite design across the ten features measured.

The Q20 data sharpens this point. Gender-sensitive facilities received the highest mean agreement score for perceived effectiveness in Q20 (M=4.41, n=22), above worksite proximity, targeted outreach, and transport support. Yet Q11 reveals that private rest and prayer space, the weakest component of this bundle, was present in only 52% of programmes, while separate toilets (74%) and drinking water (70%) were more consistently provided. High perceived value for the bundle does not translate consistently into the provision of its most dignity-sensitive component. That component is

an operational decision within the programme manager's remit, not a budget or infrastructure constraint.

Emergency attendance rules: absent from rankings because they may feel fixed

Emergency attendance rules were not selected as a top-three completion lever in Q15 and did not appear among the main participation measures in Q16. Given that camp SOPs include maternity protections and lactation breaks (BNLWG, 2020, Section 5.5; BNLWG, 2022, Section 2), this absence likely reflects how respondents categorised measures when answering the survey. Rules anchored in labour standards and regulations are experienced as fixed conditions rather than active design choices, and they therefore drop out of rankings focused on measures practitioners perceive as adjustable.

5.1.5 Domain 5: Payment Modality and Financial Control

Mobile wallets were the most widely used payment method overall (74%) and reported by 100% of camp programmes (Q12). The finding aligns with Za'atari SOP encouragement of mobile wallets in larger programmes (BNLWG, 2022, Section 3), which has led to full adoption in camp settings. Equal pay for women and men was near-universal at 96% (Q13), indicating that wage parity has effectively become standard practice and is no longer a major distinguishing feature between programmes.

The infrastructure-without-follow-through gap

The critical issue is the relationship between digital payments and women's actual financial control. In camp settings where all programmes used mobile wallets, only 56% reported making direct payments to women (Q13). Both-settings and host-community programmes reported substantially higher rates: 91% and 100% respectively. Chapter 2, drawing on GIZ (2022, p. 28) and ILO (2021, p. 27), emphasised that payment modality is a financial-control variable and that digital accounts do not automatically secure women's control over wages. Camp programmes have fully adopted digital payment infrastructure but have not ensured that wages are consistently deposited into women's own accounts. All five respondents who did not select direct payment to women had selected mobile wallets as one of their programme's payment modalities.

Payment timeliness follows the same pattern. Overall, 78% of programmes reported timely payment, but only 56% of camp programmes, compared with 91% in both-settings and 100% in host-community programmes (Q13). Chapter 2 noted that payment delays undermine household trust and erode the benefits of digitalisation (Loewe et al., 2020, p. 136; ILO, 2021, p. 27). Four of the five respondents who did not select timely payment had selected mobile wallets as one of their programme's payment modalities.

Mobile wallet use, direct payment to women, and timeliness are three distinct dimensions that cannot be collapsed into a single digital payment variable. For camp programmes in particular, the distinction is central: they have built digital infrastructure but have not yet fully translated it into consistent,

women-centred financial control.

5.1.6 Domain 6: Monitoring

The monitoring domain reveals a finding absent from the literature: the problem is not only what monitoring systems fail to collect, but what they fail to circulate.

Pipeline-stage tracking

The percentage of women selected was tracked by 83% of programmes (Q14). Women completers and women who dropped out were tracked by 74% and 70%, respectively. In contrast, only 43% of programmes monitored women applicants and only 39% monitored women starters. More than half of the programmes in the sample had no visibility into how many women reached the entry stage. Whether this emphasis on end-stage indicators reflects donor reporting requirements, evaluation framework conventions, or simply the fact that completion data is easier to collect, the survey cannot establish. What it establishes is that the imbalance is consistent across all delivery settings, not only in camps where RAIS mandates specific outputs.

Only 26% of programmes tracked gender-sensitive checklists and grievances by type, with none in host-community programmes (Q14). This aligns with the DEval meta-evaluation, which found that gender-sensitive process indicators are often weak or missing (DEval, 2021, pp. 8-9).

Knowing the data exists is not the same as using it

A separate pattern concerns how monitoring knowledge is distributed within programmes, not just across them. MEAL staff reported higher awareness of tracked indicators than field officers, but this cannot be read as a straightforward intra-organisational knowledge gap: all four MEAL staff worked in both-settings programmes, while four of the seven field officers were concentrated in camps. The two groups operated in different delivery environments, so role and setting differences cannot be separated.

A comparison within the setting shows that among camp respondents, programme managers reported tracking women applicants at 75% (3 of 4), while field officers reported 25% (1 of 4). Small cell sizes limit conclusions but suggest professional role influences monitoring awareness. One programme manager and one field officer also said "I don't know" when asked what their programmes tracked, indicating uncertainty extends beyond field staff.

Programme managers who cannot report their own participation figures

Among programme managers, the group responsible for negotiating participation targets with donors and deciding which design measures to fund, 27% selected "I don't know" for their own programme's target rate, and 27% for the actual rate. The issue is not field-level visibility. Programme managers set targets and control budgets. When a programme manager cannot report whether their programme is meeting its participation goals, it points to a breakdown in the feedback mechanism that should connect monitoring evidence to design choices. Chapter 2's monitoring recommendations

focus on data collection and indicator design (ILO, 2021, p. 10; ILO, 2024, pp. 47-50). The Q21 pattern points to a prior problem: the people making decisions are not using, and in some cases not seeing, the data that monitoring systems are meant to produce. The survey cannot confirm whether these data were collected but not circulated, or never reliably collected; both are consistent with the reporting gap observed, and distinguishing them requires further research

Better design requires better circulation, not only better collection

The standard response to monitoring gaps in CfW evaluations is to add indicators, track more pipeline stages, disaggregate more carefully, and report more completely. That response addresses the collection side of the problem. It does not address the circulation side. A programme that adds women-applicant tracking to its MEAL framework but does not establish a routine for field officers to see and use that data has improved its reporting without improving its decision-making. Better indicator design is necessary but not sufficient. It must be paired with deliberate internal communication structures: monitoring summaries shared across roles, kick-off meetings that present prior-cycle findings before implementation begins, and dropout logs maintained by field officers that feed directly into MEAL systems, so that data collected at the system level reaches the people whose daily decisions determine whether women enter and stay in programmes.

5.1.7 Feasibility Synthesis

The feasibility framework developed in Chapter 2 distinguishes between measures that can be implemented within a single programme cycle (programme-operable) and those that rely on broader policy or system change (policy-dependent). The Q17 and Q18 results apply this distinction to specific measures and reveal a consistent, actionable pattern.

What practitioners cite as constraints

Budget limits were cited by 61% of respondents as the primary barrier to implementing gender-sensitive design (Q17), rising to 78% in camp programmes. Community norms were cited by 39%, consistent with Chapter 2's identification of norm pressure as defining in host communities contexts (ILO, 2021, p. 32). All three host communities respondents cited community norms (100%), though the subgroup is treated as indicative given its size. Donor reporting requirements were cited by 30%, consistent with Chapter 2's observation that administrative demands can limit design flexibility (ILO, 2021, p. 32).

Contractor capacity, documented in the literature as a gap requiring trained personnel, dedicated budget lines, and knowledge of GBV protocols (ILO, 2021, p. 8; ILO, 2022, pp. 40-45), was not cited as a top-three constraint by any respondent. Three explanations are possible: practitioners may be attributing delivery failures to budget constraints rather than contractor performance; managers may lack sufficient visibility into contractor practices to identify them as a constraint; or contractor capacity in Jordan may genuinely have improved since the literature was written, which would itself be a finding. The data cannot distinguish between these explanations, but the complete absence of this

constraint is worth noting.

The effectiveness-feasibility tension

The clearest pattern in the feasibility data is the gap between perceived effectiveness and perceived difficulty for two measures. Worksite proximity and work-type adaptation were among the most frequently selected completion levers (70% and 52% in Q15; 39% and 48% in Q16), yet both were rated in the difficult range on Q18: work-type adaptation (M=2.55, n=11) and proximity (M=2.44, n=9), with proximity particularly low in camps (M=2.00).

The difficulty is real in both cases but differently sourced. Camp-based practitioners work within an IBV task portfolio already socially acceptable for women, while those in host communities and both-settings programmes face harder negotiations around more visible public-space activities. Proximity, physical geography, land use, and site availability impose limits that programmes cannot unilaterally overcome, especially in camps. A single easy-versus-difficult label is therefore insufficient. Some difficulties are operational and can be addressed within a programme cycle; others are structural. Figure 10 maps these measures across both dimensions, making the priority groupings visible: measures that are both valued and feasible (do first), those valued but difficult (invest in), and those of lower current priority.

Fig. 10. Feasibility (Q18) × effectiveness (Q15/Q16) priority matrix for gender-sensitive design measures.

Source: own representation.

Both-settings programmes: an underexamined operational category

One pattern absent from existing literature concerns programmes operating simultaneously across both camp and host-community settings. Previous evaluations treat the two settings as separate categories but do not examine programmes that manage both regulatory frameworks simultaneously.

Both-settings programmes showed the largest participation gap of any setting: a mean of -15.0 percentage points between target and actual rates, with six of seven paired respondents falling short (Q21). Two outlier targets of 90% and 100% amplify the mean, but the underperformance pattern holds across the group. Three convergent signals point to operational complexity as the underlying cause. First, both-settings respondents cited limited staffing and time at 45.5%, the highest of any setting (Q17). Second, they rated work-type adaptation as least feasible of any setting (M=2.25, Q18). Third, four of eleven could not report their own programme's target or actual participation rate (Q21). Managing IBV SOPs and work-permit requirements simultaneously generates compliance, reporting, and staffing obligations that single-setting programmes do not carry, and this overhead is not yet reflected in how implementing agencies resource or plan this type of delivery.

By contrast, women's quotas and targeted outreach sit firmly in the programme-operable, feasible range. Quotas received a mean feasibility rating of 3.91 (n=11) and targeted outreach 3.70 (n=10) among those who implemented them (Q18). Q19 indicates consistent positive participation-improvement signals across all four indicators, with means ranging from 3.29 to 3.52. These are measures that practitioners both value and can deliver within a single programme cycle.

Target achievement is a starting point, not an endpoint

In camps, the mean target rate was 54.2% and the mean actual rate was 57.8%, a positive gap of 3.6 percentage points (Q21). This should not be read as evidence of good programme design. Two explanations are worth considering, and both may be true simultaneously.

First, targets may be calibrated to past underperformance rather than to what the setting could realistically achieve. A target of 30-35% women's share is not ambitious where IBV is one of the very few regulated income opportunities available to camp women; routinely exceeding it may say more about the target than about the programme. Second, women in Azraq and Za'atari participate in IBV partly because they have no comparable alternative. Work-permit restrictions that limit access to host communities employment do not apply inside camps, meaning participation may reflect constrained choice rather than programme quality. Neither explanation dismisses the value of what camp programmes deliver, but both suggest that over-achievement against a weak target does not resolve the design gaps documented in this study.

Cross-domain synthesis: infrastructure without follow-through

Taken together, the six domains point to a consistent answer to the research question. Women's

uptake and completion in Jordanian CfW programmes are not determined by any single design feature, but by a chain of interacting conditions that must be addressed at both pipeline stages. At entry, the primary barriers are household consent, documentation requirements, and, particularly in host-community programmes, the absence of targeted outreach. In camps, entry barriers are further compounded by selection mechanisms, specifically FCFS and committee-based decisions, that systematically disadvantage the most constrained applicants. At completion, worksite proximity, transport support, and work-type acceptability are the most valued levers, yet the two most valued are also the hardest to operationalise under current conditions. Across both stages, the payment and monitoring domains reveal a consistent pattern: digital payment systems that do not yet guarantee women's financial control, and monitoring frameworks that track the end of the pipeline while remaining largely blind to what happens at the entry point.

The minimum viable package: six programme-operable measures, one per domain

Across every domain, a subset of measures consistently satisfies three conditions: it is programme-operable within a single cycle without regulatory reform; it was rated as feasible by the practitioners who implemented it; and it is currently absent or inconsistently applied across the sample, making it an actionable gap rather than existing good practice. Six measures emerge, one from each domain:

1. *Targeted outreach through women-accessible channels* (recruitment domain): deliverable within a single cycle, rated feasible by implementers (M=3.70, Q18), and absent from 67% of host-community programmes.
2. *Norm-sensitive work-type and task assignment combined with at least one gender-safe team structure* (work design domain): addresses the compounding of public worksite exposure, mixed-gender teams, and low female supervision identified as concentrated in camp settings.
3. *A fixed morning schedule as the programme default, with a flexible-shift option where SOP governance permits* (time and transport domain): the only measure in this domain that is programme-operable and applicable across both delivery settings without transport infrastructure investment.
4. *A gender-sensitive worksite checklist combined with a functioning confidential grievance mechanism* (worksite safety domain): addresses the gap between SOP requirements and verified practice documented in Domain 4. Where female supervisors are absent, as in 78% of camp programmes, the checklist, code of conduct, and grievance channel function as a coordinated compensating unit, not as separate items.
5. *Direct wage payments recorded in the woman's own name* (payment domain): addresses the measurable gap between digital payment infrastructure and women's actual financial control, closable through enrolment checks and account verification without waiting for broader financial-sector reform.
6. *Pipeline-stage indicator tracking from applicants through to categorised early exits* (monitoring

domain): addresses the structural invisibility of the entry stage, currently untracked in more than half of programmes, with women applicants monitored by only 43% and women starters by only 39%, and provides the feedback link between monitoring evidence and design decisions that 27% of programme managers in this sample could not demonstrate.

These six measures constitute the minimum viable package because they are the only combination that addresses every pipeline domain, applies under current regulatory conditions in both delivery settings, and requires no authority beyond the programme manager's existing procurement, staffing, and operational remit. Three additional measures, transport support, childcare provision, and work-permit access for Syrian refugee women, exceed this minimum because they depend on resources, policy conditions, or inter-agency coordination that not all programmes can guarantee within a single cycle.

The recommendations in Section 5.2 translate this analysis into specific programme-level actions, organised by domain, delivery setting, and feasibility classification. Each recommendation is a starting point for piloting and iterative adaptation, monitored against the pipeline-stage indicators in Appendix C. The relative weight of different design levers cannot be established from this data alone, as inferential testing was not applied. Any recommendation concerning safety, household consent, or social acceptability should be treated as a practitioner-side hypothesis requiring validation with women participants.

5.2 Recommendations for Action

The 36 recommendations presented in this section and consolidated in Appendix D, Table 29, were derived through a four-step process. First, the literature review established what gender-responsive CfW design and monitoring should look like across all six domains, drawing on ILO (2021, 2024), DEval (2021), UN Women Jordan Office (2024), BNLWG (2020, 2022), Loewe et al. (2020), Oxfam (2018), GIZ (2022), and World Bank (2024b) as the reference standards, with additional monitoring indicators derived from the researcher's direct field experience in CfW programme monitoring and subsequently validated against practitioner responses (Q14), as detailed below. Second, survey findings from Q1 to Q21 documented current practice, establishing what programmes in this sample actually do. Q14 specifically measured current monitoring practice against indicators drawn from two sources: monitoring elements identified as necessary in the evaluation literature, and additional indicators constructed by the researcher to capture tracking gaps not addressed in existing evaluations, which were subsequently validated through practitioner responses. Q21 provided a further monitoring-related finding, revealing that 27% of programme managers could not report their own programme's participation target or achieved rate, which directly informed R6.6 and R6.8. Third, each gap between the established standard and observed current practice was assessed across four dimensions: the delivery setting to which it applies, whether it is programme-operable or policy-dependent, the actor responsible, and the programme cycle stage at which action must occur. Q17 directly informed the programme-operable versus policy-dependent

classification by documenting the constraints practitioners identified as most limiting. Q15, Q16, Q18, and Q20 provided the effectiveness and feasibility evidence that grounded each recommendation in practitioner-reported experience: Q15 and Q16 identified which measures practitioners considered most effective for completion and participation, respectively; Q18 captured feasibility ratings from those who implemented each measure; and Q20 captured perceived effectiveness from those who did not. Fourth, each gap that met these criteria was formulated as a discrete, actionable recommendation. The count of 36 is therefore the number of distinct actionable gaps that emerged from applying this process across all six domains, not a predetermined target. Because the six domains were treated as exhaustive coverage areas, the number of recommendations per domain reflects the distinct gaps each surfaced rather than any intended balance. Of the 36, 34 are programme-operable, and 2 are policy-dependent. One recommendation (R3.6) represents an exploratory design proposition, derived from the childcare findings and the existing childcare literature, rather than a documented implementation gap. It is explicitly flagged as requiring pilot testing before wider adoption. R3.6 is the only recommendation not anchored to a documented standard-practice gap; all others derive from an observed gap between literature standard and survey-reported practice. The specific literature standard, survey gap, effectiveness evidence, and feasibility evidence for each recommendation are detailed in Appendix D, Tab. 30.

5.2.1 Recruitment, Outreach, and Selection

Only 33% of host-community programmes used targeted outreach to women (Q2), the lowest of any inclusion measure in the sample, and host communities respondents reported the lowest outreach effectiveness scores in Q1. Implementing agencies should treat targeted outreach as a required activity, not an optional one.

Targeted outreach should do more than increase the number of women applicants. It should directly address the constraints that suppress participation in the first place. Each recruitment round should use at least one women-accessible channel, for example, women's centres, schools, health centres, or trusted WhatsApp groups, rather than relying solely on male community leaders or mixed public spaces. Outreach messages should clearly state the design features that matter most for women's decisions: team composition, female supervisor availability, worksite proximity, transport or childcare support where available, and the exact location and timing of registration. Programmes can monitor whether each call for applications meets these criteria using a simple yes/no check in their MEAL tools.

In host-community programmes specifically, where application timing and location were the most severe procedural barriers (M=2.00, Q1), agencies should also review when and where applications are physically collected. Bringing registration to women's centres or community spaces rather than requiring travel to a fixed office is a low-cost design adjustment that removes a documented barrier without requiring SOP revision or donor negotiation.

Where household consent was the most severe entry barrier (M=2.48 overall; M=1.89 in camps), outreach should extend to male household members. Pre-cycle orientation sessions explaining work conditions, safety arrangements, and female supervision availability address the condition-dependent nature of consent documented in Q1 directly.

Addressing the risks associated with FCFS and committee-based decisions in camps (Q3) requires SOP-level adjustments. Camp selection frameworks should specify that FCFS is inappropriate as a primary mechanism where documentation and mobility barriers are strongest. Committee decisions should be tied to defined vulnerability and gender criteria and documented accordingly. Both steps are achievable within the existing SOP revision process and do not require broader legal reform. The corresponding programme-level actions are set out as R1.1-R1.7 in Appendix D, Table 29.

5.2.2 Work Design and work-type Acceptability

In host-community programmes, where IBV constraints do not apply, programme specifications should require contractors to move beyond highly visible public-space activities. Administrative and community-service tasks, consistent with the patterns identified in Q4, are more socially acceptable for women and should be explicitly included in contract requirements.

In camps, IBV-defined work-types are already among the more socially acceptable options for women. The more pressing gap is in supervision. IBV frameworks already define team leader and site supervisor roles with fixed skill classifications and pay scales (BNLWG, 2020, Annex 1). Allocating a minimum proportion of those positions to women is therefore a staffing decision within the programme manager's existing remit, not a regulatory one. The survey indicates this option is underutilised. It does not establish that increasing female supervision independently improves participation rates, but the compounding situation in camps makes it a necessary step regardless.

In camps specifically, the combination of public worksite exposure, limited availability of female supervisors, and a high reliance on mixed-gender teams cannot be resolved through individual fixes. Any camp programme running mixed-gender teams in public spaces without female supervisors should be required to document the full safety management package as a combined record: the code of conduct, the complaint channel, and supervisory protocols together, not as separate checklist items. The safeguard then becomes visible and trackable rather than assumed. The corresponding programme-level actions are set out as R2.1-R2.4 in Appendix D, Table 29.

5.2.3 Time, Transport, and Childcare

In host-community programmes, a fixed morning-only schedule not exceeding six hours should be formalised as the programme default. The approach is already dominant, reported by 81% of programmes (Q7). Elevating it to an explicit standard closes the time-design gap that camp SOPs already address, while preserving the flexible shift option in camp settings where SOP governance supports it.

Transport support and worksite proximity address the same underlying barrier: the distance between where women live and where they work. They should be assessed together at the programme design stage, not treated as separate decisions. When worksites are located close to women's homes, transport costs and safety concerns are reduced. Where proximity is constrained by site availability or land use, particularly in camps where proximity feasibility was rated at M=2.00 (Q18), transport support becomes the more important lever. Both measures were rated as highly effective for completion and dropout reduction in Q19, and transport was rated as highly feasible when implemented (M=4.20, Q18). In practice, this means prioritising site selection that minimises distance where proximity is achievable, and building transport support into the programme budget as a standard line item where it is not. Recording the proportion of target women living within walking distance of proposed worksites, and the transport options available to the remainder, would make proximity a trackable design criterion rather than a chance outcome. This is a proposed monitoring improvement rather than a practice the survey directly measures.

Childcare provision sits at the intersection of programme design and policy. In camps, where some programmes already provide childcare, agencies should document existing approaches and work toward shared minimum standards. In host-community programmes, small and concrete steps are possible even where infrastructure is limited: partnering with local childcare providers, offering modest allowances, or creating childcare spaces near worksites. One programme-operable option worth piloting, though it goes beyond the survey findings, is engaging women as caregivers under CfW contracts near worksites. It would simultaneously address childcare provision and create an additional socially acceptable work-type. It has not yet been documented as a tested model in the Jordanian context and would require careful design and monitoring before wider adoption. Broader policy investment in childcare infrastructure remains essential alongside these programme-level steps, as established in Chapter 2. The corresponding programme-level actions are set out as R3.1-R3.7 in Appendix D, Table 29.

5.2.4 Worksite Conditions, Safety, and Protection

Onboarding and safety briefings should be explicitly recorded and monitored in both camps and host-community programmes. In practice, monthly reporting formats should include a separate onboarding item, and in camp settings, SOP compliance on this point should be explicitly checked rather than assumed.

Private rest and prayer space was the least consistently provided worksite feature, reported by only 52% of programmes (Q11). It should be integrated into minimum SOP standards and host communities' contracts, supporting women's ability to remain on site throughout the working day without compromising dignity or religious practice.

Gender-sensitive facilities received the highest perceived effectiveness rating of any measure in the sample (M=4.41, n=22, Q20). The provision gap for its weakest component, private rest and prayer

space, is not a budget or infrastructure constraint. It is an operational and procurement decision. Implementing agencies should include gender-sensitive facility standards as a minimum site requirement in all worksite assessments and procurement contracts across both settings, not as optional additions. The corresponding programme-level actions are set out as R4.1-R4.5 in Appendix D, Table 29.

5.2.5 Payment Modality and Financial Control

In camp programmes, mobile wallet adoption should be accompanied by deliberate steps to ensure women's effective control over their wages. At enrolment, mobile wallet accounts should be verified as registered in women's own names where possible. Basic digital payment training should be provided, and alternatives, specifically cash or prepaid card payments, should be available to any woman who requests them for safety or control reasons, without requiring justification. RAIS can support this by systematically recording account ownership details at registration.

Timely payment should be a key performance indicator in all programmes. Contracts and SOPs should specify clear payment frequency expectations and include corrective measures for persistent delays. In camps, where all payments are digital, linking timeliness checks to existing recording systems is a straightforward way to operationalise this. The corresponding programme-level actions are set out as R5.1-R5.5 in Appendix D, Table 29.

5.2.6 Monitoring

Programmes should adopt pipeline-stage tracking as a standard part of monitoring. Programmes should record and review the number and percentage of women applicants, women selected, women who start work, women who complete the full cycle, and women who exit early, with categorised reasons for doing so. Programme managers should be expected to know and report these figures as a basic part of their role, rather than entirely delegating visibility into participation outcomes to MEAL staff. Programmes should also record how many eligible women are excluded at the documentation phase, treating this as a routine indicator of the strength of the barrier rather than an administrative side-effect.

These requirements are operationalised in a 16-indicator pipeline-stage monitoring framework, derived from the barrier and constraint patterns identified in this study. The framework is organised into three categories (entry, completion, and enabling conditions) and constitutes a core study output. Together, these indicators address both the data-collection gap (fewer than half of programmes tracked women applicants or starters, Q14) and the data-circulation gap (27% of programme managers could not report their own programme's target or achieved rate, Q21). Indicators 1–3 and 16 are the most critical for closing the feedback mechanism identified in Section 5.1.6; they are also the ones most consistently absent from current programme monitoring in this sample.

Entry Stage

1. **Women applicants** (n and % of women who applied per recruitment round).
2. **Women excluded at the documentation phase** (n recorded as ineligible due to documentation gaps per recruitment round; collected from field officer records or RAIS where accessible).
3. **Outreach quality checklist** (Criteria met out of 7: women-accessible channel used; at least 14 days' notice given; worksite location and hours stated; team composition stated; female supervisor availability stated; transport or childcare stated if available; non-digital channel included).
4. **Selection mechanism type** (Type recorded per round: scoring, quota, committee, first-come-first-served, or lottery).

Completion Stage

5. **Women starters** (n and % of selected women who began work).
6. **Women completers** (n and % of starters completing the full cycle).
7. **Dropout / early exit - categorised reasons** (n per category: household opposition; care responsibilities; transport or safety; worksite conditions; payment; health; other (open text field)).

Enabling Conditions

8. **Worksite proximity at site selection** (% of target women living within walking distance of the proposed worksite, recorded before the programme begins; used to document whether proximity was applied as a design criterion rather than left to chance).
9. **Transport and proximity - assessed together.** (a) Yes/no: Worksite proximity measures were applied. (b) Reasons categorised for non-application to worksite proximity within workers' walking distance; (c) transport type and % participants covered.
10. **Direct payment into women's own account** (Yes/no at enrolment: account registered in a woman's name with no third-party intermediary, Yes/no at enrolment: payment is requested in cash, no justification required).
11. **Payment timeliness** (Days from work completion to payment; flagged if exceeding the contractual deadline).
12. **Gender-sensitive worksite checklist** (Monthly per worksite: separate toilets; private rest and prayer space; drinking water; PPE appropriate for women; onboarding briefing recorded; complaint mechanism operational).
13. **Female supervisor in place** (Yes/no per worksite. If no: safety package documented as a combined record covering code of conduct, induction, and grievance channel activation)
14. **Childcare - type and coverage** (Type and % of participants with dependents who accessed childcare support).
15. **Grievances - type, resolution, and preventive action** (n per category; resolution status; days to response; preventive measures identified, if any).
16. **Internal monitoring of knowledge circulation** ((a) MEAL summary shared with field officers

and managers: yes/no; (b) field officer dropout checklists submitted to MEAL: yes/no; (c) prior-cycle findings presented at programme kick-off meeting: yes/no).

Closing the intra-organisational monitoring knowledge gap identified in Section 5.1.6 requires routine internal communication structures alongside this indicator set: monitoring summaries shared across roles before each implementation cycle begins, and attendance and dropout logs maintained by field officers that feed directly into central MEAL systems. These structural mechanisms are what translate data collection into the design decisions the data is meant to inform.

The indicators above are not equally urgent across all settings. Full measurement specifications, priority classifications, and setting-specific differentiation are provided in Appendix C, Tables 27 and 28.

The full set of recommendations, mapped by domain, delivery setting, feasibility classification, responsible actor, and programme cycle stage, is provided in Appendix D, Table 29, as a practitioner-ready reference. Of the 36 recommendations, 34 are classified as programme-operable within a single cycle. Two are policy-dependent and require action at the institutional or government level beyond the individual programme.

6. Conclusion

6.1 Answer to the Research Question

The research question asked which CfW design features are associated with higher women's uptake and completion in Jordan, and how feasible these features are under current regulatory and delivery constraints.

Design features associated with uptake and completion

At the entry stage, targeted outreach through women-accessible channels and women's quotas were most consistently associated with higher uptake. Targeted outreach produced positive signals across all four participation indicators in Q19. At the completion stage, worksite proximity was the most widely selected lever (70%, Q15), with dropout-reduction signals of $M=4.00$ in Q19. However, its distribution across programmes reflected site availability and programme geography rather than deliberate design decisions, meaning the most valued completion lever is not yet being actively managed as one. Transport support produced the strongest completion and dropout-reduction signals of any implemented measure (both $M=4.25$, Q19), yet remained absent from 61% of programmes. On feasibility, proximity and work-type adaptation, the two most valued completion levers, were also the two rated most difficult to implement ($M=2.44$ and $M=2.55$ respectively, Q18), while targeted outreach and women's quotas sat firmly in the feasible range ($M=3.70$ and $M=3.91$). Women's participation is therefore not associated with any single design decision but with a chain of conditions that must be addressed at both pipeline stages, under setting-specific constraints that govern which measures are actionable within a single programme cycle.

Barriers at the entry stage

At the entry stage, the most consistently reported barriers were household consent and social norms. Documentation requirements were most consistently associated with suppressed entry-stage participation before any selection decision was made, particularly in host-community programmes where targeted outreach was also insufficient. Only 39% of programmes applied any proactive mechanism to identify women at risk of exclusion before selection, a rate consistently low across all delivery settings (Q2). Most programmes focused on inclusion measures while leaving upstream exclusion risks unaddressed. In camps, the barrier profile is further compounded by selection mechanisms, specifically FCFS and committee-based decisions, which tend to disadvantage women facing the heaviest documentation and mobility constraints.

Documentation barriers across settings

Documentation barriers operate differently across settings. In camps, the RAIS eligibility stack screens women out before selection begins. In host communities, the requirement for formal work permits places most Syrian refugee women outside the eligible pool before any recruitment decision is made. Both-settings programmes, operating simultaneously under IBV SOPs and work-permit requirements, indicated the largest participation gap of any setting (mean -15.0 percentage points, Q21), consistent with the overhead of managing two regulatory frameworks within a single programme cycle. Camp programmes, which on average met or exceeded their participation targets by 3.6 percentage points (Q21), should not be read as evidence of good programme design. Targets in camp settings may be calibrated to what is already achievable under constrained choice conditions, and over-achievement against a low benchmark does not resolve the design gaps identified across those same programmes.

Infrastructure without follow-through

In the payment domain, a parallel infrastructure-without-follow-through pattern emerged: all camp programmes used mobile wallets, yet only 56% reported making direct payments into women's own accounts, indicating that digitalisation alone does not automatically secure women's financial control over wages. In the monitoring domain, 27% of programme managers could not report their programme's participation target or achieved rate, indicating a breakdown in the feedback mechanism that should link monitoring evidence to design decisions. The problem is one of data circulation and utilisation, not only data collection.

Governance frameworks and their limits

Across the work design, payment, and monitoring domains, a further pattern emerged that the governance architecture alone does not predict. Camp programmes, operating under the most structured governance framework, showed the lowest rates of female supervisors, the widest gap between mobile wallet use and direct payments to women, and lower onboarding briefing rates than host-community programmes, despite SOP requirements. Where female supervisors are

unavailable, the gap cannot simply be noted and left to the programme manager's discretion. The compounding of low supervision, public worksite exposure, and mixed-gender teams in camp settings points to the need for a defined compensating package, covering codes of conduct, gender-sensitive induction, and grievance channel activation, triggered by the absence of female supervision rather than assembled ad hoc. Governance frameworks set the conditions for better design. They do not guarantee it.

The minimum viable package

Taken together, the domain-by-domain findings point to six programme-operable measures, one per domain, rated as feasible within a single delivery cycle without regulatory reform, constituting the minimum viable package derived from this study (Section 5.1.7).

6.2 Contribution of the Study

This study makes five specific contributions to the existing literature.

Monitoring as a circulation problem, not only a collection problem

Earlier literature describes monitoring failures mainly as system-level problems: missing gender-sensitive indicators or insufficient disaggregation across the sector (DEval, 2021, pp. 8-9; ILO, 2024, pp. 47-50). This study documents a second, prior problem: even when data are collected, they do not consistently reach the staff who make design and budget decisions, as documented in Section 5.1.6. While the broader monitoring-and-evaluation literature recognises evidence-to-decision gaps in general, the CfW evaluations reviewed for this study do not identify this monitoring-to-decision feedback failure as a distinct obstacle to women's participation.

Digital payments and financial control

The existing literature warned that mobile wallet infrastructure does not automatically secure women's control over wages (GIZ, 2022, p. 28; ILO, 2021, p. 27). This study indicates that, in the Jordanian context, camp programmes fully adopted digital payments, yet direct payments into women's own accounts were reported at a substantially lower rate. The gap between digital infrastructure and women's actual financial control is measurable in this sample, and programme design can address it through enrolment checks, account verification, and staff guidance, without waiting for broader financial-sector reform.

The effectiveness-feasibility tension

The measures practitioners selected most often as completion levers, worksite proximity and work-type adaptation, were also rated as most difficult to implement. Guidance documents classify these as controllable design variables (ILO, 2022; ILO, 2024). The survey indicates that practitioners working in Syrian refugee camps and host-community settings experience significant constraints due to geography, regulatory frameworks, and available task portfolios. Grounding this tension in practitioner-level ratings rather than conceptual claims distinguishes this study from earlier evaluations.

Future design guidance needs to distinguish between measures that are both valued and deliverable within a single cycle, and measures that require structural conditions that programmes cannot create on their own.

Where earlier recommendations have and have not translated into practice

Because the survey was conducted in 2026 and the key evaluations and governance documents reviewed in Chapter 2 predate it, the study documents where earlier recommendations have translated into changed practice and where they have not. Digital payments and women's quotas appear largely institutionalised in camp settings, whereas transport support, entry-stage monitoring, and childcare have remained structurally weak despite repeated attention in the literature. This temporal dimension is not available to studies relying solely on earlier evaluation data and constitutes a distinct contribution to the field.

The structural double-bind in camp selection

FCFS and committee-based decisions were found to coexist exclusively in camp settings, which have high documentation barriers and household consent constraints. Previous evaluations have assessed selection mechanisms individually and have not identified this combination as a structural double-bind. Linking it to the documented barrier profile of the most constrained applicants provides a concrete basis for SOP-level revisions to selection rules.

Both-settings programmes as a distinct operational category

Previous evaluations of CfW in Jordan compare camp and host-community programmes as separate categories but do not examine programmes operating simultaneously across both regulatory frameworks. This study identifies both-settings programmes as a structurally distinct group, showing the largest participation gap of any setting (mean -15.0 percentage points, n=7; median -10.0; see Section 4.10, Q21), the highest rates of unknown participation figures (36% of both-settings respondents unable to report their own target or actual rate, compared with 27% of programme managers across the full sample), and the greatest staff and time constraints (45.5%, Q17). Differentiated planning guidance for this operational category is absent from the evaluated CfW literature.

Together, these six contributions move the field's understanding of gender-inclusive CfW design from system-level barrier identification to organisation-level implementation analysis, from knowing that barriers exist to locating where, for whom, and under whose operational authority they can be addressed.

Operationalisation

These contributions are operationalised at two levels. At the programme level, the 36 recommendations offer implementing partners a design-ready, setting-differentiated pathway to address the persistent gap between CfW's theorised double dividend and its realised outcomes for women, providing the operational specificity that evaluators have found absent in current practice (ILO, 2024, p.

45). At the policy level, the classification of recommendations into programme-operable and policy-dependent categories gives donors and government counterparts a structured basis for prioritising reform, acknowledging that the barriers most constraining women's participation, work-permit access and national childcare infrastructure lie beyond what any single programme cycle can resolve (Loewe et al., 2020, p. 107-108).

Across all six contributions, the minimum viable package in Section 5.1.7 is the most directly actionable output: six measures, one per domain, each with a documented feasibility rating, selection rationale, and setting differentiation, offering practitioners a starting point that requires no regulatory reform to implement.

6.3 Objectives Revisited

Objective 1 was met. The survey produced setting-disaggregated barrier profiles across all six design domains, organised around the two pipeline stages and covering both entry and completion phases of women's participation.

Objective 2 was met. Chapters 4 and 5 present practitioner-rated effectiveness rankings for all design levers, disaggregated by delivery setting and respondent role, alongside a feasibility matrix that distinguishes measures implementers consider operational within a single programme cycle from those they rate as structurally constrained.

Objective 3 was met through a benchmarking approach. Current CfW design and monitoring practices were measured against evaluation-level recommendations from ILO, DEval, and UN Women, the closest available reference standard, with Q14 specifically measuring the monitoring gap. The absence of a standardised Jordan-specific benchmark is a finding in its own right. The pipeline-stage indicator framework in Appendix C addresses that absence through a prospective benchmarking approach, establishing minimum measurable standards derived from practitioner-confirmed feasibility thresholds. The 36 recommendations in Appendix D translate the identified gaps into programme-operable and policy-dependent actions.

Objective 4 was met. Appendix C, derived from section 5.2, sets out 36 recommendations across six design domains, each specifying whether it can be implemented within a single programme cycle through procurement, staffing, and routine contracts, or whether it depends on wider system change. Of the 36, 34 are programme-operable, and two are policy-dependent. The full set is consolidated in Appendix D, Table 29, mapped by domain, delivery setting, feasibility classification, responsible actor, and programme cycle stage.

Objective 5 was met. Section 5.2 sets out a 16-indicator pipeline-stage monitoring framework, organised by stage, priority level, and delivery setting, grounded in the specific gaps identified in this survey. The indicators have not been tested or validated in practice during this study, and their workability across different programme contexts remains to be confirmed by future implementation and research.

6.4 Limitations

The 23 practitioners in this sample, programme managers, field officers, MEAL staff, and safeguarding professionals, were drawn purposively from across Jordan's CfW delivery landscape, spanning both camp and host-community settings. No central registry of CfW implementers exists, so statistical generalisability is not claimed. The sample's strength is the specificity and direct operational experience of its respondents, not its size. They cover the full programme cycle and operate across two structurally distinct regulatory frameworks within the same country, a combination a larger but less targeted sample would not reliably capture. Findings are interpreted as exploratory patterns. The host communities subgroup (n=3) is the most analytically constrained and is treated as indicative throughout.

The researcher's professional background in GIZ Jordan may have biased the network toward better-resourced implementing organisations familiar with SOP-based delivery.

All data are self-reported. The intra-organisational monitoring knowledge gap identified in Section 5.1.6 raises a concern: respondents may describe their programme's documentation rather than actual practice. Findings reflect practitioners' statements, not independently verified work. The risk is highest in worksite conditions regarding harassment prevention, grievance mechanisms, and codes of conduct, which face social desirability pressures; reporting non-provision in these areas carries professional and reputational costs.

The study collected no data from women participants. It cannot test whether practitioners' perceptions of barriers align with women's own experiences, or whether higher participation rates translated into meaningful change in women's working lives. This is not a minor caveat. It is the study's most important structural limitation, and it defines the primary direction for future research.

The cross-sectional design means all associations between design features and outcomes are correlational; no causal conclusions can be drawn. The findings are anchored in Jordan's specific regulatory conditions in 2026. If IBV rules, work-permit frameworks, childcare provision, or digital financial inclusion change materially, some feasibility assessments will need to be revised.

6.5 Directions for Future Research

6.5.1 Empirical Research Priorities

The most important direction is to place women participants at the centre. This study documents what practitioners believe works. It cannot show whether women agree, which barriers feel most binding to them, or how design changes affect their daily experience of CfW work. Answering the research question fully requires women's own voices alongside implementer perceptions, not as supplementary data but as primary evidence. A mixed-methods study combining a structured beneficiary survey with focus group discussions across both delivery settings would provide that evidence base.

A second direction concerns the camp selection environment. FCFS and committee-based decisions were found to coexist exclusively in camps, the same setting with the heaviest documentation and household consent barriers. A study using RAIS administrative data linked to household and demographic information could test whether these mechanisms produce gender-differentiated exclusion in practice, and whether alternative selection tools generate more equitable entry profiles.

Third, the intra-organisational monitoring knowledge gap identified in Section 5.1.6 warrants investigation as a standalone organisational question. This study provides initial quantitative evidence of the gap but does not explain its organisational origins. Future research examining information flows within implementing organisations, through process mapping, document analysis, and staff interviews, could identify the conditions that make field staff more or less likely to access and use monitoring data in day-to-day implementation.

Fourth, comparative research across displacement contexts would test whether the two-stage pipeline framework and the design levers identified here hold beyond Jordan. Jordan's CfW landscape is shaped by camp-specific governance structures, developed SOP frameworks, and a particular combination of donor, government, and UN actors. Applying a similar design-focused, pipeline-based lens in Lebanon, Uganda, or comparable displacement settings could distinguish context-specific features from consistent participation levers, and support organisations working across multiple countries in aligning gender-responsive design guidance with diverse implementation evidence.

Fifth, childcare as a CfW design element deserves a dedicated study. This study identifies it as the most consistently recognised missing element in the sample and raises the possibility of designing childcare as a CfW activity itself, with women employed as caregivers in women-only teams near worksites. A focused evaluation of programmes that have experimented with co-located childcare could assess whether this model improves participation and completion, what it requires to scale, and what it means for the caregivers it employs alongside the participants it is meant to retain.

Sixth, the proximity paradox identified in Section 5.1.3 warrants investigation. Worksite proximity was the completion lever most valued by practitioners, yet its distribution across programmes was determined by site availability rather than by deliberate design decisions. A study examining how site selection is made and documented in CfW programme planning, and whether proximity criteria are formally applied before implementation begins, would test whether this is a design blind spot or a structural constraint. That distinction has direct implications for what implementing agencies can realistically be held accountable for.

Seventh, camp settings' consistent target over-achievement alongside documented design gaps raises a question that has not been examined: whether current participation targets function as genuine accountability benchmarks or as baselines calibrated to what is already achievable. A dedicated study of target-setting methodology and its relationship to actual programme ambition would provide the evidence needed to distinguish between the two.

Eighth, the large-scale return of Syrian refugees to Syria since late 2025 reduced the registered refugee population in Jordan from over 650,000 to under 400,000 by April 2026 (UNHCR, 2025a; UNHCR, 2026) and will reshape the demand profile, target-setting logic, and institutional justification for CfW programming in Jordan. Future research should examine whether programme design assumptions calibrated for a larger, more stable refugee population remain valid under a rapidly declining one, and whether the design features identified in this study retain their relevance as the balance between refugee and host communities participants shifts.

6.5.2 Policy and Operational Implications

The most fundamental question for the field is: what is CfW for? These programmes sit uneasily between emergency response and development investment. When framed as emergency tools, their short cycles and temporary income logic are accepted without scrutiny. When framed as development investments, claims of sustained impact are made that the evidence does not consistently support. Community norm training and gender dialogues are genuinely important, but they are preparatory investments rather than development outcomes. They create a more receptive baseline. They do not create jobs. Even where community attitudes improve and programme design is optimised, Syrian women in Jordan face a regulatory ceiling that programme design cannot lift: work-permit restrictions confined to specific sectors, and a formal labour market where even Jordanian women without displacement-related barriers face 33.9% unemployment. Programmes that claim to build pathways to formal employment without confronting these structural conditions are making promises the design cannot keep. The question is not only how to design CfW better. It is how CfW connects, or fails to connect, to the broader architecture of economic opportunity that would make participation in it mean something beyond the duration of the cycle.

Donors and lead agencies negotiating programme frameworks with host governments must treat regulatory reform as a precondition of funding, not an afterthought. Work-permit restrictions, RAIS eligibility requirements, and the structural gap between IBV's volunteering classification and formal employment rights are all documented here and in preceding evaluations. Before committing to another programme cycle, donors should require evidence that the regulatory environment will not systematically undermine the programme's own gender objectives, and use the leverage they hold through policy dialogue, Jordan Compact mechanisms, and coordinated advocacy to shift conditions that individual programme teams cannot move on their own.

Implementing agencies should examine what they could accomplish together that they cannot accomplish alone. The larger opportunities remain unrealised: a jointly funded childcare facility serving multiple programmes in the same community; a shared government dialogue on regulatory reform; and institutionalised cross-programme knowledge systems that preserve what field teams learn about dropout reduction rather than losing it at programme closure. Coordination between implementing agencies is not a logistical preference. It is a design obligation, and treating it any differently is a choice with consequences for the women these programmes are meant to serve.

6.6 Closing Statement

Women's participation in CfW programmes is consistently framed as a target: a percentage to report, a threshold to meet, a box to tick for donor compliance. This study shows what that framing produces. Programmes tracked who was selected and who completed, but fewer than half tracked who applied or who actually started work. The entry stage, where most exclusions occur, remained largely invisible in monitoring systems. Donors who accept headcount percentages as evidence of gender inclusion are, in effect, incentivising implementers to get women through the door rather than to understand and address why they are not coming through it at all. Meaningful accountability requires indicators that cover the full participation pipeline, not just its final output. The 16-indicator framework proposed in this study addresses that gap. But frameworks change nothing if donors do not require them, if implementers do not use them to identify failures, and if the language of inclusion remains a reporting exercise rather than a design discipline. Baseline studies matter, but they are a starting point. Continuous monitoring of who applies, who drops out, and why, is what turns the baseline into evidence that changes programme design.

This study began with a straightforward question: which programme design features are associated with higher women's participation in CfW in Jordan, and how feasible are they under current constraints? The answer is not simple, but it is clear. The features that matter most are known: proximity, transport support, targeted outreach, and direct financial control. They are not discoveries. They appear in evaluations from 2018, 2020, 2021, and 2024. The problem is not knowledge. The problem is a system of incentives that rewards counting women over understanding their participation, that accepts infrastructure without accountability for outcomes, and that funds programme cycles without asking whether the regulatory, labour market, and social conditions surrounding those cycles allow the stated objectives to be achieved.

CfW provides a dignified work environment for women, helping them avoid informal labour with worse conditions. It can influence household and community norms over time with careful design and honest monitoring. However, it cannot replace the necessary reforms, investments, and structural changes on which it depends. Viewing it as a standalone solution risks turning promising programmes into cycles with limited impact.

The practitioners who responded to this survey are working within that system. They make real decisions, within real constraints, that determine whether women enter and stay in programmes. This study was built on their knowledge. Its recommendations are addressed to them, their organisations, and the donors and policy bodies that shape the conditions in which they work. The women this study could not directly reach, whose experiences, barriers, and choices remain the most important evidence not yet collected, are the reason the obligation exists at all. The obligation is shared. What suffices is a committed, coordinated, honest effort by implementers, donors, government counterparts, and the private sector to build the conditions under which women's participation in these programmes means something beyond the duration of the cycle that funded it.

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The following appendices provide supplementary material referenced in the main body of the thesis. Each appendix is identified by a letter and referred to at the relevant point in the text.

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Appendix A: Survey Instrument: Cash-for-Work (CfW) Programme Design and Women's Uptake and Completion in Jordan

Platform: Qualtrics Online Survey | Administration period: 27.2.2026-15.03.2026 | n=23 valid responses

INTRODUCTION AND CONSENT

Dear participant,

This anonymous survey is part of a master's thesis at IU Internationale Hochschule GmbH (IU). It asks about your professional experience with Cash-for-Work (CfW) programmes in Jordan to understand which programme design features are associated with higher women's uptake and completion, and how feasible these features are under current regulatory and delivery constraints.

Please answer only if you have been involved in planning, implementing, supervising, safeguarding, or monitoring/reporting a CfW programme in Jordan within the last 60 months. If you know colleagues who meet this criterion, you are welcome to forward the survey link to them.

How to answer: Please respond about one specific CfW programme or one phase you know best. If you do not have visibility on an item, select 'Don't know' where available.

Time required: 8–12 minutes.

Confidentiality/anonymity: Your name is not requested, and responses are anonymous. Please do not include any information that could identify you or others.

Voluntary participation: Participation is voluntary. You may stop at any time by closing the survey. By selecting 'Yes' on the consent question and continuing, you consent to participate.

IU does not receive any personal data about you. For questions, contact the student researcher:

Name: Nora Borini | Email: nora.borini@iu-study.org

Key definitions

Women's uptake: women entering the programme pipeline (e.g., women applying/selected/starting work).

Women's completion: women completing the full work cycle/contract as defined by the programme.

Women's dropout: women not completing the full work cycle after starting work.

Measures/Levers: design or operational features intended to improve women's uptake and/or completion (e.g., childcare, transport support, women-only teams).

CONSENT I have read the information above and consent to participate.

Yes

No

→ If No → End of Survey

SECTION A - BACKGROUND: RESPONDENT ROLE AND DELIVERY CONTEXT

a Have you been directly involved in planning/implementing a CfW programme in Jordan in the last 60 months?

Yes

No

→ If No → End of Survey

b Select the option that best matches your main role for the programme/phase you are answering about.

Programme manager/coordinator - direct delivery/management

Field officer/supervisor/contractor supervisor - direct implementation

MEAL staff/data staff - monitoring, data management, reporting (not direct delivery)

Safeguarding/protection - case management/complaints

Donor/ministry/municipality - oversight/coordination

Limited involvement / not enough information

→ If "Limited involvement" → End of Survey

c Which population(s) did the CfW programme primarily target?

Jordanians only

Syrians only

Mixed Jordanians and Syrians

d Main CfW delivery setting(s)?

Host communities

Refugee camp

Both

e Does your organisation report CfW programme activities publicly (evaluation reports/annual reports/donor reports)?

Yes

No

f What is the typical work cycle length in days? (If more than one model, select all that apply most of the time.)

≤ 10 days

11–20 days

21–40 days

41–60 days

61–90 days

> 90 days

SECTION B - CFW RECRUITMENT, OUTREACH, AND SELECTION (Programme Entry)

Q1 For the statements below, please answer based on your overall judgement for the programme/phase you are referring to.

	Strongly agree	Somewhat agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat disagree	Strongly disagree
Outreach channels reached women effectively (community leaders, women's groups, local networks).					
Recruitment information was accessible to women (timing, location, language, clarity).					
The selection criteria were clear to applicants.					
Documentation/eligibility requirements created barriers for women.					
Household-level consent/gender role norms reduced women's ability to apply.					
A complicated registration process reduced women's ability to apply.					

CfW application location/hours reduced women's ability to apply.					
Women perceived the recruitment process as fair and transparent.					

Q2 Please select all that apply most of the time from your programme/phase practices.

- The programme used specific measures to increase women applicants (e.g., targeted messaging, women-focused sessions).
- The programme used targets/quotas for women in selection.
- The programme had a process for identifying and addressing women's exclusion risks in selection.

Q3 Primary CfW selection mechanism. (If mixed, select all that apply.)

- Women's quotas
- First-come, first-served
- Scoring/vulnerability ranking
- Lottery
- Committee decision

SECTION C - WORK-TYPE, LOCATION, AND TEAM COMPOSITION (Design Features)

Q4 What was the main CfW work-type(s) offered to women? (Select a maximum of 3 most relevant to your programme.)

- Cleaning
- Solid waste management and recycling
- Greening/agriculture
- Community services
- Administrative/data tasks
- Care
- Light maintenance (e.g., painting, light refurbishment)
- Construction/heavy tasks
- Home-based or semi-skilled income activities (e.g., tailoring, food production)

Q5 What was the typical worksite exposure for women cash workers in your programme?

- Mostly public/open spaces
- Mostly semi-private (municipal or other entity facilities)
- Mostly indoor

Q6 In your programme (select all that apply):

- Work-type and worksite were culturally acceptable for most women in the target communities.
- Women-only teams were available.
- Mixed-gender teams were managed in a way that women considered acceptable and safe.
- Female supervisors/team leads were available when needed.

SECTION D - TIME, TRANSPORT, AND CHILDCARE

Q7 What was women's daily schedule pattern?

- Morning only - fixed
- Afternoon only - fixed
- Flexible shifts

Q8 Typical worksite assignment for women was:

- Within the same neighbourhood
- Same city
- Different city

Q9 What was the transport support provided?

- None
- Cash transport allowance
- Organised transport

Q10 What was the childcare support provided?

- None
- Onsite childcare
- Childcare allowance
- Referral/partner childcare

SECTION E - WORKSITE CONDITIONS, FACILITIES, SAFETY, AND PROTECTION

Q11 Select items and conditions that were available or applied most of the time at worksites where women worked. (Select all that apply.)

- Separate toilets were available
- Private rest/prayer space was available
- Drinking water was provided
- PPE was provided when task type required
- Supervision practices supported women's continued attendance (respectful treatment, practical handling of emergencies)
- Code of conduct communicated
- Onboarding/induction/safety briefing provided
- Harassment prevention measures in place and understood
- Confidential reporting channel usable by women
- Complaints handled in a timely manner

SECTION F - PAYMENT MODALITY AND FINANCIAL CONTROL

Q12 What was the payment method used for women? (If multiple, select all that apply.)

- Cash
- Iris recognition (EyePay)
- Mobile wallet
- Prepaid/debit card
- Bank transfer

Q13 Please select all that apply most of the time in the programme you are referring to.

- Wages for women and men were equal (equal pay for the same work).
- Wages were paid directly to women participants (not via household intermediaries).
- Wages were mostly paid on time.

SECTION G - MONITORING, KPIS, AND COMPLETION

Q14 Select items that are routinely recorded in your programme/phase (even if not publicly published). If you do not have visibility over what is recorded, select "I don't know". (Select all that apply.)

- % women among applicants
- % women among selected
- % women among starters (attended at least 1 day)
- % women among completers (completed full cycle)
- % women dropout
- Reasons for dropout (categorised)
- Worksite facility checklist (gender-sensitive)
- Grievances by type (categorised)
- Payment timeliness
- I don't know

SECTION H - PROGRAMME DESIGN LEVERS, EFFECTIVENESS, AND FEASIBILITY

Q15 Which implemented measures were most effective in improving women's completion (attending the full cycle)? (Select up to 3.)

- Work-type adapted to be acceptable for women
- Worksite proximity (assignment closer to home)
- Flexible schedule/shorter shifts
- Transport support
- Childcare support
- Women-only teams (where needed)
- Female supervisor/team lead (where needed)
- Gender-sensitive facilities (toilets/water/privacy space)
- Code of conduct + induction/safety briefing
- Confidential grievance channel usable by women
- Payment directly to women (modality)

- Payment timeliness improvements
- Gender guidance/training for supervisors/contractors
- Attendance rules adapted for emergencies

Q16 Which implemented measures actually achieved higher women's participation overall (uptake and completion)? (Select up to 3.)

- Targeted outreach to women
- Women's targets/quotas
- Selection/registration adjustments (documentation, location/hours)
- Work-type adapted to be acceptable for women
- Worksite proximity (assignment closer to home)
- Flexible schedule/shorter shifts
- Transport support
- Childcare support
- Women-only teams (where needed)
- Female supervisor/team lead (where needed)
- Gender-sensitive facilities (toilets/water/privacy space)
- Code of conduct + induction/safety briefing
- Confidential grievance channel usable by women
- Payment directly to women (modality)
- Payment timeliness improvements
- Gender guidance/training for supervisors/contractors
- Attendance rules adapted for emergencies

Q17 Which constraints most limit these measures' feasibility in your setting? (Select up to 3.)

- Budget limits
- Donor requirements/reporting format
- Government approvals/regulatory constraints

- Data protection/privacy restrictions
- Limited staffing/time
- Limited childcare options in the area
- Transport market/cost/safety constraints
- Worksite availability/location constraints
- Contractor capacity/behaviour
- Community norms/acceptance

Q18 How feasible are the following measures to implement within current budgets, regulations, and operational constraints? (Branching logic will only display measures selected in Q16 to rate.)

	Very difficult	Somewhat difficult	Neither	Somewhat feasible	Very feasible
Targeted outreach to women					
Women's targets/quotas					
Selection/registration adjustments (documentation, location/hours)					
Work-type adapted to be acceptable for women.					
Worksite proximity (assignment closer to home)					
Flexible schedule/shorter shifts					
Transport support					
Childcare support					
Women-only teams (where needed)					
Female supervisor/team lead (where needed)					
Gender-sensitive facilities (toilets/water/privacy space)					
Code of conduct + induction/safety briefing					
Confidential grievance channel usable by women					

Payment directly to women (modality)					
Payment timeliness improvements					
Gender guidance/training for supervisors/contractors					
Attendance rules adapted for emergencies.					

Q19 After the measures selected above were implemented, how would you rate the following outcomes?

	Much lower	Slightly lower	About the same	Slightly higher	Much higher
Women's uptake rate among applicants					
Women's completion rate among starters					
Women's dropout rate					
Women's overall participation rate					

Q20 Based on your overall judgement, observation, or interaction with women workers, the following measures would increase women's overall participation (uptake/completion). (Branching logic will only display measures that were *NOT* selected in Q16 to rate.)

	Strongly agree	Some-what agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Some-what disagree	Strongly disagree	I don't know
Targeted outreach to women						
Women's targets/quotas						
Selection/registration adjustments (documentation, location/hours)						
Work-type adapted to be acceptable for women.						
Worksite proximity (assignment closer to home)						
Flexible schedule/shorter shifts						
Transport support						
Childcare support						
Women-only teams (where needed)						

Female supervisor/team lead (where needed)						
Gender-sensitive facilities (toilets/water/privacy space)						
Code of conduct + induction/safety briefing						
Confidential grievance channel usable by women						
Payment directly to women (modality)						
Payment timeliness improvements						
Gender guidance/training for supervisors/contractors						
Attendance rules adapted for emergencies.						

Q21 What is the programme's latest rate (%)? Enter a number from 0 to 100. If not known, select "I don't know."

Indicator	Value (0–100) / I don't know
% Women's targeted participation rate	
% Women's actual participation rate	

- End of Survey -

Thank you for your time and contribution to this research.

Appendix B: Full Survey Results by Delivery Setting and Respondent Role (when applied).

Tab. 12 Q1 - Perceptions of the recruitment process, by setting and role (Mean, 1–5 Likert scale) (n=23)

Item	Overall (n=23)	By Delivery Setting			By Respondent Role			
		Both (n=11)	Camp (n=9)	Host Comm. (n=3)	PM/Coord. (n=11)	Field Off. (n=7)	MEAL (n=4)	Safeg. (n=1)
Outreach reached women effectively	4.17	4.09	4.67	3.00	4.27	4.14	3.75	5.00
Recruitment information accessible to women	4.48	4.45	4.44	4.67	4.64	4.43	4.25	4.00
The selection criteria are clear to applicants	4.22	4.27	4.00	4.67	4.45	4.29	3.50	4.00
Recruitment perceived as fair and transparent	4.04	4.09	4.11	3.67	4.27	3.86	3.50	5.00
Documentation requirements (barrier, rev.)	2.70	3.45	2.11	1.67	2.64	2.29	4.00	1.00
Registration complexity (barrier, rev.)	2.83	3.36	2.11	3.00	2.45	3.29	3.50	1.00
Application time/location (barrier, rev.)	2.91	3.27	2.78	2.00	3.09	3.29	2.25	1.00
Household consent/gender norms (barrier, rev.)	2.48	3.00	1.89	2.33	2.45	2.43	3.00	1.00

Source: Own representation.

Tab. 13 Q4 - Work-types offered to women - frequency by delivery setting, multiple selection (n=23)

Item	Overall (n=23)	By Delivery Setting		
		Both (n=11)	Camp (n=9)	Host Comm. (n=3)
Cleaning	15 (65%)	6 (55%)	7 (78%)	2 (67%)
Solid waste & recycling	12 (52%)	6 (55%)	4 (44%)	2 (67%)
Greening/agriculture	8 (35%)	6 (55%)	0 (0%)	2 (67%)
Community services	6 (26%)	1 (9%)	4 (44%)	1 (33%)
Administrative & data tasks	9 (39%)	6 (55%)	2 (22%)	1 (33%)
Care work	2 (9%)	0 (0%)	2 (22%)	0 (0%)
Light maintenance	1 (4%)	1 (9%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Construction / heavy tasks	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Home-based / semi-skilled	3 (13%)	2 (18%)	1 (11%)	0 (0%)

Source: Own representation.

Tab. 14 Q11 - Worksite conditions, facilities, safety and protection, frequency by delivery setting, multiple selection (n=23)

Item	Overall (n=23)	By Delivery Setting		
		Both (n=11)	Camp (n=9)	Host Comm. (n=3)
Separate toilets available	17 (74%)	8 (73%)	6 (67%)	3 (100%)
Private rest/prayer space available	12 (52%)	4 (36%)	6 (67%)	2 (67%)
Drinking water provided	16 (70%)	9 (82%)	5 (56%)	2 (67%)
PPE provided (when task type required)	20 (87%)	10 (91%)	7 (78%)	3 (100%)
Supervision practices supported attendance	17 (74%)	8 (73%)	6 (67%)	3 (100%)
Code of conduct communicated	17 (74%)	8 (73%)	6 (67%)	3 (100%)
Onboarding/safety briefing provided	18 (78%)	10 (91%)	5 (56%)	3 (100%)
Harassment prevention measures are in place	17 (74%)	9 (82%)	6 (67%)	2 (67%)
Confidential reporting channel available	18 (78%)	10 (91%)	6 (67%)	2 (67%)
Complaints handled in a timely manner	18 (78%)	10 (91%)	6 (67%)	2 (67%)

Source: Own representation.

Tab. 15 Q14 -Monitoring items routinely recorded, frequency by setting and role, multiple selection (n=23)

Item	Overall (n=23)	By Delivery Setting			By Respondent Role			
		Both (n=11)	Camp (n=9)	Host Comm. (n=3)	PM/Coord. (n=11)	Field Off. (n=7)	MEAL (n=4)	Safeg. (n=1)
% women among applicants	10 (43%)	5 (45%)	4 (44%)	1 (33%)	5 (45%)	2 (29%)	3 (75%)	0 (0%)
% women among selected	19 (83%)	9 (82%)	7 (78%)	3 (100%)	8 (73%)	6 (86%)	4 (100%)	1 (100%)
% women among starters	9 (39%)	5 (45%)	3 (33%)	1 (33%)	4 (36%)	2 (29%)	3 (75%)	0 (0%)
% women among completers	17 (74%)	7 (64%)	7 (78%)	3 (100%)	9 (82%)	4 (57%)	3 (75%)	1 (100%)
% women dropout	16 (70%)	7 (64%)	7 (78%)	2 (67%)	7 (64%)	4 (57%)	4 (100%)	1 (100%)
Dropout reasons categorised	14 (61%)	7 (64%)	6 (67%)	1 (33%)	6 (55%)	4 (57%)	3 (75%)	1 (100%)
Gender-sensitive worksite checklist	6 (26%)	4 (36%)	2 (22%)	0 (0%)	4 (36%)	0 (0%)	2 (50%)	0 (0%)
Grievances by type categorised	6 (26%)	4 (36%)	2 (22%)	0 (0%)	3 (27%)	1 (14%)	2 (50%)	0 (0%)
Payment timeliness recorded	10 (43%)	5 (45%)	3 (33%)	2 (67%)	5 (45%)	2 (29%)	2 (50%)	1 (100%)
I don't know	2 (9%)	1 (9%)	1 (11%)	0 (0%)	1 (9%)	1 (14%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)

Source: Own representation.

Tab. 16 Q15 Measures most effective in improving women's completion, frequency by setting and role, multiple select up to 3 (n=23)

Item	Overall (n=23)	By Delivery Setting			By Respondent Role			
		Both (n=11)	Camp (n=9)	Host Comm. (n=3)	PM/Coord. (n=11)	Field Off. (n=7)	MEAL (n=4)	Safeg. (n=1)
Work-type adapted for women	12 (52%)	6 (55%)	4 (44%)	2 (67%)	6 (55%)	3 (43%)	2 (50%)	1 (100%)
Worksite proximity (closer to home)	16 (70%)	9 (82%)	6 (67%)	1 (33%)	7 (64%)	4 (57%)	4 (100%)	1 (100%)
Flexible schedule / shorter shifts	4 (17%)	1 (9%)	2 (22%)	1 (33%)	2 (18%)	0 (0%)	1 (25%)	1 (100%)
Transport support	7 (30%)	5 (45%)	1 (11%)	1 (33%)	1 (9%)	3 (43%)	3 (75%)	0 (0%)
Childcare support	2 (9%)	0 (0%)	2 (22%)	0 (0%)	2 (18%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Women-only teams	8 (35%)	3 (27%)	3 (33%)	2 (67%)	4 (36%)	3 (43%)	1 (25%)	0 (0%)
Female supervisor/team lead	3 (13%)	2 (18%)	0 (0%)	1 (33%)	2 (18%)	1 (14%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Gender-sensitive facilities	3 (13%)	1 (9%)	1 (11%)	1 (33%)	1 (9%)	2 (29%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Code of conduct & induction	2 (9%)	1 (9%)	1 (11%)	0 (0%)	2 (18%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Confidential grievance channel	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Direct payment to women	5 (22%)	3 (27%)	2 (22%)	0 (0%)	3 (27%)	1 (14%)	1 (25%)	0 (0%)
Payment timeliness improvements	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Gender guidance/training for supervisors	1 (4%)	0 (0%)	1 (11%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (14%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Emergency attendance rules	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)

Source: Own representation.

Tab. 17 Q16 Measures that achieved higher women's participation, frequency by setting and role, multiple select up to 3 (n=23)

Item	Overall (n=23)	By Delivery Setting			By Respondent Role			
		Both (n=11)	Camp (n=9)	Host Comm. (n=3)	PM/Coord. (n=11)	Field Off. (n=7)	MEAL (n=4)	Safeg. (n=1)
Targeted outreach to women	10 (43%)	7 (64%)	3 (33%)	0 (0%)	4 (36%)	2 (29%)	4 (100%)	0 (0%)
Women's quotas/targets	11 (48%)	6 (55%)	5 (56%)	0 (0%)	6 (55%)	4 (57%)	1 (25%)	0 (0%)
Selection/registration adjustments	3 (13%)	2 (18%)	1 (11%)	0 (0%)	2 (18%)	0 (0%)	1 (25%)	0 (0%)
Work-type adapted for women	11 (48%)	4 (36%)	5 (56%)	2 (67%)	4 (36%)	3 (43%)	3 (75%)	1 (100%)
Worksite proximity	9 (39%)	3 (27%)	4 (44%)	2 (67%)	4 (36%)	3 (43%)	1 (25%)	1 (100%)
Flexible schedule / shorter shifts	3 (13%)	0 (0%)	1 (11%)	2 (67%)	1 (9%)	1 (14%)	0 (0%)	1 (100%)
Transport support	5 (22%)	3 (27%)	1 (11%)	1 (33%)	1 (9%)	2 (29%)	2 (50%)	0 (0%)
Childcare support	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Women-only teams	3 (13%)	1 (9%)	1 (11%)	1 (33%)	3 (27%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Female supervisor/team lead	2 (9%)	2 (18%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (18%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Gender-sensitive facilities	1 (4%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (33%)	0 (0%)	1 (14%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Code of conduct & induction	2 (9%)	1 (9%)	1 (11%)	0 (0%)	2 (18%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Confidential grievance channel	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Direct payment to women	3 (13%)	2 (18%)	1 (11%)	0 (0%)	2 (18%)	1 (14%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Payment timeliness improvements	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Gender guidance/training	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Emergency attendance rules	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)

Source: Own representation.

Tab. 18 Q17 - Constraints limiting implementation feasibility, frequency by setting and role, multiple selection up to 3 (n=23)

Item	Overall (n=23)	By Delivery Setting			By Respondent Role			
		Both (n=11)	Camp (n=9)	Host Comm. (n=3)	PM/Coord. (n=11)	Field Off. (n=7)	MEAL (n=4)	Safeg. (n=1)
Budget limits	14 (61%)	6 (55%)	7 (78%)	1 (33%)	6 (55%)	4 (57%)	3 (75%)	1 (100%)
Donor requirements/reporting format	7 (30%)	2 (18%)	3 (33%)	2 (67%)	4 (36%)	2 (29%)	1 (25%)	0 (0%)
Government approvals / regulatory constraints	4 (17%)	1 (9%)	3 (33%)	0 (0%)	2 (18%)	2 (29%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Data protection/privacy restrictions	3 (13%)	1 (9%)	2 (22%)	0 (0%)	2 (18%)	1 (14%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Limited staffing time	6 (26%)	5 (45%)	1 (11%)	0 (0%)	4 (36%)	0 (0%)	2 (50%)	0 (0%)
Limited childcare options in the area	6 (26%)	2 (18%)	3 (33%)	1 (33%)	2 (18%)	2 (29%)	1 (25%)	1 (100%)
Transport market/cost/safety constraints	2 (9%)	1 (9%)	1 (11%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (14%)	1 (25%)	0 (0%)
Worksite availability/location constraints	4 (17%)	2 (18%)	1 (11%)	1 (33%)	0 (0%)	2 (29%)	2 (50%)	0 (0%)
Contractor capacity/behaviour	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Community norms/acceptance	9 (39%)	4 (36%)	2 (22%)	3 (100%)	4 (36%)	2 (29%)	2 (50%)	1 (100%)

Source: Own representation.

Tab. 19 Q18 - Feasibility ratings of implemented measures, by setting and role (Mean, 1–5 Likert scale) (n=23)

Item	Overall (n=23)	By Delivery Setting			By Respondent Role			
		Both (n=11)	Camp (n=9)	Host Comm. (n=3)	PM/Coord. (n=11)	Field Off. (n=7)	MEAL (n=4)	Safeg. (n=1)
Targeted outreach to women	3.70 (n=10)	3.57 (n=7)	4.00 (n=3)	-	4.25 (n=4)	4.50 (n=2)	2.75 (n=4)	-
Women's quotas/targets	3.91 (n=11)	4.00 (n=6)	3.80 (n=5)	-	3.50 (n=6)	4.50 (n=4)	4.00 (n=1)	-
Selection/registration adjustments	3.33 (n=3)	3.00 (n=2)	4.00 (n=1)	-	3.00 (n=2)	-	4.00 (n=1)	-
Work-type adapted for women	2.55 (n=11)	2.25 (n=4)	2.40 (n=5)	3.50 (n=2)	2.75 (n=4)	3.33 (n=3)	1.33 (n=3)	3.00 (n=1)
Worksite proximity	2.44 (n=9)	3.00 (n=3)	2.00 (n=4)	2.50 (n=2)	2.50 (n=4)	2.67 (n=3)	2.00 (n=1)	2.00 (n=1)
Flexible schedule / shorter shifts	2.67 (n=3)	-	3.00 (n=1)	2.50 (n=2)	2.00 (n=1)	3.00 (n=1)	-	3.00 (n=1)
Transport support	4.20 (n=5)	3.67 (n=3)	5.00 (n=1)	5.00 (n=1)	5.00 (n=1)	5.00 (n=2)	3.00 (n=2)	-
Childcare support	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Women-only teams	4.33 (n=3)	4.00 (n=1)	5.00 (n=1)	4.00 (n=1)	4.33 (n=3)	-	-	-
Female supervisor/team lead	3.00 (n=2)	3.00 (n=2)	-	-	3.00 (n=2)	-	-	-
Gender-sensitive facilities	2.00 (n=1)	-	-	2.00 (n=1)	-	2.00 (n=1)	-	-
Code of conduct & induction	1.00 (n=2)	1.00 (n=1)	1.00 (n=1)	-	1.00 (n=2)	-	-	-
Confidential grievance channel	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Direct payment to women	3.67 (n=3)	3.00 (n=2)	5.00 (n=1)	-	3.00 (n=2)	5.00 (n=1)	-	-
Payment timeliness improvements	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Gender guidance/training	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Emergency attendance rules	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Source: Own representation.

Tab. 20 Q19 - Women's uptake rate (among applicants): response distribution by setting and role and mean Score (n=21)

Group	Much lower	Slightly lower	About the same	Slightly higher	Much higher	Mean
Overall (n=21)	1 (5%)	3 (14%)	5 (24%)	12 (57%)	0 (0%)	3.33
Both (n=11)	1 (9%)	1 (9%)	3 (27%)	6 (55%)	0 (0%)	3.27
Camp (n=7)	0 (0%)	1 (14%)	1 (14%)	5 (71%)	0 (0%)	3.57
Host Comm. (n=3)	0 (0%)	1 (33%)	1 (33%)	1 (33%)	0 (0%)	3
PM/Coord. (n=10)	1 (10%)	0 (0%)	4 (40%)	5 (50%)	0 (0%)	3.3
Field Off. (n=6)	0 (0%)	2 (33%)	0 (0%)	4 (67%)	0 (0%)	3.33
MEAL (n=4)	0 (0%)	1 (25%)	0 (0%)	3 (75%)	0 (0%)	3.5
Safeg. (n=1)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	3

Source: Own representation.

Tab. 21 Q19 - Women's completion rate (among starters): response distribution by setting and role and mean Score (n=21)

Group	Much lower	Slightly lower	About the same	Slightly higher	Much higher	Mean
Overall (n=21)	2 (10%)	2 (10%)	5 (24%)	8 (38%)	4 (19%)	3.48
Both (n=11)	1 (9%)	1 (9%)	3 (27%)	5 (45%)	1 (9%)	3.36
Camp (n=7)	0 (0%)	1 (14%)	2 (29%)	2 (29%)	2 (29%)	3.71
Host Comm. (n=3)	1 (33%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (33%)	1 (33%)	3.33
PM/Coord. (n=10)	1 (10%)	0 (0%)	4 (40%)	4 (40%)	1 (10%)	3.4
Field Off. (n=6)	1 (17%)	1 (17%)	0 (0%)	2 (33%)	2 (33%)	3.5
MEAL (n=4)	0 (0%)	1 (25%)	0 (0%)	2 (50%)	1 (25%)	3.75
Safeg. (n=1)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	3

Source: Own representation.

Tab. 22 Q19 - Women's dropout rate: response distribution by setting and role and mean Score (n=21)

Group	Much lower	Slightly lower	About the same	Slightly higher	Much higher	Mean
Overall (n=21)	4 (19%)	7 (33%)	6 (29%)	4 (19%)	0 (0%)	3.52
Both (n=11)	1 (9%)	4 (36%)	3 (27%)	3 (27%)	0 (0%)	3.27
Camp (n=7)	2 (29%)	2 (29%)	2 (29%)	1 (14%)	0 (0%)	3.71
Host Comm. (n=3)	1 (33%)	1 (33%)	1 (33%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	4.00
PM/Coord. (n=10)	1 (10%)	4 (40%)	3 (30%)	2 (20%)	0 (0%)	3.4
Field Off. (n=6)	2 (33%)	1 (17%)	2 (33%)	1 (17%)	0 (0%)	3.67
MEAL (n=4)	1 (25%)	2 (50%)	0 (0%)	1 (25%)	0 (0%)	3.75
Safeg. (n=1)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	3.00

Source: Own representation.

Tab. 23 Q19 - Women's overall participation rate: response distribution by setting and role and mean Score (n=21)

Group	Much lower	Slightly lower	About the same	Slightly higher	Much higher	Mean
Overall (n=21)	3 (14%)	1 (5%)	5 (24%)	11 (52%)	1 (5%)	3.29
Both (n=11)	2 (18%)	0 (0%)	3 (27%)	5 (45%)	1 (9%)	3.27
Camp (n=7)	0 (0%)	1 (14%)	1 (14%)	5 (71%)	0 (0%)	3.57
Host Comm. (n=3)	1 (33%)	0 (0%)	1 (33%)	1 (33%)	0 (0%)	2.67
PM/Coord. (n=10)	2 (20%)	0 (0%)	2 (20%)	6 (60%)	0 (0%)	3.2
Field Off. (n=6)	1 (17%)	0 (0%)	2 (33%)	3 (50%)	0 (0%)	3.17
MEAL (n=4)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (25%)	2 (50%)	1 (25%)	4
Safeg. (n=1)	0 (0%)	1 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2

Source: Own representation

Tab. 24 Q19 - Mean scores by measure implemented (Q16): uptake, completion, dropout & Overall (n=21)

Measure (Q16)	n	Uptake	Completion	Dropout (rev.)	Overall
Women's quotas	10	3.7	3.7	3.4	3.5
Targeted outreach to women	10	3.7	3.7	3.5	3.7
Work-type adapted for women	10	3.1	3.3	3.5	3.2
Worksite proximity	8	3.5	3.88	4	3.25
Transport support	4	3.75	4.25	4.25	3.75
Selection/registration adjustments	3	3	3	3	2.67
Flexible schedule/shift	3	3.33	4	4	3
Women-only teams	3	3.67	4.33	4.33	4
Female supervisors/team leads	2	2.5	2.5	3	2.5
Code of conduct / induction	2	2.5	2	2	2.5
Direct payment to women	2	2.5	2.5	3	2.5
Gender-sensitive facilities	1	2	1	3	1
Childcare support	0	-	-	-	-
Confidential grievance channel	0	-	-	-	-
Payment timeliness safeguard	0	-	-	-	-
Gender guidance/training	0	-	-	-	-
Emergency attendance rules	0	-	-	-	-

Source: Own representation

Tab. 25 Q20 - Perceived agreement that measures would increase participation, by setting and role (Mean, 1–5 Likert scale) (n=23)

Item	Overall (n=23)	By Delivery Setting			By Respondent Role			
		Both (n=11)	Camp (n=9)	Host Comm. (n=3)	PM/Coord. (n=11)	Field Off. (n=7)	MEAL (n=4)	Safeg. (n=1)
Targeted outreach to women	4.17 (n=12)	4.50 (n=4)	4.00 (n=6)	4.00 (n=2)	4.29 (n=7)	4.00 (n=4)	-	4.00 (n=1)
Women's quotas/targets	3.83 (n=12)	4.40 (n=5)	3.75 (n=4)	3.00 (n=3)	4.00 (n=5)	2.67 (n=3)	4.67 (n=3)	4.00 (n=1)
Selection/registration adjustments	4.10 (n=20)	4.00 (n=9)	4.12 (n=8)	4.33 (n=3)	4.22 (n=9)	4.00 (n=7)	4.00 (n=3)	4.00 (n=1)
Work-type adapted for women	4.08 (n=12)	4.29 (n=7)	4.50 (n=4)	1.00 (n=1)	4.71 (n=7)	3.50 (n=4)	2.00 (n=1)	-
Worksite proximity	4.36 (n=14)	4.62 (n=8)	4.00 (n=5)	4.00 (n=1)	4.57 (n=7)	4.00 (n=4)	4.33 (n=3)	-
Flexible schedule / shorter shifts	3.65 (n=20)	4.18 (n=11)	3.00 (n=8)	3.00 (n=1)	3.90 (n=10)	3.17 (n=6)	3.75 (n=4)	-
Transport support	4.00 (n=17)	4.62 (n=8)	3.14 (n=7)	4.50 (n=2)	4.00 (n=10)	3.75 (n=4)	5.00 (n=2)	3.00 (n=1)
Childcare support	4.00 (n=22)	4.00 (n=11)	4.22 (n=9)	3.00 (n=2)	4.45 (n=11)	3.33 (n=6)	3.75 (n=4)	4.00 (n=1)
Women-only teams	3.85 (n=20)	4.00 (n=10)	3.75 (n=8)	3.50 (n=2)	4.12 (n=8)	3.71 (n=7)	4.00 (n=4)	2.00 (n=1)
Female supervisor/team lead	3.70 (n=20)	3.67 (n=9)	3.44 (n=9)	5.00 (n=2)	3.67 (n=9)	4.00 (n=6)	3.75 (n=4)	2.00 (n=1)
Gender-sensitive facilities	4.41 (n=22)	4.36 (n=11)	4.44 (n=9)	4.50 (n=2)	4.64 (n=11)	4.33 (n=6)	4.00 (n=4)	4.00 (n=1)
Code of conduct & induction	4.00 (n=21)	3.60 (n=10)	4.50 (n=8)	4.00 (n=3)	4.33 (n=9)	4.29 (n=7)	2.50 (n=4)	5.00 (n=1)
Confidential grievance channel	3.90 (n=21)	3.82 (n=11)	4.12 (n=8)	3.50 (n=2)	4.27 (n=11)	3.80 (n=5)	2.75 (n=4)	5.00 (n=1)
Direct payment to women	4.00 (n=19)	3.44 (n=9)	4.50 (n=8)	4.50 (n=2)	4.44 (n=9)	4.20 (n=5)	2.50 (n=4)	5.00 (n=1)
Payment timeliness improvements	3.83 (n=23)	3.64 (n=11)	4.11 (n=9)	3.67 (n=3)	4.45 (n=11)	3.71 (n=7)	2.00 (n=4)	5.00 (n=1)
Gender guidance/training	3.87 (n=23)	3.73 (n=11)	4.00 (n=9)	4.00 (n=3)	4.45 (n=11)	3.86 (n=7)	2.50 (n=4)	3.00 (n=1)
Emergency attendance rules	4.10 (n=20)	4.10 (n=10)	4.00 (n=8)	4.50 (n=2)	4.18 (n=11)	4.20 (n=5)	3.33 (n=3)	5.00 (n=1)

Source: Own representation.

Tab. 26 Reported women's targeted and actual participation rates (%), by setting and role (n=18)

Group	Target Rate Mean (%)	Target n (valid)	Actual Rate Mean (%)	Actual n (valid)	Gap (Actual – Target)	Don't Know Target Actual
Overall (n=23)	47.6%	19	45.5%	18	-4.2%	4 5
Both (n=11)	51.9%	7	36.9%	7	-15.0%	4 4
Camp (n=9)	54.2%	9	57.8%	9	3.6%	0 0
Host Comm. (n=3)	18.0%	3	20.5%	2	-1.5%	0 1
PM/Coord. (n=11)	58.0%	8	50.4%	8	-7.6%	3 3
Field Off. (n=7)	40.4%	7	48.3%	6	2.8%	0 1
MEAL (n=4)	31.0%	3	20.3%	3	-10.7%	1 1
Safeg. (n=1)	65.0%	1	65.0%	1	0.0%	0 0

Source: Own representation.

Appendix C: Pipeline-Stage Monitoring Indicator Framework and Specifications

This framework applies a prospective benchmarking approach, developing a minimum measurable standard for gender-responsive CfW monitoring where no sector-wide benchmark currently exists. Each indicator represents a gap between current practice, recommendations from existing evaluation frameworks, and implementing organisation standards, as confirmed by the full survey instrument, specifically Q14 for the monitoring domain. Priority levels reflect practitioner-confirmed feasibility thresholds established in Chapter 5.

Tab. 27. 10Pipeline-stage monitoring framework - indicators, priority, and setting

Indicator	Measurement unit	Priority	Setting
ENTRY STAGE			
1. Women applicants	<i>n and % of women who applied per recruitment</i>	High	Both
2. Women excluded from the documentation stage	<i>n recorded as ineligible at pre-eligibility stage due to documentation gaps, per recruitment round; collected from field officer records or RAIS (the camp registration and eligibility system) where accessible</i>	High	Both
3. Outreach quality checklist	<i>Criteria met (out of 7): women-accessible channel; ≥14 days' notice; worksite location and hours stated; team composition stated; female supervisor availability stated; transport/childcare stated if available; non-digital channel included</i>	High	Host communities
4. Selection mechanism type	<i>Type recorded per round: scoring / quota / committee / FCFS / lottery</i>	Medium	Both: Priority in camps (highest concentration)

COMPLETION STAGE			
5. Women starters	<i>n and % of selected women who began work</i>	High	Both
6. Women completers	<i>n and % of starters completing the full cycle</i>	High	Both
7. Dropout / Early exit - categorised reasons	<i>n per category: household opposition; care; transport/safety; worksite conditions; payment; health; other (open text field).</i>	High	Both
8. Worksite proximity at site selection	<i>% of target women living within walking distance of the proposed worksite, recorded at the site selection stage before the programme begins; used to document whether proximity was assessed as a design criterion.</i>	Medium	Both: Higher priority in refugee camps
ENABLING CONDITIONS			
9. Transport and proximity - assessed together	<i>Transport and proximity - assessed together. (a) Yes/no: Worksite proximity measures were applied. (b) Reasons categorised for non-application to worksite proximity within workers' walking distance; (c) transport type and % participants covered.</i>	High	Both: Higher priority in refugee camps
10. Direct payment into women's own account	<i>Yes/no at enrolment: account in a woman's name; no third-party intermediary; Yes/no at enrolment: Payment requested in Cash (no justification required).</i>	High	Both: Higher priority in refugee camps
11. Payment timeliness	<i>Days from work completion to payment, flagged if exceeding contractual deadline</i>	Medium	Refugee camps

12. Gender-sensitive worksite checklist	<i>Monthly per worksite: separate toilets; private rest/prayer space; drinking water; PPE fit for women; onboarding briefing recorded; complaint mechanism operational</i>	High	Both: Higher priority in host communities
13. Female supervisor in place	<i>Yes/no per worksite. If no: safety package documented as a combined record</i>	Medium	Refugee camps
14. Childcare - type and coverage	<i>Type and % of participants with dependents who accessed it</i>	Medium	Both: Higher priority in Host communities
15. Grievances - type, resolution, and preventive measures	<i>n per category; resolution status; days to response; preventive measures identified, if any</i>	Medium	Both
16. Internal monitoring of knowledge circulation	<i>(a) MEAL summary shared with field officers and managers, yes/no; (b) field officer log, dropout checklists submitted to MEAL, yes/no; (c) a kick-off meeting before launching work cycles to present findings of the effectiveness of implemented measures, barriers, and lessons learned from field officers/ direct implementation and contractors/supervisors, yes/no</i>	High	Both

Source: Own representation, based on survey findings and literature reviewed in Chapter 2. High priority = large, consistent gap directly linked to participation outcomes, programme-operable. Medium=gap evidenced but smaller, less consistent across settings, or partially policy-dependent.

Tab. 28. Indicators, Jordan-specific justification, and setting differentiation justification.

Indicator (measurement unit)	Jordan-specific justification and data source	Setting priority justification
1. Women applicants	Tracked by only 43% of programmes (Q14), the weakest entry-stage indicator. Without it, low uptake cannot be distinguished from low conversion at selection. Within camps, programme managers reported tracking this at 75% compared to 25% among field officers (both n=4), suggesting a potential role-based awareness gap, though the pooled MEAL-to-field-officer comparison is confounded by setting composition (Q14).	Both settings. Critical in camps where RAIS creates a pre-selection exclusion layer invisible to all other indicators.
2. Women excluded from the documentation stage	Documentation rated second strongest barrier overall (M=2.70, Q1; M=2.11 camps). Only 39% applied exclusion risk screening (Q2). The scale of exclusion before selection begins is entirely unmeasured. In host communities, work permit eligibility excludes the majority of Syrian refugee women before recruitment (Loewe et al., 2020, p.49).	Camps: RAIS eligibility stack. Host communities: formal work permit threshold.
3. Outreach quality checklist	Targeted outreach was used only by 33% of host-community programmes (Q2). Household consent is condition-dependent (M=2.48, Q1). The World Bank (2024b, p. 33) suggests that husbands' approval depends on safety, team composition, and transport information. An outreach message that directly communicates these conditions reduces the consent barrier before application. Application timing barrier (M=2.91, Q1) supports	Priority in host communities: no SOP content standard for outreach messages. In camps, BNLWG SOPs specify posting locations but not the information that must be communicated to women.

Indicator (measurement unit)	Jordan-specific justification and data source	Setting priority justification
	the ≥14-day notice criterion. ILO (2021, p.8): male-dominated networks systematically exclude women regardless of eligibility.	
4. Selection mechanism type	Committee decisions were reported exclusively in camp and both-settings programmes (56% and 18% respectively; 0% in host communities), while FCFS, though most concentrated in camps (44%), was also reported by one host-community programme (33%). Together, these two mechanisms are most heavily concentrated in camps, the setting with a high documentation barrier (M=2.11) and household consent barrier (M=1.89). Both mechanisms disadvantage women facing the heaviest constraints. The recording mechanism type makes the selection architecture reviewable (ILO, 2021, p. 27).	Priority in camps: only setting where FCFS and committee decisions co-exist alongside the highest entry barriers.
5. Women starters	Tracked by only 39% of programmes (Q14), the lowest tracking rate in the dataset. Gap between selected and starting is a distinct failure point: a woman may be selected but unable to start due to household objection or worksite conditions not matching outreach expectations. Without this, completion rates cannot be correctly interpreted.	Both settings. Especially relevant in camps where entry conditions and completion conditions diverge most sharply (Q5, Q6).
6. Women completers	Tracked by 74% of programmes (Q14), the most established completion indicator, but loses analytical value without a starter's denominator. Completion without starters collapses	Both settings.

Indicator (measurement unit)	Jordan-specific justification and data source	Setting priority justification
	two pipeline stages and can overstate performance where early attrition is high.	
7. Dropout/ Early exit - categorised reasons	Dropout was tracked by 70%, but reasons were tracked by only 61% and rarely categorised (Q14). The seven categories correspond directly to barriers documented in Q1, Q9, Q10, Q11, and Q13. Without categorisation, dropout data cannot be linked to specific design failures or inform the next programme cycle.	Both settings. A simple exit tick-box form is programme-operable without additional infrastructure.
8. Worksite proximity at site selection	Top completion lever (70%, Q15); strongest dropout-reduction signal (M=4.00, Q19). Yet Q8 indicated proximity follows site availability, not design decisions; no setting-differentiated pattern exists. Recording at the site selection stage converts proximity from a background variable into a trackable design criterion.	Both settings. Especially relevant in camps where proximity feasibility is lowest (M=2.00, Q18).
9. Transport and proximity - assessed together	Transport is absent from 61% of programmes, 78% in camps (Q9). Highly feasible where implemented (M=4.20, Q18); the strongest completion and dropout signals in Q19 (both M=4.25). Proximity compensation hypothesis not supported: camp proximity distribution (56/44) is near-identical to overall sample (52/48, Q8). Both indicators must be assessed together to enable setting-specific decisions on which lever to prioritise (Q18, Q19).	Priority in camps: 78% no transport, proximity feasibility M=2.00. Priority in host communities: transport market failures dominate (Alam & Bagnoli, 2023, pp.55-57).

Indicator (measurement unit)	Jordan-specific justification and data source	Setting priority justification
10. Direct payment into women's own account	100% mobile wallet use in camps, but only 56% reported direct payment to women, vs 91% both-settings, 100% host communities (Q13). Digitalisation does not equal financial control: GIZ (2022, pp. 3, 28) documented that 42% of women worried about mobile technology errors, and separated women feared partner access to their accounts. Verifiable through RAIS account registration.	Priority in camps: the largest gap between digital infrastructure and women's actual financial control. Verifiable through RAIS (the camp registration and eligibility system).
11. Payment timeliness	Only 56% of camp programmes reported timely payment, compared with 91-100% elsewhere (Q13). In camps, all payments are digital; delays are due to system management failures, not logistics problems. Payment delays undermine household confidence and undermine trust-building (Loewe et al., 2020, p. 136; ILO, 2021, p. 27).	Priority in camps: sharpest timeliness gap by setting; all payments traceable digitally.
12. Gender-sensitive worksite checklist	Tracked by only 26% of programmes; entirely absent from host communities (Q14). Highest perceived effectiveness of any measure (M=4.41, Q20), yet only 4% selected it as a top participation lever (Q16). Private rest/prayer space reported by only 52% overall, 36% in both-settings (Q11). Onboarding briefings are mandatory under camp SOPs, but reported by only 56% of camp programmes, lower than the host communities (100%,	Priority in host communities: entirely absent. Priority in camps: onboarding gap contradicts SOP requirements.

Indicator (measurement unit)	Jordan-specific justification and data source	Setting priority justification
	Q11). A monthly checklist closes the gap between what is required and what is verified (ILO, 2024, p.37).	
13. Female supervisor in place	Only 22% of camp programmes had female supervisors vs 82% both-settings, 67% host communities (Q6). IBV frameworks define supervisor roles as contractable at fixed pay scales (BNLWG, 2020, Annex 1), a staffing decision rather than a regulatory one. In camps: 67% public worksites + 78% mixed-gender teams + 22% female supervision creates a compounding safety gap. Where no female supervisor is in place, the compensating package must be recorded as a unit, not as separate checklist items (ILO, 2022, p.54).	Priority in camps: compounding gap, lowest supervision, highest public exposure, and highest mixed-gender teams. Programme operable under IBV staffing provisions.
14. Childcare - type and coverage	Only 17% of programmes provided any childcare, all in camps (Q10); zero in both-settings and host communities. Q20 indicated childcare as the most endorsed unimplemented measure in camp settings (M=4.22). Expanded childcare is estimated to raise women's LFP by 7.3 pp (World Bank, 2024b, p. 7). Q17: Budget limits (61%) and limited local options (26%) are the main constraints; tracking what is achievable within those constraints enables incremental improvement.	Priority in the host communities: zero provision despite indicated need. In camps, provision exists but is not standardised across programmes.

Indicator (measurement unit)	Jordan-specific justification and data source	Setting priority justification
15. Grievances - type, resolution, and preventive measures	Tracked by only 26% of programmes (Q14). Camp SOPs require complaint mechanisms with two entry points, a non-supervisor focal point, and a three-week response (BNLWG, 2020, Section 5.6). The existence of a mechanism does not confirm the use or analysis of its outputs. Without type categorisation, grievance data cannot be linked to specific design failures or support learning.	Both settings. In host communities, the mechanism depends on contractor compliance, and tracking is more critical where SOP enforcement is absent.
16. Internal monitoring of knowledge circulation	27% of programme managers selected "I don't know" for both the target and actual women's participation rate (Q21). Programme managers negotiate targets and select design measures; if they cannot report whether their programme meets participation goals, the feedback loop between monitoring and design decisions is broken. This indicator requires no new data collection; it requires existing data to reach decision-makers.	Both settings. Most acute in both-settings programmes, which indicated the largest negative participation gap (mean: -15.0 pp, Q21).

Source: Own representation, based on survey findings (Chapter 4), compared against the ILO (2021, 2024), DEval (2021), UN Women Jordan Office (2024), and BNLWG (2020, 2022) evaluation frameworks and recommendations, and against implementing organisation standards.

Appendix D: Consolidated Recommendations by Design Domain, Delivery Setting, Feasibility Classification, Responsible Actor, and Programme Cycle Stage

Tab. 29. Inclusion standards by domain, delivery setting, feasibility classification, responsible actor, and programme cycle stage.

#	Recommendation	Design Domain	Delivery Setting	Feasibility	Responsible Actor	Cycle Stage
R1.1	Deploy multi-channel women-targeted outreach (female community leaders, SMS, posters at women's centres) for each recruitment round, with messages explicitly stating available work-types, schedule, and worksite location.	Recruitment	Both	Programme-operable	Programme Manager / Field Officer	Design
R1.2	Embed women's quota and targeted outreach clauses in procurement TORs	Recruitment	Both	Programme-operable	Programme Manager / Procurement Officer	Procurement
R1.3	Apply a documented exclusion-risk screening checklist at selection to identify women facing compounded barriers (documentation gaps, mobility constraints, household consent issues) and refer them to targeted support before exclusion.	Recruitment	Both	Programme-operable	Programme Manager / Field Officer	Design

#	Recommendation	Design Do- main	Deliv- ery Set- ting	Feasibility	Responsible Actor	Cycle Stage
R1.4	Conduct pre-cycle household orientation sessions target- ing male household members to address consent barriers, covering work conditions, safety arrangements, and fe- male supervision availability.	Recruitment	Both	Programme- operable	Field Officer	Induc- tion
R1.5	Designate at least one women-accessible community loca- tion and a minimum application window of 14 days per re- cruitment round, prioritising locations outside male-domi- nated public spaces in host communities' settings.	Recruitment	Both	Programme- operable	Programme Manager	Design
R1.6	Assign a designated UNHCR field unit contact to provide RAIS pre-eligibility assistance for women with incomplete documentation files before the application deadline.	Recruitment	Camp	Programme- operable	UNHCR / Pro- gramme Man- ager	Design
R1.7	Advocate for work-permit facilitation for Syrian refugee women	Recruitment	Host com- muni- ties	<i>Policy-de- pendent</i>	Donor / Minis- try / ILO	Policy- level
R2.1	Offer low-stigma work-types (admin, community services, care-related tasks)	Work De- sign	Both	Programme- operable	Programme Manager	Design

#	Recommendation	Design Domain	Delivery Setting	Feasibility	Responsible Actor	Cycle Stage
R2.2	Establish women-only teams or managed-safe mixed teams with codes of conduct.	Work Design	Both	Programme-operable	Programme Manager / Field Officer	Design / Induction
R2.3	Allocate at least 30% of supervisor and team lead positions to women and specify this threshold in procurement contracts and IBV staffing plans.	Work Design	Both	Programme-operable	Programme Manager	Procurement / Design
R2.4	Establish indoor or semi-private task assignments rather than high-visibility public-space work in communities where social stigma against women's outdoor labour is documented at the programme design stage.	Work Design	Both	Programme-operable	Programme Manager	Design
R3.1	Standardise a fixed morning-only schedule not exceeding six hours as the default programme format, with flexible shifts as an opt-in alternative in camp settings only.	Time / Transport / Childcare	Camp	Programme-operable	Programme Manager	Design
R3.2	Prioritise neighbourhood-level worksite proximity in site selection decisions	Time / Transport / Childcare	Both	Programme-operable	Programme Manager	Design

#	Recommendation	Design Domain	Delivery Setting	Feasibility	Responsible Actor	Cycle Stage
R3.3	Provide organised transport or a cash transport allowance as a budget line item where worksite proximity cannot be achieved within the same neighbourhood; assess proximity first before defaulting to transport provision.	Time / Transport / Childcare	Both	Programme-operable	Programme Manager	Procurement / Design
R3.4	Pilot onsite childcare or childcare allowance (camp settings first)	Time / Transport / Childcare	Camp	Programme-operable (pilot)	Programme Manager / Implementing Agency	Design
R3.5	Formalise inter-agency minimum childcare standards within the BNLWG SOP revision process, including facility type, caregiver ratio, and proximity requirements.	Time / Transport / Childcare	Camp	Programme-operable	BNLWG / Implementing Agency	Design
R3.6	Pilot a women-as-caregivers CfW model by employing women on IBV contracts as on-site caregivers for participating mothers, with a structured evaluation of uptake and completion effects, host communities expansion to be a second-phase recommendation pending pilot results.	Time / Transport / Childcare	Camp	Programme-operable (<i>to be tested</i>)	Programme Manager	Design

#	Recommendation	Design Domain	Delivery Setting	Feasibility	Responsible Actor	Cycle Stage
R3.7	National childcare infrastructure expansion	Time / Transport / Childcare	Both	Policy-dependent	Government / World Bank / Donors	Policy-level
R4.1	Record onboarding and safety briefings as a monitored SOP compliance item	Worksite Safety	Both	Programme-operable	Programme Manager / Field Officer	Induction / Monitoring
R4.2	Integrate private rest and prayer space into SOP minimums and host communities' contracts.	Worksite Safety	Both	Programme-operable	BNLWG / Donor / Programme Manager	Procurement
R4.3	Embed gender-sensitive facility standards (separate toilets, private rest and prayer space, drinking water, PPE fitted for women) as a pass/fail criterion in worksite pre-commencement assessments.	Worksite Safety	Both	Programme-operable	Programme Manager / Procurement Officer	Procurement

#	Recommendation	Design Do- main	Deliv- ery Set- ting	Feasibility	Responsible Actor	Cycle Stage
R4.4	Require host communities' contracts to mandate a confidential grievance mechanism with at least two entry points and a designated non-supervisory focal point, mirroring the minimum standard already established in camp SOPs; verify operationalisation at induction.	Worksite Safety	Host com- muni- ties	Programme- operable	Programme Manager / Safeguarding Officer	Procure- ment / Induc- tion
R4.5	Enforce code of conduct and harassment-prevention protocols at all worksites.	Worksite Safety	Both	Programme- operable	Programme Manager / Field Officer	Induc- tion / Monitor- ing
R5.1	Verify at enrolment that the mobile wallet/account is registered in the woman's name.	Payment	Camp	Programme- operable	Programme Manager / MEAL	Induc- tion
R5.2	Provide digital payment literacy training at enrolment	Payment	Both	Programme- operable	Programme Manager / Field Officer	Induc- tion

#	Recommendation	Design Domain	Delivery Setting	Feasibility	Responsible Actor	Cycle Stage
R5.3	Offer cash or prepaid card payment as an opt-in alternative at enrolment for women who indicate that digital modality poses household control or safety risks, without requiring justification.	Payment	Both	Programme-operable	Programme Manager	Design / Induction
R5.4	Specify timely payment as a KPI in all contracts with corrective measures for delays.	Payment	Both	Programme-operable	Programme Manager / Donor	Procurement
R5.5	Link payment timeliness verification to RAIS recording system	Payment	Camp	Programme-operable	Programme Manager / MEAL / UNHCR	Monitoring
R6.1	Track pipeline-stage indicators: applicants, selected, starters, completers, early exits with reasons	Monitoring	Both	Programme-operable	MEAL / Programme Manager	Monitoring
R6.2	Record women excluded at the documentation stage as a routine pipeline indicator	Monitoring	Both	Programme-operable	MEAL / Programme Manager	Monitoring

#	Recommendation	Design Domain	Delivery Setting	Feasibility	Responsible Actor	Cycle Stage
R6.3	Incorporate payment timeliness, gender-sensitive worksite checklist results, and grievances disaggregated by type and resolution status into the standard monthly monitoring report.	Monitoring	Both	Programme-operable	MEAL	Monitoring
R6.4	Deploy a standardised exit form at the point of early programme exit, with pre-coded dropout categories (household opposition, care responsibilities, transport, worksite conditions, payment, health) and an open 'other' field.	Monitoring	Both	Programme-operable	Field Officer / MEAL	Monitoring
R6.5	Track 'core package' indicator: number of gender-sensitive measures implemented per reporting cycle (exploratory/untested).	Monitoring	Both	Programme-operable	MEAL / Programme Manager	Monitoring
R6.6	Require MEAL staff to distribute a one-page pipeline summary to programme managers and field officers at the close of each reporting cycle, covering uptake, dropout, and grievance trends.	Monitoring	Both	Programme-operable	MEAL / Programme Manager	Monitoring
R6.7	Require field officers to submit weekly attendance and dropout logs to the central MEAL system using a	Monitoring	Both	Programme-operable	Field Officer	Monitoring

#	Recommendation	Design Do- main	Deliv- ery Set- ting	Feasibility	Responsible Actor	Cycle Stage
	standardised form, with submission tracked as a field of- ficer performance indicator.					
R6.8	Require programme managers to report women's partici- pation target, achieved rate, and dropout reasons to the lead agency at each reporting cycle as a named delivera- ble; flag non-submission or "unknown" responses as a programme management performance issue requiring fol- low-up.	Monitoring	Both	Programme- operable	Programme Manager	Monitor- ing

Source: Own representation. based on survey findings and literature reviewed in Chapter 2. These recommendations constitute the action plan derived from the benchmarking exercise, translating identified gaps between current practice and existing evaluation frameworks into programme-operable and policy-dependent actions. The pipeline-stage indicator framework supporting implementation monitoring is presented in Appendix C.

Tab. 30. Derivation Sources for Inclusion standards recommendations in Tab. 29.

#	Recommendation	Literature Standard	Current Practice Gap (Q1-Q14)	Effectiveness Evidence (Q15/Q16)	Feasibility Evidence (Q18)	Perceived Effectiveness (Q20)
R1.1	Deploy multi-channel women-targeted outreach for each recruitment round, with messages explicitly stating work types, schedule, and worksite location.	ILO (2021, p.8): outreach through community leaders and culturally appropriate practices linked to stronger women's participation. BNLWG (2020, s.2.1; 2022, s.3): job notices required across multiple locations, including community centres.	Q2: targeted outreach applied by only 65% (n=15); host-community setting lowest (33%, n=1). Q1: Outreach reached women less effectively in host communities (M=3.00) vs camps (M=4.67).	Not included as Q15 option (entry-stage measure). Q16: selected by 43% (n=10) among the top three measures associated with higher participation.	M=3.70 (n=10), feasible by those who implemented it.	M=4.17 (n=12), practitioners who did not select it in Q16 rated it as effective.
R1.2	Embed women's quota and targeted outreach clauses in procurement TORs.	BNLWG (2020, s. 3.7; 2022, s. 4): quotas encouraged as a standard inclusion requirement. ILO (2021, p. 27) recommends wide advertising and open processes to strengthen women's confidence in the selection process.	Q2: women's quotas applied by 74% (n=17) and targeted outreach by 65% (n=15), indicating neither is universally embedded in procurement.	Not included as Q15 option. Q16: women's quotas selected by 48% (n=11) and targeted outreach by 43% (n=10).	Women's quotas: M=3.91 (n=11). Targeted outreach: M=3.70 (n=10).	Women's quotas: M=3.83 (n=12). Targeted outreach: M=4.17 (n=12).

#	Recommendation	Literature Standard	Current Practice Gap (Q1-Q14)	Effectiveness Evidence (Q15/Q16)	Feasibility Evidence (Q18)	Perceived Effectiveness (Q20)
R1.3	Apply a documented exclusion-risk screening checklist at selection to identify women facing compounded barriers and refer them to support.	BNLWG (2020, s. 3.3.1); Oxfam (2018, p. 18); GIZ (2022, pp. 9-10): documentation gaps and RAIS eligibility requirements can exclude women before any selection decision is made.	Q1: Household consent is the strongest barrier overall (M=2.48), most acute in camps (M=1.89); documentation is the second strongest (M=2.70), most severe in camps (M=2.11). Q2: exclusion risk screening was applied by only 39% (n=9).	N/A	N/A	Q20: selection/registration adjustments M=4.10 (n=20), related measure rated highly effective.
R1.4	Conduct pre-cycle household orientation sessions targeting male household members to address consent barriers.	ILO (2021, p.32); Loewe et al. (2020, pp.107-108): household approval is condition-dependent, shaped by transport safety, worksite exposure, and financial hardship. Programmes addressing these conditions before recruitment expand the eligible pool.	Q1: Household consent and gender norms rated the strongest barrier overall (M=2.48), most acute in camps (M=1.89). No programme reported systematic male household orientation in Q2.	N/A	N/A	N/A

#	Recommendation	Literature Standard	Current Practice Gap (Q1-Q14)	Effectiveness Evidence (Q15/Q16)	Feasibility Evidence (Q18)	Perceived Effectiveness (Q20)
R1.5	Designate at least one women-accessible community location and a minimum application window of 14 days per recruitment round.	Oxfam (2018, pp. 20-21); Loewe et al. (2020, p. 102, 136, 146); ILO (2022, p. 54): limited weekday hours and locations associated with men shut out eligible women who know about opportunities and meet eligibility criteria. The specific 14-day minimum window is proposed by this study as a programme-operable response to the application-timing barrier (M=2.91, Q1); it is not specified in the cited sources.	Q1: application time and location barrier (M=2.91 overall), most severe in host communities (M=2.00), where no procedural standard governs how or where applications are collected.	N/A	N/A	Q20: selection/registration adjustments M=4.10 (n=20).
R1.6	Assign a designated UNHCR field unit contact to provide RAIS pre-eligibility	BNLWG (2022, s.3): RAIS eligibility must be checked and verified by the UNHCR Field Unit at least	Q1: documentation rated second strongest barrier overall (M=2.70), most severe in camps (M=2.11).	N/A	N/A	N/A

#	Recommendation	Literature Standard	Current Practice Gap (Q1-Q14)	Effectiveness Evidence (Q15/Q16)	Feasibility Evidence (Q18)	Perceived Effectiveness (Q20)
	assistance to women with incomplete documentation.	three days before enrolment. BNLWG (2020, s. 3.3.1): eligibility criteria include documentation requirements that can exclude women prior to selection.	Q2: exclusion risk screening was applied by only 44% of camp programmes (n=4).			
R1.7	Advocate for facilitating work permits for Syrian refugee women (host communities, policy-dependent).	Loewe et al. (2020, p.49): by mid-2019, only ~5% of work permits issued to Syrians went to women (7,875 of 156,761); by 2025, this share had risen to 15.6% (UNHCR, 2025b), reflecting incremental progress, though structural exclusion persists. BNLWG (2022, s. 3; 2020, s. 3.3): host communities CfW falls under formal employment rules	Q1: Documentation is rated as a barrier in host-community settings. Formal work permit threshold excludes most Syrian refugee women before recruitment begins; it cannot be resolved at the programme level.	N/A	N/A	N/A

#	Recommendation	Literature Standard	Current Practice Gap (Q1-Q14)	Effectiveness Evidence (Q15/Q16)	Feasibility Evidence (Q18)	Perceived Effectiveness (Q20)
		requiring a valid work permit, unlike camp IBV.				
R2.1	Offer low-stigma work types (admin, community services, care-related tasks).	Loewe et al. (2020, pp.104-106): tasks in public spaces traditionally associated with men are widely perceived as unsuitable for women due to social stigma. ILO (2024, p.37): gender-sensitive implementation included work-type adaptation, but sensitivity to women's needs remained incomplete.	Q4: cleaning (65%) and solid waste/recycling (52%) are dominant; care work is reported by only 9% (n=2), and community services by 26% (n=6). Q5: 57% of programmes are in mostly public/open spaces, the highest in camps (67%).	Q15: Work type selected by 52% (n=12) as top completion measure. Q16: selected by 48% (n=11) as top participation measure.	M=2.55 (n=11), rated as difficult to implement; highest dispersion (SD=1.57), indicating sharp setting differences.	M=4.08 (n=12), practitioners who did not select it in Q16 rated it as effective.
R2.2	Establish women-only teams or managed-safe mixed teams with codes of conduct.	ILO (2024, p.37): gender-sensitive implementation included women-only team arrangements; sensitivity to women's needs	Q6: Women-only teams reported by 52% (n=12) overall but only 44% in camps (n=4). Mixed-gender teams managed	Q15: Women-only teams selected by 35% (n=8) as the top completion	M=4.33 (n=3), the highest feasibility rating of any measure.	M=3.85 (n=20).

#	Recommendation	Literature Standard	Current Practice Gap (Q1-Q14)	Effectiveness Evidence (Q15/Q16)	Feasibility Evidence (Q18)	Perceived Effectiveness (Q20)
		remained incomplete. ILO (2022, p.54): Female supervisors are a contractable design option.	safely, reported by 78% of camp programmes as the primary arrangement when female supervisors are unavailable.	measure. Q16: selected by 13% (n=3) as top participation measure.		
R2.3	Allocate at least 30% of supervisor and team lead positions to women and specify this threshold in procurement contracts and IBV staffing plans.	ILO (2022, pp. 29, 36): A minimum of 30% for women's participation is an established gender-responsive procurement benchmark (e.g., in Kenya, Tanzania, and Timor-Leste). ILO (2022, p. 54): female supervisors are an explicit, contractable design option; gender-balanced supervision cannot be replaced by adjusting work-type alone. BNLWG (2020, Annex 1): IBV frameworks define supervisor roles at	Q6: Female supervisors are available in only 22% of camp programmes (n=2), despite SOP frameworks governing camps. Overall, 57% (n=13), but with a stark camp-specific gap.	Q15: female supervisor selected by 13% (n=3) as top completion measure. Q16: selected by 9% (n=2) as top participation measure.	M=3.00 (n=2), approximates scale midpoint; small n limits interpretation.	M=3.70 (n=20).

#	Recommendation	Literature Standard	Current Practice Gap (Q1-Q14)	Effectiveness Evidence (Q15/Q16)	Feasibility Evidence (Q18)	Perceived Effectiveness (Q20)
		fixed pay scales. This study applies the established 30% benchmark specifically to supervisory positions.				
R2.4	Establish indoor or semi-private task assignments, documenting the documented social stigma against women's outdoor labour at the programme design stage.	Loewe et al. (2020, pp. 104-106) note that visibility and stigma attached to women performing public work are the main reasons for low participation in public-space tasks. ILO (2024, p.37): incomplete programme sensitivity, including dignified working conditions.	Q5: 57% of programmes operated in mostly public/open spaces; camps are highest at 67%. Q6: 65% (n=15) reported culturally acceptable work or worksite arrangements, indicating social norms are recognised but not consistently addressed through task design.	Q15: work type selected by 52% (n=12). Q16: selected by 48% (n=11) as top participation measure.	M=2.55 (n=11), difficult to implement.	M=4.08 (n=12).
R3.1	Standardise a fixed morning-only schedule of up to 6 hours as the default, with	BNLWG (2020, s. 2.1): Azraq SOP caps daily working hours at six and requires that hours be	Q7 (n=21): 81% use fixed morning-only schedule; 19% (n=4) reported flexible shifts, exclusively in	Q15: flexible schedule selected by 17% (n=4) as top	M = 2.67 (n = 3) approximates the scale midpoint.	M=3.65 (n=20).

#	Recommendation	Literature Standard	Current Practice Gap (Q1-Q14)	Effectiveness Evidence (Q15/Q16)	Feasibility Evidence (Q18)	Perceived Effectiveness (Q20)
	flexible shifts as an opt-in alternative in camp settings only.	specified in job advertisements. Flexible shifts are an SOP provision in camp settings.	camp settings. Both-settings and host-community programmes reported only fixed schedules with no flexible option.	completion measure. Q16: selected by 13% (n=3) as top participation measure.		
R3.2	Prioritise neighbourhood-level worksite proximity in site selection decisions.	Loewe et al. (2020, p. 136, 161): women cited CfW as attractive specifically because it was close to home; proximity reduces transport costs and harassment risk. ILO (2021, p.32): transport availability and combining work with domestic responsibilities were the most consistent barriers.	Q8: responses are almost evenly split, 52% (n=12) within the same neighbourhood, 48% (n=11) in the same city. No strong setting pattern; site selection appears driven by availability rather than proximity criteria.	Q15: worksite proximity selected by 70% (n=16) as top completion measure, highest of all measures. Q16: selected by 39% (n=9) as top participation measure.	M=2.44 (n=9), lowest feasibility rating, indicating most difficult to implement. Highest effectiveness, lowest feasibility: the core effectiveness-feasibility gap.	M=4.36 (n=14), second-highest Q20 score.
R3.3	Provide organised transport or a cash	ILO (2021, p.32): Transport availability is the	Q9: 61% (n=14) did not provide any transport	Q15: Transport support was	M=4.20 (n=5), the highest feasibility	M=4.00 (n=17).

#	Recommendation	Literature Standard	Current Practice Gap (Q1-Q14)	Effectiveness Evidence (Q15/Q16)	Feasibility Evidence (Q18)	Perceived Effectiveness (Q20)
	transport allowance where worksite proximity cannot be achieved; assess proximity first before defaulting to transport.	most consistent barrier. Loewe et al. (2020, pp.136- 139): delays and transport uncertainty undermine household trust and programme continuity.	support. Among those that did (39%, n=9), organised transport was the most common (n=6, 26%). Q17: transport cost and safety constraints cited by only 9% (n=2), indicating budget limits (61%) as the main barrier to provision.	selected by 30% (n=7) as the top completion measure. Q16: selected by 22% (n=5) as top participation measure.	rating of any logistical measure; high effect and high feasibility when implemented.	
R3.4	Pilot onsite childcare or childcare allowance (camp settings first).	World Bank (2024b, p.7): formal childcare reaches less than 3% of children under five in Jordan; care obligations push women out of paid work. The UN Women Jordan Office (2024, p. 35) identified childcare as a shared barrier across both settings.	Q10: only 17% of programmes (n=4) provided any childcare support; all four were camp programmes (0% in both-settings and host communities). Q17: Budget limits (61%) and limited local childcare options (26%) are the primary constraints.	Q15: Childcare support was selected by 9% (n=2) as the top completion measure. Q16: not selected by any respondent as an implemented top participation measure (0%).	In Q18 ratings, childcare was not selected as an implemented top three Q16 measure by any respondent.	M=4.00 (n=22, 1 DK excluded), broad recognition of value despite near-absent provision.

#	Recommendation	Literature Standard	Current Practice Gap (Q1-Q14)	Effectiveness Evidence (Q15/Q16)	Feasibility Evidence (Q18)	Perceived Effectiveness (Q20)
R3.5	Formalise inter-agency minimum childcare standards within the BNLWG SOP revision process.	BNLWG (2020, 2022): camp SOPs govern IBV programme standards comprehensively but contain no specifications on childcare facility type, caregiver ratio, or proximity requirements.	Q10: 44% of camp programmes (n=4) provided some childcare, all four in camps; no consistent or standardised approach. BNLWG SOP governance covers all other worksite standards; the absence of childcare standards is a gap in an otherwise regulated framework.	N/A	N/A	N/A
R3.6	Pilot a women-as-caregivers CfW model employing women as on-site caregivers for participating mothers.	An exploratory proposition derived from childcare findings (Q10) and World Bank (2024b) evidence on childcare demand. Not derived from a documented implementation gap. Not yet documented as a tested model in the Jordanian context.	Q10: all 4 programmes that provided childcare were camps; none employed women as caregivers under CfW contracts. The model is not observed in current practice.	N/A	N/A	N/A

#	Recommendation	Literature Standard	Current Practice Gap (Q1-Q14)	Effectiveness Evidence (Q15/Q16)	Feasibility Evidence (Q18)	Perceived Effectiveness (Q20)
R3.7	National childcare infrastructure expansion (policy-dependent).	World Bank (2024b, p.7): 7.3pp increase in women's labour force participation estimated if childcare is provided free of charge; most districts have no licensed facilities. World Bank EWEO operation identifies childcare infrastructure as a core policy investment gap.	Q10: 83% of programmes (n=19) provided no childcare support. Q17: limited childcare options cited as a constraint by 26% (n=6). The main limitation is beyond programme-level resolution.	N/A	N/A	N/A
R4.1	Record onboarding and safety briefings as a monitored SOP compliance item.	BNLWG (2020, s. 5; 2022, s. 5); ILO (2022, pp. 40-45): safety and protection measures can be mandated through SOPs and procurement requirements. Onboarding briefings are a standard SOP requirement in camps.	Q11: Onboarding and safety briefings were reported by 78% (n=18) overall, but only 56% of camp programmes, despite the SOP requirement. Host communities (100%) exceeded camps on this item, a reversal of	Q15: Code of conduct and induction was selected by 9% (n=2) as the top completion measure. Q16: selected by 9% (n=2) as top	Code of conduct and induction: M=1.00 (n=2), both who implemented it rated it very difficult.	M=4.00 (n=21).

#	Recommendation	Literature Standard	Current Practice Gap (Q1-Q14)	Effectiveness Evidence (Q15/Q16)	Feasibility Evidence (Q18)	Perceived Effectiveness (Q20)
			the expected regulatory pattern.	participation measure.		
R4.2	Integrate private rest and prayer space into the minimum SOP requirements and host communities contracts.	BNLWG (2020, s. 5; 2022, s. 5): SOP minimum standards cover worksite facilities. ILO (2024, pp. 33, 37): evaluators documented worksites lacking adequate gender-sensitive facilities, including rest spaces.	Q11: private rest and prayer space was the least reported worksite feature (52%, n=12), meaning 48% of programmes lacked it. Not specified as a mandatory standard in host communities contracts.	Q15: gender-sensitive facilities selected by 13% (n=3) as top completion measure. Q16: selected by 4% (n=1) as top participation measure.	Gender-sensitive facilities: M=2.00 (n=1), very small n, interpret with caution.	M=4.41 (n=22), the highest Q20 score of any measure across the full dataset.
R4.3	Embed gender-sensitive facility standards as a pass/fail criterion in worksite pre-commencement assessments.	ILO (2024, pp. 39-40): independent evaluators documented specific violations in Jordan, including the lack of drinking water and toilets at worksites. ILO (2024, pp.33, 37): sensitivity to women's needs, including dignified	Q11: Separate toilets 74%, drinking water 70%, PPE 87%. Private rest and prayer space is lowest at 52%. High self-reported rates may mask compliance gaps given persistent participation shortfalls.	Q15: gender-sensitive facilities selected by 13% (n=3). Q16: selected by 4% (n=1).	Gender-sensitive facilities: M=2.00 (n=1). Small n; facility standards not tested as a Q16 measure in most programmes.	M=4.41 (n=22), strongest perceived effectiveness across the dataset.

#	Recommendation	Literature Standard	Current Practice Gap (Q1-Q14)	Effectiveness Evidence (Q15/Q16)	Feasibility Evidence (Q18)	Perceived Effectiveness (Q20)
		working conditions, remained incomplete.				
R4.4	Require host communities contracts to mandate a confidential grievance mechanism with two entry points and a non-supervisory focal point.	BNLWG (2020, s. 5.6; 2022, s. 5): camp SOPs require at least two reporting channels, a non-supervisory focal point, an enrolment briefing, and a three-week response time. No equivalent standard exists in host communities contract frameworks.	Q11: Confidential reporting channels are present in 78% (n=18) of programmes overall. Setting-disaggregated data (Appendix B, Tab. 14) reveal a gap between the camp SOP standard and host communities practice. Q14: grievances tracked by type by only 26% (n=6).	Q15: grievance channel not selected by any respondent as a top completion measure (0%). Q16: not selected by any respondent (0%).	No Q18 ratings, grievance channel not a Q16 selectable measure.	M=3.90 (n=21, 2 DK excluded).
R4.5	Enforce code of conduct and harassment-prevention protocols at all worksites. This composite indicator is	BNLWG (2020, s.5; 2022, s.5): code of conduct and harassment prevention mandated as SOP minimums. ILO (2022, pp.40-45): SOPs and	Q11: Code of conduct reported by 74% (n=17) and harassment prevention by 74% (n=17), indicating 26% of programmes lack these protections. ILO	Q15: Code of conduct and induction selected by 9% (n=2). Q16: selected by 9% (n=2).	Code of conduct and induction: M=1.00 (n=2), both rated as very difficult, suggesting the gap is	M=4.00 (n=21).

#	Recommendation	Literature Standard	Current Practice Gap (Q1-Q14)	Effectiveness Evidence (Q15/Q16)	Feasibility Evidence (Q18)	Perceived Effectiveness (Q20)
	proposed as a supplementary management metric in addition to the 16-indicator framework and requires testing before adoption.	procurement requirements can mandate these protections.	(2024, pp.39-40) documented compliance gaps in Jordan through an independent evaluation.		in enforcement, not adoption.	
R5.1	Verify at enrolment that the mobile wallet/account is registered in the woman's name.	BNLWG (2022, s. 3): Za'atari SOP requires that all payments be recorded in RAIS. GIZ (2022, pp.15, 28): Without rules about account ownership, direct payments do not guarantee women control their wages. ILO (2021, p.27): payment modality is a financial-control variable.	Q12: mobile wallets used by 100% of camp programmes (n=9). Q13: Despite universal mobile wallet use in camps, only 56% of camp programmes reported direct payment to women, compared to 91% in both-settings. Infrastructure was adopted without follow-through on account ownership.	Q15: direct payment to women selected by 22% (n=5) as the top completion measure. Q16: selected by 13% (n=3) as top participation measure.	Direct payment: M=3.67 (n=3), rated in a feasible range.	M=4.00 (n=19).

#	Recommendation	Literature Standard	Current Practice Gap (Q1-Q14)	Effectiveness Evidence (Q15/Q16)	Feasibility Evidence (Q18)	Perceived Effectiveness (Q20)
R5.2	Provide digital payment literacy training at enrolment.	GIZ (2022, pp. 3, 7, 28): 63% of mobile payment users in Jordan are male, 37% female; 42% of women reported worrying about mistakes with mobile technology; women's mobile wallet ownership lagged men's by 22 pp in 2022.	Q12: Mobile wallets are dominant overall (74%) and universal in camps (100%). Q13: Direct payment to women is only 56% in camps despite full digital infrastructure. The gap between digital payment adoption and women's effective financial control is measurable in this sample.	N/A	N/A	N/A
R5.3	Offer cash or pre-paid card payment as an opt-in alternative for women who indicate digital modality poses household control or safety risks, without requiring justification.	GIZ (2022, pp. 15, 28): women separated from partners raised concerns about partners monitoring or accessing their mobile accounts. ILO (2021, p.27): payment modality is a financial control decision. Cash at the worksite	Q12: cash used by 35% (n=8) and prepaid debit cards by 17% (n=4), indicating alternatives exist but are not systematically offered as opt-in. Q13: direct payment to women only 78% overall, 56% in camps.	Q15: direct payment selected by 22% (n=5). Q16: selected by 13% (n=3).	Direct payment: M=3.67 (n=3).	M=4.00 (n=19).

#	Recommendation	Literature Standard	Current Practice Gap (Q1-Q14)	Effectiveness Evidence (Q15/Q16)	Feasibility Evidence (Q18)	Perceived Effectiveness (Q20)
		may give more effective control than a monitored mobile wallet.				
R5.4	Specify timely payment as a KPI in all contracts with corrective measures for delays.	Loewe et al. (2020, pp. 136, 139): payment delays undermine household trust and undermine the confidence that digital payment systems are meant to guarantee. ILO (2021, p. 27) documents payment timeliness as a practical implementation constraint.	Q13: Timely payment was reported by 78% overall, but only 56% of camp programmes, the same setting that has achieved full mobile wallet adoption. Four of five respondents who did not select timely payment had selected mobile wallets, showing that digital adoption does not guarantee timeliness. Q14: Payment timeliness was tracked by only 43% (n=10).	Q15: Payment timeliness was not selected by any respondent as a top completion measure (0%). Q16: not selected (0%).	In the Q18 ratings, payment timeliness is not a selectable measure in Q16.	M = 3.83 (n = 23); all respondents rated this measure.
R5.5	Link payment timeliness verification to	BNLWG (2022, s.3): all payments must be	Q14: Payment timeliness was tracked by only 43%	N/A	N/A	N/A

#	Recommendation	Literature Standard	Current Practice Gap (Q1-Q14)	Effectiveness Evidence (Q15/Q16)	Feasibility Evidence (Q18)	Perceived Effectiveness (Q20)
	RAIS recording system (camps).	recorded in RAIS. Researcher monitoring knowledge: RAIS system capacity to support payment timeliness tracking identified as an underused verification mechanism, validated through Q14 findings showing low timeliness tracking rates.	(n=10) of programmes. In camps where RAIS already records payment data, linking timeliness verification to existing recording infrastructure is a low-cost extension of current practice.			
R6.1	Track pipeline-stage indicators: women applicants, selected, starters, completers, early exits with reasons.	ILO (2021, p.35-36) Key Lesson 4: monitoring must go beyond counting jobs and build an evidence base for future planning. ILO (2024, pp.47-52) calls for specific tracking at each stage of the participation pipeline. DEval (2021, pp.8-9): gender-sensitive process	Q14: women selected tracked by 83% (n=19), but women applicants tracked by only 43% (n=10) and women starters by only 39% (n=9), the two lowest tracking rates in the dataset. More than half of the programmes had no visibility	N/A	N/A	N/A

#	Recommendation	Literature Standard	Current Practice Gap (Q1-Q14)	Effectiveness Evidence (Q15/Q16)	Feasibility Evidence (Q18)	Perceived Effectiveness (Q20)
		indicators are often weak or missing.	into how many women reached the entry stage.			
R6.2	Record women excluded at the documentation stage as a routine pipeline indicator.	Researcher monitoring knowledge: documentation exclusions were identified as an invisible pre-entry dropout category not captured in any of the reviewed monitoring systems.	Q2: Exclusion risk screening was used by only 39% (n=9), indicating that most programmes have no visibility into upstream exclusion. The scale of exclusion before selection begins is entirely unmeasured.	N/A	N/A	N/A
R6.3	Incorporate payment timeliness, gender-sensitive worksite checklist results, and grievances disaggregated by type into the standard monthly monitoring report.	ILO (2024, pp.47-52) calls for stronger monitoring of programme processes. DEval (2021, pp.8-9): gender-sensitive process indicators are often weak or missing in Jordan CfW evaluations.	Q14: payment timeliness tracked by 43% (n=10); gender-sensitive worksite checklist tracked by only 26% (n=6); grievances by type tracked by only 26% (n=6). None tracked in host-community	N/A	N/A	N/A

#	Recommendation	Literature Standard	Current Practice Gap (Q1-Q14)	Effectiveness Evidence (Q15/Q16)	Feasibility Evidence (Q18)	Perceived Effectiveness (Q20)
			programmes (Appendix B, Tab.15).			
R6.4	Deploy a standardised exit form with pre-coded dropout categories (household opposition, care responsibilities, transport, worksite conditions, payment, health) and an open “other” field.	Researcher monitoring knowledge: the seven pre-coded dropout categories were formulated by this study from the barrier typology documented in Chapter 2 (household opposition, care responsibilities, transport/safety, worksite conditions, payment, health, other). The categories are a proposed instrument, not derived from a measured tracking gap.	Q14: dropout reasons tracked by 61% (n=14), the highest tracking rate below the completion-stage indicators. However, tracking <i>whether</i> reasons exist differs from tracking <i>categorised</i> reasons that can be linked to design decisions, and Q14 did not capture whether reasons were recorded in categorised form. The seven-category exit form is the proposed addition.	N/A	N/A	N/A
R6.5	Track a core package indicator:	Researcher monitoring knowledge: an aggregate	Q14: Individual gender-design measures are	N/A	N/A	N/A

#	Recommendation	Literature Standard	Current Practice Gap (Q1-Q14)	Effectiveness Evidence (Q15/Q16)	Feasibility Evidence (Q18)	Perceived Effectiveness (Q20)
	number of gender-sensitive design measures implemented per reporting cycle.	design-quality indicator identified as absent from the monitoring frameworks reviewed in the Jordan CfW sector; proposed as a novel composite measure requiring testing.	tracked in isolation (worksite checklist: 26%; grievances: 26%) and are never aggregated into a programme-level design-quality score. A composite indicator was not among the items surveyed.			
R6.6	Require MEAL staff to distribute a one-page pipeline summary to programme managers and field officers at the closing of each reporting cycle.	Researcher monitoring knowledge: internal distribution mechanism identified as the structural response to the knowledge circulation gap documented in Q21. not identified in the evaluations reviewed for this study.	Q21: 27% of programme managers (n=3 of 11) could not state their own programme's participation target or achieved rate. Data is being collected but not reaching decision-makers. The problem is circulation, not collection.	N/A	N/A	N/A
R6.7	Require field officers to submit weekly attendance and	DEval (2021); ILO (2024, pp.47-52): data submission gaps between field	Q14: Dropout reasons were tracked by 61%, but without standardised	N/A	N/A	N/A

#	Recommendation	Literature Standard	Current Practice Gap (Q1-Q14)	Effectiveness Evidence (Q15/Q16)	Feasibility Evidence (Q18)	Perceived Effectiveness (Q20)
	dropout logs to the central MEAL system using a standardised form.	and central systems identified as a monitoring weakness. Researcher monitoring knowledge: weekly standardised submission identified as the structural fix.	categorisation or submission protocols. Role-based analysis showed field officers reported lower monitoring awareness than programme managers, suggesting field-to-centre data flows are inconsistent.			
R6.8	Require programme managers to report participation target, achieved rate, and dropout reasons to the lead agency at each reporting cycle as a named deliverable; flag non-submission or unknown responses as a performance issue.	Researcher monitoring knowledge derived from Q21 finding. Not identified as a named accountability requirement in the evaluations reviewed for this study in Jordan.	Q21: 27% of programme managers (n=3 of 11) could not state both their target and achieved rate. Both-settings programmes showed the highest rate of unknown participation figures (36%). Making upward reporting a named, tracked deliverable directly	N/A	N/A	N/A

#	Recommendation	Literature Standard	Current Practice Gap (Q1-Q14)	Effectiveness Evidence (Q15/Q16)	Feasibility Evidence (Q18)	Perceived Effectiveness (Q20)
			addresses the knowledge-circulation failure.			

Appendix E: Data Cleaning and Coding Log

Tab. 31. Data cleaning and coding decisions (n=23)

No.	Response ID	Variable(s) affected	Original value	Action taken	Justification and rule applied
Section 1 - Data entry correction (n=1)					
1	Not available	target population delivery_setting	target_population="Mixed Jordanians and Syrians" delivery_setting="Refugee camp"	Recoded to target_population="Syrians only"	Jordanian nationals do not reside in Jordan's Syrian refugee camps (Azraq and Za'atari). The combination is factually impossible and indicates a selection error at the point of response. Recoding applies the correct population category consistent with the stated delivery setting. This is the only instance in the 23-response dataset where this combination appears. The correction was made before any analysis.
Section 2 - Internal consistency exclusions from Q19 (n=2)					
2	R_9fxETIVqGUksx3l	q19_uptake_rate_change_num q19_completion_rate_change_num	Uptake=5 (Much higher) Completion=5 (Much higher) Dropout raw=5 (Much higher dropout)	Excluded from all Q19 analyses. Q19 n reduced to 21.	The dropout item asks how the dropout rate changed following implementation. Higher dropout is an unfavourable outcome. The respondent rated both uptake and completion as "Much higher" (positive direction) but simultaneously rated dropout as "Much higher" (raw=5),

No.	Response ID	Variable(s) affected	Original value	Action taken	Justification and rule applied
		q19_dropout_rate_change_raw q19_dropout_rate_change_rev_num	Dropout reversed=1		indicating a large increase in dropout. This is incompatible: a programme cannot simultaneously achieve strongly improved completion and a large increase in dropout. The pattern indicates misinterpretation of the scale direction on the only reverse-coded item in Q19. Per standard response quality criteria, the full Q19 response set was excluded rather than selectively retaining other items, as partial retention would require unwarranted assumptions about which items within the same response set are reliable (see Section 3.8).
3	R_8umkDMO3A3P1NTP	q19_uptake_rate_change_num q19_completion_rate_change_num q19_dropout_rate_change_raw	Uptake=2 (Slightly lower) Completion=1 (Much lower) Dropout raw=1 (Much lower dropout) Dropout reversed=5	Excluded from all Q19 analyses. Q19 n reduced to 21.	The respondent rated uptake as "Slightly lower" and completion as "Much lower" (in the negative direction), while simultaneously rating dropout as "Much lower" (raw=1), indicating a large reduction in dropout. A programme with substantially worsening uptake and completion cannot simultaneously achieve a large reduction in dropout. This again indicates misinterpretation of the reverse-coded item scale direction.

No.	Response ID	Variable(s) affected	Original value	Action taken	Justification and rule applied
		q19_dropout_rate_change_rev_num			The same exclusion rule as Decision 2 was applied.
Section 3 - Mid-collection instrument revision affecting Q7 (n=2)					
4	R_9tgpzOmLOeUSLek R_8eW0x6JByQyQcYo	q7_daily_schedule q7_daily_schedule_code	Selected original response option: "Fixed daily schedule" (legacy category, code=9)	Excluded from Q7 analysis only. Q7 analytical base=n=21. All other variables for these respondents were retained.	An early version of Q7 included an undifferentiated "Fixed daily schedule" option alongside a separate "Morning only - Fixed" option. Following respondent feedback during data collection indicating ambiguity, the options were revised, and the question was harmonised. The two responses coded 9 (legacy) pre-date this revision and cannot be reliably classified as either "Morning only - Fixed" or another schedule type without making assumptions that the data do not support. Excluding them from Q7 analysis only avoids misclassification while preserving all other data from these respondents. The exclusion does not materially change Q7's descriptive interpretation (Section 4.4).

Source: Own representation. All decisions documented in this log were applied before any analytical outputs reported in Chapters 4 and 5.

Tab. 32. Coding conventions applied to the full dataset

Item type	Original Qual- trics format	Coded as	Notes
Single-choice items	Text response labels	Categorical variable; numeric code as- signed per category	Code scheme documented in column headers of analyti- cal CSV (e.g., <code>delivery_setting_code</code>)
Multiple-select items	Multi-response text fields	Binary indicator variables: 1=selected, 0=not selected; one variable per re- sponse option	Variable names follow the pattern: <code>q[number]_[option]</code> . To- tals may exceed <code>n</code> due to multi-selection.
Matrix Likert items	1–5 scale labels (e.g., Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree)	Ordered numeric 1–5; stored as integer	Reverse-coded items identified in variable name suffix (<code>_rev</code>). Q19 dropout item reverse-coded so higher=more favourable (lower dropout).
Numeric items (Q21)	0–100 free-entry percentage	Continuous variable (0–100 scale); gap computed as achieved minus target (percentage points)	"I don't know" is treated as missing for gap computation; cases with unknown target or actual are excluded from gap analysis (see Section 3.9).
"I don't know" responses	Text option alongside scale	Retained as a distinct reportable cate- gory; not imputed or treated as missing	Applied in Q14, Q20, and Q21. Contextual interpretation is documented in Section 3.9.

Source: Own representation. All decisions documented in this log were applied before any analytical outputs reported in Chapters 4 and 5.

Declaration of Authenticity

I hereby declare that I have completed this master's thesis on my own, without any external assistance. I have used only the specified sources and aids, and I have listed all sources from which I have extracted text and content. This thesis, or any part of it, has not been presented to another examination board. I agree to a plagiarism check of my thesis via a plagiarism detection service.

Amman, Jordan, 29.04.2026

Nora Al Borini

